

D4.2 Grassroot Needs & Factors of Rural Attractiveness

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Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

Table of Contents

List of Tables	6
List of Figures	7
Executive Summary	9
Keywords	9
1 Introduction.....	10
1.1 Policy context	12
1.2 Project context	14
2 Methodological framework.....	15
2.1 Literature study of rural attractiveness	15
2.2 Survey of rural attractiveness in pilot regions	15
2.3 SWOT analysis to summarise the results from literature study and survey.....	20
2.4 Regional needs assessment	20
3 Grass roots needs analysis	21
3.1 Survey results analysis and pre-clustering.....	21
3.1.1 Pre-clustering of regions based on survey results	26
3.2 Recognising the rural needs through SWOT analysis.....	35
3.3 Regional clustering based on needs assessment.....	54
3.3.1 Quality of life	55
3.3.2 Social capital.....	58
3.3.3 Cultural diversity	61
3.3.4 Natural capital	63
4 Challenges	65
5 Conclusions.....	67
Bibliography.....	72
Annex 1. Survey about rural attractiveness in PoliRural pilot regions.....	73
Annex 2. Guidance for SWOT analysis and needs assessment	76
Annex 3. Links to regional pilot surveys.....	82
Annex 4. Survey tool guide	83
Annex 5. Survey results.....	94
Annex 6. PILOTS' SWOT	101
Annex 7. Pilot's List of Needs	125

Annex 8. Panel Workshop comments	147
Annex 9 SWOT Indicators	155
Annex 10 Responses to the Monitors' Comments and Advisory Board Review.....	184

List of Tables

Table 1. Survey Participants per pilot	21
Table 2. Pillar 1 Availability of public and other services. Compilation SWOT	38
Table 3. Pillar 2 Recreational and social activities. Compilation SWOT	41
Table 4. Pillar 3 Living conditions and quality of life. Compilation SWOT	43
Table 5. Pillar 4 Demographic and human capital. Compilation SWOT	45
Table 6. Pillar 5 Business, economy and innovation. Compilation SWOT	47
Table 7. Pillar 6 Social and cultural aspects. Compilation SWOT	51
Table 8. Pillar 7 Environment and biodiversity. Compilation SWOT	52
Table 9. Battery of proposed questions for the survey	74
Table 10. SWOT	78
Table 11. Comments to the SWOT	79
Table 12. List of Needs	80
Table 13. Results of the Discussions with Panel: (Mainly ideas)	81
Table 14. Numbers of responses by age and gender	94
Table 15. Numbers of responses by category / organization	95
Table 16. Number of responses by question's numbers	96
Table 17. Flanders / BELGIUM SWOT	101
Table 18. Central Bohemian / CZECH REPUBLIC SWOT	102
Table 19. SLOVAKIA SWOT	105
Table 20. Häme / FINLAND	107
Table 21. Central Greece / GREECE SWOT	110
Table 22. Monaghan / IRELAND SWOT	112
Table 23. Galilee / ISRAEL SWOT	113
Table 24. Apulia / ITALY SWOT	115
Table 25. Vidzeme / LATVIA SWOT	116

Table 26. Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM SWOT	119
Table 27. Mazowieckie / POLAND SWOT.....	122
Table 28. Segóbriga / SPAIN SWOT.....	123
Table 29. Flanders / BELGIUM Needs	125
Table 30. Central Bohemian / CZR Needs	126
Table 31. Slovakia Needs.....	128
Table 32. Häme/Finland Needs.....	130
Table 33. Central Greece/Greece Needs	132
Table 34. Monaghan / Ireland Needs	134
Table 35. Galilee/ Israel Needs	135
Table 36. Apulia / Italy Needs	136
Table 37. Vidzeme / Latvia Needs.....	138
Table 38. Gevgelija-Strumica /-FYROM Needs.....	141
Table 39. Mazowieckie / Poland Needs	143
Table 40. Segóbriga / Spain Needs	144
Table 41. Flanders / BELGIUM SWOT Indicators	155
Table 42. Central Bohemian / CZECH REPUBLIC SWOT Indicators	155
Table 43. SLOVAKIA SWOT Indicators	157
Table 44. Häme / FINLAND SWOT Indicators.....	158
Table 45. Central Greece / GREECE SWOT Indicators.....	159
Table 46. Monaghan / IRELAND SWOT Indicators	164
Table 47. Galilee / ISRAEL SWOT Indicators	165
Table 48. Apulia / ITALY SWOT Indicators	166
Table 49. Vidzeme / LATVIA SWOT Indicators	167
Table 50. Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM SWOT Indicators	174
Table 51. Mazowieckie / POLAND SWOT Indicators.....	182
Table 52. Segóbriga / SPAIN SWOT Indicators.....	183

List of Figures

Figure 1. Age Range Distribution	22
Figure 2. Survey gender distribution.....	23

Figure 3. Survey category distribution	24
Figure 4. Survey organisation distribution	25
Figure 5. Survey Result: Availability of public and other services	27
Figure 6. Survey Results: Recreational and social activities	29
Figure 7. Survey Results: Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	30
Figure 8. Survey Results: Demographic & human capital	31
Figure 9. Survey Results: Business, economy & innovation	32
Figure 10. Survey Results: Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	33
Figure 11. Survey Results: Environment & biodiversity	34
Figure 12. Pillar 1 prioritized needs cluster map: Availability of public and other services	56
Figure 13. Pillar 3 prioritized needs cluster map: Living conditions and quality of life	57
Figure 14. Pillar 4 prioritized needs cluster map: Demographic and human capital	59
Figure 15. Pillar 5 prioritized needs cluster map: Business, economy and innovation	60
Figure 16. Pillar 2 prioritized needs cluster map: Recreational and social activities	62
Figure 17. Pillar 6 prioritized needs cluster map: Social and cultural aspects	62
Figure 18. Pillar 7 prioritized needs cluster map: Environment and biodiversity	64
Figure 19. Quality of life needs cluster map.	68
Figure 20. Social capital needs cluster map.	69
Figure 21. Cultural diversity needs cluster map	70
Figure 22. Natural capital needs cluster map.	71

Executive Summary

This report on Grassroots needs and factors of rural attractiveness developed in collaboration with the Polirural regional pilots, provides a deeper understanding on what are those aspects that makes rural areas attractive or unattractive with a view to their particular contexts (quality of life, cultural diversity , natural capital and social capital), for established populations and recent or potential newcomers.

This report seeks the updating of pilots' knowledge of rural reality, through PoliRural's survey and also interactive workshops with the regional stakeholder's panels.

Different factors of attractiveness have been identified with commonalities for the different pilots, many have a cross-cutting consideration with regard to: digitalisation, green economy and women and youth participation are seen as crucial factors and thus there is a need to work on their enhancement.

Commonalities and differences with regard to individual framework conditions and policy challenges at EU level have been identified, which have allowed to cluster and/or re-cluster of pilots based on common needs rather than geography.

Keywords

Rural needs, rural attractiveness, social capital, natural capital, economic development

1 Introduction

Rural areas represent most of Europe's territory (91%) and population (59%) (REDR, 2019). When measuring against socio-economic indicators rural areas tend to lag behind urban areas. The urbanisation processes that have occurred in the EU and other areas at global level have promoted sustained changes in the rural areas in the last decades. Lower population and business density make it more challenging to develop private businesses and public services in rural areas. Now, with the undergoing process of digitalisation of the society and the economy, rural areas across Europe are undergoing rapid change. The connectiveness, and the increase of virtual interactions and the enhanced exchange of information and knowledge contains risk but also real opportunity for rural areas to play a new and distinct role.

One of the most valuable characteristics of the EU is that related to the differences with regard to, history, culture, habits, capacities, abilities, among other, that all together bring the strength of the region, however PoliRural will provide a set of knowledge resources including an inclusive learning environment where rural populations, researchers and policymakers come together to address common problems.

This deliverable summarises the findings obtained in needs gathering exercise T4.3 Regional needs gathering and analysis. The exercise oriented to assess the needs of rural areas, was carried out simultaneously in the 12 pilot areas of the PoliRural project. Regional stakeholder panels in all pilot regions attended to this task in co-operation with project partners.

While this task is considered to be of great importance for the correct development of other activities considered in the POLIRURAL project, it was requested to the POLIRURAL Steering Group a schedule modification in task T4.2, T4.3 and T4.4. At this regard, the following proposal for the delivery of the task activities was presented to the Steering Committee:

“The work plan proposal to fulfil the Task 4.3 agreed activities seem to be very tight within the timeframe proposed in the Grant agreement. Two work plan proposals are set at the end of this document with regard to two different scenarios. One scenario that allows to fulfil the calendar restrictions, although will not allow to have a final report of sufficient quality; and a second scenario which should allow to develop the agreed activities with time enough to engage key stakeholders at regional pilots’ level, reflect the different inputs from regional pilots and have a final report (D4.2) of high quality and very useful for further development of Polirural outcomes.

It is proposed to develop a survey questionnaire following the guidelines set in D1.3. the questionnaire should cover the 7 pillars observed in the guidelines. The questionnaire should have a core basis of questions, no more than 40 in total, that should be valid for all the regional pilots with the possibility of setting two optional questions per pilot. It should be used the proposed scoring 1-5, although a combination of quantitative scoring should be considered in order to allow a stronger homogenisation and higher quality of the survey results. The survey should be developed online, with preference making use of the EC online free survey tool as

proposed in D1.3 and users friendly, taking into consideration the different categories of stakeholders that should answer the survey.

The targeted stakeholders per category (policy makers, rural population, recent entrants and potential entrants to rural areas, experts and innovators) should be identified by each regional pilot leader. At this regard, the Task leader (Tragsa) will provide an estimation of the targeted number of survey participants expected per regional pilot, at least two weeks prior to the survey launch.”

Scenario 1 for Task 4.3 (LEAD Tragsa) work plan with deadline M10

- Task start: 01/12/2019
- Telco for task arrangements and task work plan discussion (with all task participants): 05/12/2019
- Preparation of questionnaire for online survey following D1.3: 13/12/2019
- Finalisation of questionnaire (translation into different languages by each task country participant): 20/12/2019
- Survey launch: 06/01/2020
- Desk research on existing literature and data mining making use of D1.3 and D1.1: 05/12/2019-11/01/2020
- Survey follow-up and monitoring: 06/01/2020-19/01/2020
- End of survey period and collection and data analysis: 20/01/2020-10/02/2020
- Draft development of SWOT analysis and discussion with regional panels: 10/02/2020-28/02/2020
- 1st Draft D4.2 Grass roots needs and factors of rural attractiveness: 9/03/2020
- Draft revision by Task participants: 09/03/2020-16/03/2020
- Final report for Task 4.3 (D4.2): 31/03/2020

Scenario 2 for Task 4.3 (LEAD Tragsa) work plan proposal with extended deadline M12

- Task start: 01/12/2019
- Telco for task arrangements and task work plan discussion (with all task participants): 05/12/2019
- Preparation of draft online survey questionnaire following D1.3: 16/12/2019
- Circulation of draft questionnaire among pilot leaders for revision and comments also from key stakeholders at regional pilots 16/12/2019-13/01/2020.
- Consolidation of draft questionnaire revision and finalisation of Questionnaire in English 17/01/2020
- Circulation among pilot regions leader for translation into different languages by each task country participant): 17/01/2020-24/01/2020
- Survey launch: 27/01/2020
- Desk research on existing literature and data mining making use of D1.3 and D1.1: 05/12/2019-27/01/2020
- Survey follow-up and monitoring: 27/01/2020-14/02/2020
- End of survey period: 14/02/2020
- Surveys data collection and analysis: 17/02/2020-28/02/2020
- Draft development of SWOT analysis and discussion with regional panels: 02/03/2020-17/04/2020
- 1st Draft D4.2 Grass roots needs and factors of rural attractiveness: 30/04/2020

- Draft revision by Task participants: 30/04/2020-15/05/2020
- Final report for Task 4.3 (D4.2): 31/05/2020

Finally, it was agreed that the most convenient scenario was number 2. It is important to take into account that the work was fully developed while the COVID crisis occurred.

This extension allowed the identification of needs to be carried out adequately and in a comprehensive manner, giving all pilots the opportunity to carry out a participatory process to identify and prioritize those most relevant needs in their territories. The collection of policies and measures was carried out once the needs identification phase was completed. Good communication and coordination between the Task leader (Tragsa) team and the WP4 Leader happened, who was responsible for the compilation of policies and measures, made it possible for the information flow and work to be done more efficiently.

Taking into account the existing literature in the field of regional development and smart specialisation, a common methodology based on a template with relevant research questions, a coordinated framework for secondary data, included big/unstructured data, as well as questionnaires and question guides, have been provided and made available to pilot leaders.

The findings from survey and its comparison with existing official indicators have been summarised in a draft SWOT analysis in each pilot region. According to project plan in the Grant Agreement, the results of SWOT analysis were to be discussed with regional stakeholder panels and pilot partners. Due to COVID19 pandemic (declared by WHO from 11 March 2020) and its consequences like restrictions to face-to-face meetings, pilot participants were forced to come up with new ways to work with stakeholders to replace face-to-face meetings.

The SWOT analysis and the interactive discussions have been carried out in parallel in all pilot regions. Due to the coordinated structure, it has been identified, in a secondary step, commonalities and differences with regard to individual framework conditions and policy challenges.

This task has therefore concluded with clustering or re-clustering of pilots rather based on common aspects or preferences expressed in the survey and the further analysis on needs assessment carried out in the different pilots, rather than geography.

This task will also look to feed the development of Task 4.4 on Needs-Policy mapping

1.1 Policy context

The Cork 2.0 Declaration states that the “participants of the Cork 2.0 European Conference on Rural Development, urge the policy makers of the European Union to:

Systematically review other macro and sectorial policies through a rural lens, considering potential and actual impacts and implications on rural jobs and growth and development prospects, social well-being, and the environmental quality of rural areas and communities;

Build on this momentum and further develop the agricultural and rural policy towards a result-oriented, simple, and flexible approach, based on partnership and reflecting Union objectives as well as the needs and aspirations on the ground;”

At this regard, Polirural T4.3 *Regional Needs Gathering and Analysis* is oriented to assess the grass roots needs and develop a clusterization of different EU regions based on their common needs identified through the combination of different research techniques: social analysis techniques (survey and participatory workshops) and desk research on existing related literature and indicators. However, it finally would not be possible to make use of the text mining tool as it was not ready during the period this task has been developed.

Also related to the above mentioned Cork Declaration: The needs quest is around seven areas to search on the needs on which refers to different sectorial policies:

1. Public goods and services
2. Recreational
3. Living conditions & standard of living
4. Demographics & human capital
5. Business, economy & innovation
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas
7. Environment & biodiversity

Despite the fact that the agricultural sector was not explicitly considered in any of the 7 pillars, the needs related to agricultural and livestock activity were subject of several comments in the debates with the agents of the territories linked to (5) Business, economy and innovation and (7) Environment and biodiversity areas.

This project is also developed within the context of different ongoing initiatives, like Smart Villages, that can be understood as communities that are made up of rural people who take the initiative to explore practical solutions to the underlying challenges they face and to seize new opportunities related to digital technologies, social innovation in rural services, new win-win relationships with urban areas, and activities which reinforce the role of rural areas in the transition to a greener, healthier and more caring society¹.

The needs assessment presented in this deliverable/report takes into consideration the main policies for the period 2014-2020, that have had a direct impact on the development of rural areas: EAFRD legal framework, Rural Development Programs, RIS3 strategies; Digital single market initiative. Also, the future policies that are being developed for the period 2021-2027 such as: CAP 2021-2027 legal proposal; EU Green Deal Strategy and Farm to Fork strategy for sustainable food.

It is as well relevant to build Polirural outcomes on other past or ongoing related EU projects. At this regard, different projects outcomes have been considered to develop these task activities, among others: Ruraljobs (FP7), Robust (2020), Ruritage (H2020) and Claim (FP7).

¹ EU RURAL REVIEW No 26. SMART VILLAGES REVITALISING RURAL SERVICES. Publications Office of the European Union, 2018. Available online: https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/sites/enrd/files/enrd_publications/publi-enrd-rr-26-2018-en.pdf

1.2 Project context

This deliverable is developed within the Polirural WP4 *Current rural situation*. The different interlinkages that exist among the different work packages makes that this deliverable and the task 4.3 on *Assessment of rural needs* is developed in coherence of the rest of foreseen activities to reach the overall proposed objectives. This task will also look to feed the development of Task 4.4 on Needs-Policy mapping.

In general, this deliverable has been performed making use of the cross-cutting areas and work packages, at this regard this report mainly makes use of:

Polirural Framework (WP1): This deliverable is based on the guidance provided by the Polirural *D1.3 Needs Gathering & Policy Mapping Template*. It has also been supported by PoliRural first review on the available literature on rural needs in every participating region (*D1.1 Envisioning More Attractive Rural Places & Professions*).

2 Methodological framework

The research performed to develop this task is based on a mixed methodology (Tashakorri and Teddlie, 2003) and multi-strategy research (Bryman, 2001). This comes to compromise the work with different types of data and different research methods. Mixed research methods are considered appropriate for those cases in which the object of the research demands an interdisciplinary approach.

Phases of research: The work, which has been planned in four phases, is structured in the analysis of grass roots needs of rural areas in Europe, to be performed in 12 different pilots' cases.

Phases of the needs gathering task can be summarized as following:

1. Literature study of rural attractiveness
2. Mass survey to stakeholder groups and general population of regional pilots
3. Findings of these surveys summarised to SWOT analyses and SWOT results discussed with regional panels (workshops)
4. Clustering of pilot regions

2.1 Literature study of rural attractiveness

A first phase on literature study of rural attractiveness was mainly oriented to collect information through desk research consultation and data collection. According to project plan, pilots were supposed to use the text mining tool and regional libraries as third phase of needs gathering task. Because the development of text mining technology and regional libraries (WP2) were not operating in spring 2020, pilots were not able to use text mining tool for needs gathering.

2.2 Survey of rural attractiveness in pilot regions

From the analysis of the situation, which derives from the scenario set, **a second phase** of proposal development was implemented with the purpose of obtaining data through social research techniques like **mass surveys**.

All pilots conducted similar online survey in their regions (Annex 1). The survey was designed with a view to further allow a cluster analysis. Each pilot has conducted a survey that covers the needs of the surveys target groups in their area. The surveys were translated into national languages and then summary reports were provided for the common use in PoliRural (see link to the different surveys in Annex 3). Pilots had the possibility to add two optional questions. Two regions included specific questions, although it is not considered in the global SWOT, these questions may have had effect to the recognized needs of each region.

Survey methodology

I. Target audience to be surveyed

The target groups to participate in the needs gathering exercise were established rural populations and recent or potential newcomers. To allow multiple views and interpretations, the survey should have covered as many attitudes of different demographic groups as possible. The opinions and views of young people, women, creative professionals, newcomers and educated people were considered of relevance in understanding rural attractiveness. Following to the regional stakeholder panels creation based on POLIRURAL D1.3 guidelines and orientations. These panels include representation of all relevant stakeholder groups of each pilot region (policymakers, rural populations, recent or potential entrants to rural areas, experts, innovators). In addition to these main target groups, regional stakeholder's panels could also define their own, more special segments, such as e.g., agricultural academic, community, agro-industry, agri-tech startups, and education bodies.

The diversity of the rural territories that are engaged in POLIRURAL reflects the reality of different contexts that make up European rural areas. It is not exclusively referred to different natural, cultural, economic development or population parameters, but there is also great diversity in relation to the political and social organization of the territories, the degree of implementation of European development policies being very different between one rural area and another. In some areas there are strong and well organized social and civil organizations while in other areas this is not the case. In the same way, the structures of the political leaders and organizations involved in decision-making on rural development policies are very different, so each pilot has defined their group of stakeholders considering their particular context and following the guidelines developed within Task 1.2 Concept Design & Methodology Development (see D1.3 Needs gathering & Policy Mapping Template). However, all the pilots have followed the indications referring to the stakeholder group assuming a valid and adequate representation of different actors linked to the territory, with sufficient capacity to be able to contribute to assess and provide ideas of interest for the evaluation of the territory's needs and formulation of proposals for future strategies and policies that can be applied for the development of the territories.

To support the recommendations of deliverable D1.3 on the target groups and give their definition a scientific basis, the local stakeholder groups' set-up has been consistent with other approaches like the following one, from Cranfield University:

The
Process Flow of Stakeholder engagement

<https://www.fundacionseres.org/lists/informes/attachments/1118/stakeholder%20engagement.pdf>.

Stage 1: Identify the stakeholders and prioritize as critical to the organization.

Stage 2: Understand the correlation between what the stakeholders and organization want and need.

Stage 3: Prepare the stakeholder engagement and agree the commitment

Stage 4: Adaptation to the different levels of trust of every stakeholder

Stage 5: Make clear the bases of that trust through a consultation process

Stage 6: A process to implement measures according to the agreed issues

Stage 7: Knowledge management at all stages of the process assuring transparency.

The stakeholder set-up is also consistent with the guidance of the EU Rural Review 19 "Improving Stakeholder Involvement". This document defines different levels of participation of the parties involved. In the case of POLIRURAL, the involvement of the parties involved refers to the participatory planning of local or regional rural development strategies mentioned in the Rural Review. In POLIRURAL the ultimate goal is to influence the definition of European policies and programs, which is the maximum level of stakeholder involvement mentioned in the Review.

As stated in the Review, stakeholders are, by definition, people or organizations that have something at stake in some area, either through involvement or influence. In the context of rural development policy, it identifies three main categories that are consistent with the categories established in the POLIRURAL stakeholder panel. In the first place, the

designers and implementers of policies and programs are distinguished. Within this group, in the context of POLIRURAL, policy makers and experts have been distinguished. Below are the bodies and organizations representing the interest groups as well as people involved in rural development actions that in the case of POLIRURAL have been grouped under the name of Rural Community. In addition, and due to POLIRURAL's particular interest in rural attractiveness, it was decided to take into consideration in the project within the panel and therefore in the survey, the Rural New Comers category.

The survey was targeted both to the members of the panel, so as to larger population of the targeted area. This allows collecting the opinion of all the interested parties mentioned in the Review.

II. Survey tools

For the survey, it was recommended to use online tools as it was considered a more reliable, effective and fast way of collecting information. Paper-based version should only be used when it was not possible to reach the target audiences with the online survey. There were both commercial and free tools to create online surveys. The EU Survey online tool, which is the Commission online tool for survey management free of charge, was considered following the recommendations from D1.3.

III. Survey scale

Each survey has used similar types of scales and levels of measurement so that data analysis and comparison can be done in a structured manner. In other words, real comparison or joint analysis of survey results across all pilots has been possible as each pilot used the same set of questions and scales, with the possibility of having two optional questions per regional pilot to look for specificities in the area.

For the survey responses, it was proposed the use of Likert scale from 1-5, which measures how the respondents agree or disagree with the following statements regarding rural attractiveness. (1=Strongly disagree, 5=Strongly agree, 0=Doesn't apply). This 5-point Likert scale is recommended to use when researching general public. It is faster to respond than 7-point scale and provides higher degree of measurement precision than 4-point scale. It allows also to select neutral option for those who want to select it. It also provides opportunity to detect changes if the study is repeated.

There were set few contrast questions, one per pillar, that seek to confirm or reject differences or similarities between a group of elements or included terms used by the informant. It has allowed to notice the level of comprehension and reliability of the answers and, also the relevance for the respondents of the main pillar properties. As a result, the use of Likert scale allows evaluating which pillars and questions are at high, low or at medium level. For instance, if the level of public services perceived as good, or does the area offer good opportunities for business and innovation.

In parallel, for each pilot there were identified different quantitative indicators, to measure qualitative aspects related to the questions. This has provided a comparison basis between the official data and the perception of the targeted population to develop a more accurate further analysis.

IV. Survey design

One of the added values of the POLIRURAL project is that it is simultaneously analyzing different European territories with very different characteristics in some cases. The future EC policy for rural development should be able to address the different contexts of rural diversity that exist in Europe. For this reason, the POLIRURAL project is of great value in gathering information from different areas that will provide different perspectives. For this reason, although the information from the pilots may seem, a priori, very different, the achievement of systematized conclusions is guaranteed by the common methodology used when collecting the information, by the use of common templates to collect the same contents and a homogeneous analysis system for all cases.

Taking into account the aforementioned diversity among the different territories participating in POLIRURAL, each pilot established which was their best spectrum of agents to direct the survey to. Hence, in some cases the number of responses differed from one pilot to another. For example in the case of Central Greece or Italy, the stakeholder panel was not big enough at that early stage and the engagement of the stakeholders in the activities of POLIRURAL limited.

The survey was designed with a view to further allow a cluster analysis. Each pilot conducted the survey that covers the needs of the above-mentioned target groups in their area. The common survey questionnaire (table 9/Annex 1) offered tools to explore how needs are currently met. The questionnaires were translated into national languages and then summary report provided for the common use in POLIRURAL (see link to the different surveys in Annex 3).

Considering the research objective of PoliRural, it was necessary to collect some personal and privacy related information from respondents, which included for instance:

- Age range:18-25; 26-40; 41-55; 56-65; >65
- Gender: Male; Female
- Category of the respondents: Policy maker; Rural population; Recent entrants to rural areas; Potential entrants to rural areas; Experts; Innovators; Others
- Organization: Private enterprise; Professional consultancy, Self-employed; Farmer; Business or professional association; Research and academy; Local authority; Regional authority; National authority; NGO; Others

GDPR aspects were considered following POLIRURAL guidance and recommendations.

2.3 SWOT analysis to summarise the results from literature study and survey

A **third phase** was oriented to summarise the findings from the survey, combined with the comparison with existing indicators for each pillar in each pilot region, to SWOT analyses followed by the organization of the **regional stakeholder panel workshops** that were organized as participatory workshops with targeted stakeholders that should have allowed the discussion on main findings from the SWOT.

SWOT methodology:

The SWOT analysis dates back to 1950's and 1960's but it was Wehrich (1982) that introduced SWOT matrix as a tool for situation analysis. SWOT has been pointed in most of the references of strategic planning. (Ghazinoory et al, 2011)

SWOT analysis is a strategic planning technique used to help to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for policy making, decision making² and strategy making (or planning).

A review of most frequent areas and scopes which SWOT has been applied in case studies or applied-methodological papers made by Ghazinoory, shows that the fields which SWOT is used the most, is agriculture and its sidelong fields.

It is designed for use in the preliminary stages of decision-making processes and can be used as a tool for evaluation of the strategic position of an organization or a geographic area (Caves, 2004).

It is intended to specify the objectives of the project and identify the internal and external factors that are favorable and unfavorable to achieving those objectives. Users of a SWOT analysis often ask and answer questions to generate meaningful information for each category to make the tool useful and identify their competitive advantage. SWOT has been described as the tried-and-true tool of strategic analysis.

These previous activities, were supposed to be also supported by the results extracted from the text mining tool developed within Polirural project, although this tool was not operational when this report was being performed

2.4 Regional needs assessment

This has allowed to encounter the **fourth phase** to assess the grass roots needs in the EU, by analyzing the different SWOT and needs assessment from pilots and clustering of pilot regions based on common needs rather than geography.

Participative process:

^{2 2} Decision-making is the terminology used in rural development to refer to the participation of the population in decisions about local development strategy. In this case, it refers to the fact that young people have adequate possibilities to participate and contribute with their opinions on the strategies and measures that are applied in the territories. See the definition of LEADER on the web-site of the European Network for Rural Development https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/leader-clld_en

Following the participatory methodology of POLIRURAL, in the regional needs assessment, stakeholders contributed with their vision in relation to the clearness of the elements of the SWOT, and their faithful reflection of the reality of the pilot territory.

In turn, stakeholders have also given their opinion on whether the identified needs really include all the priority aspects and challenges that the pilot territory faces. All these comments have been collected and can be consulted in Table 13 in Annex 2.

3 Grass roots needs analysis

3.1 Survey results analysis and pre-clustering

The survey was developed in parallel in all the Polirural regional pilots during the same period, beginning on Feb 10th and ended on March 9th, 2020. The survey results from each pilot region are presented in Annex 5.

In total the survey has gathered the interest of a total of 1296 respondents for the 12 regional pilots. (Table 1)

Table 1. Survey Participants per pilot

PILOT / COUNTRY	Total
Apulia / Italy	29
Central Bohemian Region / Czech Rep.	41
Central Greece/ Greece	31
Cuenca / Spain	56
Flanders / Belgium	103
Galilee / Israel	25
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	119
Hame / Finland	90
Mazowieckie / Poland	103
Monaghan / Ireland	78
Nitra / Slovakia	157
Vidzeme / Latvia	439

>> Nitra becomes Slovakia due to pilot's change of criteria

Age range distribution

On average, 2/3 of the survey respondents belongs to the age ranges 26-55, however there are few regions characterized by a younger profile of respondents Slovakia 33,12% of total number of respondents (18-25), and Cuenca-Spain with 14,29% of total respondents (18-25). There are, as well, two regions were respondents belongs to the higher age range (>65): Galilee-Israel 32% and Apulia-Italy 13,29%. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Age Range Distribution

Gender distribution

The respondents’ genders follow a balance distribution with 44,73% of males and 55,27% of females. However, in few regions the respondents’ gender is unbalanced with a higher participation of males: Galilee-Israel 68% and Central Greece-Greece 74,19% and other regions with a higher percentage of female respondents: Vidzeme-Latvia 76,99% and Hame-Finland 72,22%. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Survey gender distribution

Stakeholders category distribution

The first category choice among the respondents of the survey was the “rural population category” with on average a 55,17%, followed by 16,86% that were identified within the category “others” and a 10% belongs to the category “experts”. It should be highlighted the small number of respondents belonging to the other categories: policy makers (5,98%); new entrants (5,44%); “potential entrants” (4,04%) and those identified as “innovators” with a 2,49%.

It should be noticed the balanced participation of the different categories of stakeholders in regions like Slovakia and Vidzeme-Latvia. However, there are few regions where there are not respondents for different categories: Ie. “Potential entrants to rural areas” in Cuenca-Spain, Apulia-Italy and Galilee-Israel. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Survey category distribution

Type of organization

With regard to the respondents type of organization, the higher percentage of respondents belongs to “others” (19%) organization, followed by “local authority” (17,16%), private enterprise (14,30%) and “farmers” (11,28%). In few regions there is not any respondent from the “regional authority” type of organization: Monaghan-Ireland; Central Bohemian region-Czech Rep.; Cuenca-Spain and Apulia-Italy.

Although there are few regions with a very well balanced distribution of respondents organizations: Flanders-Belgium, Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM and Mazowieckie-Poland. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Survey organisation distribution

When preparing the survey design, it was raised the concern with different demographic groups, and respondents were segmented into different categories: region, age range, gender, category of stakeholder and organization.

Within each category, the structure of the survey forced the respondents to identify with a single option. In other words, within “Distribution by category”, although the same respondent was a new participant and an expert, the respondent must choose a single option with which they most identify, to avoid possible overlaps.

It was intended to develop a statistical analysis ie. Cross tabulation, however, the final participation in the survey with a limited number of respondents in some regional pilots, could not allow to implement a consistent statistical analysis for all the pilot regions. *The survey*

provided support to the swot exercises developed in the 11 pilots with a systematized and common methodology. Although, for some cases the number of respondents to the survey could have indicated a bias, the process for the identification of the grass root needs based on participatory and developmental process mitigated this risk. The survey results were as well confronted to different existing indicators at each pilot level that allowed to reduce the possible bias and reinforced the participatory process leading to the identification of the grass roots needs.

3.1.1 Pre-clustering of regions based on survey results

There is a need for clustering the survey results to support the further development of the needs assessment and clustering per commonalities rather than geography. At this regard the survey results have been analysed based on three different categories:

- % of positive responses to the questions above the remaining categories (Strongly agree plus agree)
- % neutral responses to the questions above the remaining categories
- % of negative responses to the questions above the remaining categories (strongly disagree plus disagree)

To allow the classification of the results it has been set a different colour for each classification category: Green for positive responses, blue for neutral responses; red for negative responses; and white for those responses that considered that the questions do not apply to the settings of the region.

This analysis should provide a further support to clustering the needs based on the assessment developed for each regional pilot and its integration with a view of the prioritisation and survey results pre-clustering.

For the ease of the analysis and a better understanding of the survey results the proposed questions have been classified within each pillar based on common domains.

1. Availability of public and other services

Transportation/Mobility

- 1) There is sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises, schools, universities)
- 2) The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are sufficient
- 3) The connections between rural and urban areas (e.g. airports, train connection) are sufficient.
- 4) Good intra-regional public transportation is available in the area.

5) Public transportation is important to me (contrast)

Medical

- 6) There are good medical (primary care) services in your village/region

Educational

- 7) There are good schools (primary and second level) in the area
- 8) There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area

Care

- 9) There are good daycare facilities in the area

Digital

- 10) There is a good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G/fiber)
- 11) There are adequate public provision of online e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services
- 12) There is enough support for tele-working opportunities in the area

Security

- 13) I feel safe and secure in my region

Figure 5. Survey Result: Availability of public and other services

>> Nitra becomes Slovakia due to pilot's change of criteria

For the transportation and mobility aspects considered within this pillar, there is a strong perception of the relevance of the public transportation for the respondents in all the regions, exclusive of Monaghan.

From the survey results it can be identified few regions with common concerns on the lack of good transportation and mobility services in the region: Central Greece, Hame, Cuenca, Galillee and Apulia.

Regarding the medical and day care services, it seems there is a good vision on the existing services in the different regions.

For digital services, there is a good perception on the internet connectivity in all the regions exclusive of Cuenca. However, there are other aspects related to digitisation and the development of conditions for rural attractiveness like the capacity to develop remote work and improve tele working that is seen as a weakness in a group of regions: Slovakia, Central Greece, Vidzeme, Central Bohemian region and Cuenca.

In general, it is perceived as good the availability of primary schools and lifelong learning opportunities, with the only exception of Monaghan and Central Greece and Cuenca.

2. Recreational and social activities

14) I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.

Young/Children recreational activities

15) There are enough recreational activities for young people in the area.

16) There are enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet

17) Extra-curricular activities (e.g.: music, dance, arts) for children are accessible in the area.

Elderly

18) Elderly people are offered activities and a space where to meet.

Other

19) This area offers quality commercial services such as restaurants, shops, car maintenance, etc.

20) Recreation and social activities are important to me (contrast)

Figure 6. Survey Results: Recreational and social activities

Within this pillar, there is a common concern about the importance of social and recreational activities for the population of all the regions exclusive of Monaghan and Apulia.

In general, there is a good view about the existence of opportunities for recreational activities for young people, exclusive of Slovakia, Central Greece, Hame and Vidzeme regions. In contrast in these regions there is a good perception on the extra-curricular opportunities (music, dance, sports) for young people). In contrast, a number of regions (7/12) have a bad perception about the availability of activities and spaces for elderly people.

3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living

Housing

21) Housing opportunities are adequate in the area.

22) I am proud of living in the area (Contrast)

Living conditions

23) Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are high

Social cohesiveness

24) There are problems of integration with some population in the territory (Minorities, newcomers....)

25) There are important social or political conflicts in the area

Figure 7. Survey Results: Living condition, quality of life and standard of living

>> Nitra becomes Slovakia due to pilot's change of criteria

The pride of living in the different regions is very well appreciated through the survey results. However, there are some housing concerns in 5 regions: Central Greece, Vidzeme, Cuenca, Apulia and Gevgelija-Strumica.

Within this pillar and within the social cohesiveness aspects, there is a common view to the existence of problems with regard to the integration of some population in the territory, however it seems there are not social or political conflicts in the regions.

4. Demographic & human capital

- 26) There are enough young people in the area.
- 27) There are enough women in the area.
- 28) There are enough babies born in the area.
- 29) There are enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e., children, elderly).
- 30) Our community and voluntary sectors are well developed and address the social needs of our region and create opportunities.
- 31) It is possible to find opportunities to develop family plans

Figure 8. Survey Results: Demographic & human capital

>> Nitra becomes Slovakia due to pilot's change of criteria

With regard to the demographic and human capital aspects raised through the survey results it can be identified a number of regions that have a common pattern in their responses profile: Central Greece, Monaghan, Cuenca, Apulia and Gevgelija-Strumica were it seems that there are serious concerns with regard to the existence of a balance human capital to allow the sustainability of the region and the capacities to develop family plans.

There is another group of regions integrated by Mazowieckie, Apulia, Flanders, Central Bohemian region, Central Greece and Slovakia, where seems to have good human capital.

5. Business, economy & innovation

Entrepreneurship and business ecosystem enhancement

- 32) The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses.
- 33) There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities
- 34) There is an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area
- 35) There are adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development with the provision of experienced services
- 36) The area is good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals.

For the entrepreneurship and business ecosystem enhancement there is a common pattern for a number of regions (6): Slovakia, Central Greece-Greece, Monaghan-Ireland, Central Bohemia-Czech Rep., Cuenca-Spain and Galilee-Israel. There are other patterns within these subpillar aspects, with the identification of some commonalities among Flanders-Belgium, Vidzeme-Latvia, Mazowieckie-Poland and Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM.

Circular economy

- 37) The area favors eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy)
- 38) There are not enough possibilities for employment. (Contrast)**

There is a common vision on the lack of enough opportunities for employment in all the regions exclusive of four: Flanders-Belgium, Mazowieckie-Poland, Central Bohemian-Czech Rep. and Monaghan-Ireland

Tourism

- 39) The area offers possibilities for sustainable tourism (cultural heritage, nature, sports, local food...)

In general, in all the regions out of two (Monaghan and Apulia), it is well appreciated the possibilities for sustainable tourism.

Agrifood

- 40) The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry.

In general, in all the regions out of three (Slovakia, Monaghan and Apulia), it is well appreciated the possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry.

Figure 9. Survey Results: Business, economy & innovation

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

- 41) Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life.
- 42) Loneliness and isolation do not affect many people in the area.
- 43) There are good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making.
- 44) In the area exists lively communities and citizen-driven local activities.
- 45) There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area.

For the pillar on social and cultural aspects of rural areas, there is a large diversity of responses with respect to each question. Loneliness and isolation is in general an aspect that seems to affect to a majority of the pilot regions.

There are few regions with common pattern: Central Greece, Cuenca-Spain and Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM, where loneliness and isolation, opportunities for young people to participate in decision making and the existence of lively communities and citizen-driven local activities, seems not to be good enough for the survey respondents.

In contrast, the rest of the regions, exclusive of Monaghan-Ireland have a good vision on the situation of the social and cultural aspects. So as for the opportunities for women to participate in social activities and working life in the regions.

Figure 10. Survey Results: Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

>> Nitra becomes Slovakia due to pilot's change of criteria

7. Environment & biodiversity

- 46) The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery.
- 47) Nature in the area is diverse.
- 48) High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area.

Agriculture

- 49) Cultivation practices in the area are done in environmentally sound way.

50) Environment and landscapes are important to me (Contrast)

For this pillar, there is a stronger common understanding for all the pilot regions, exclusive of Monaghan region in Ireland, where environment and landscapes are not considered important and, in coherence, the questions oriented to assess the environmental aspects are negatively rated, except the one related to environmental practices in agriculture. In contrast, this aspect is positively considered in Cuenca-Spain, Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM and Mazowieckie-Poland regions.

Figure 11. Survey Results: Environment & biodiversity

>> Nitra becomes Slovakia due to pilot's change of criteria

3.2 Recognising the rural needs through SWOT analysis

For the ease of the recognition of the rural needs it has been performed a global SWOT analysis, based on a draft development of SWOT analysis produced, which made use of the survey results, to facilitate the interactive discussions with the regional panels, developed between 9th March 2020 and mid-April 2020.

A SWOT analysis and needs assessment per pilot has been implemented. At this regard, the findings from the survey analysis were summarised in a draft SWOT (strengths and weaknesses analysis). To the extent possible, the structured SWOT was carried out on the survey questions that covered the 7 pillars considered in PoliRural report *D1.3 Needs gathering and policy mapping template*.

In the SWOT, it was set a common understanding for the collection of meaningful information for each category to make the tool useful. It was provided a guidance which included a common template for the development of this exercise (Annex 2), in which there were the principles for the fulfilment of the different phases to reach a SWOT for each pilot.

Furthermore, SWOT results were discussed with regional panel (workshops, interviews) to define the list of Needs and factors of attractiveness of the territory. Pilots leaders have facilitated the regional panel meetings during the committed period, to discuss and enrich the SWOT results and needs gathering analysis.

The guidance was as well oriented to ensure that needs might be well-rooted in the SWOT elements to serve as a consistent and solid basis, for the definition of future political rural development strategies.

The prioritization of the list of needs based on a ranking, which could further allow the development of effective strategies to address the more crucial issues in the territory, is of relevance. A template for the list of needs was also available in the guidance document (Annex 2).

Pilots should have had to summarize the core ideas of the discussions in order to make possible in a second step, to identify commonalities and differences with regard to individual framework conditions of territories and policy challenges.

A draft global SWOT with regional clustering per each of the seven pillars was developed (Tables 2-8). This integrates all the information provided by each of the 12 pilot region's leaders. Also, a list of needs has been developed between mid-April and mid-May 2020.

Factors of attractiveness:

The attributes of a rural area are always obvious to the local inhabitants, who will make their own decisions about its relative attractiveness as a place to live and work in. But for potential newcomers, there is a need to market the rural area and make potential newcomers aware of what is available, the potential. We need to paint a picture of what living and working in our rural area will be like, should someone choose to move here. Models in Sweden and elsewhere demonstrate that a proactive approach is often needed to make people aware of what an area

can offer and to help sustain a community. The challenge often articulated is how do we keep our young people in the area. This should be looked at differently; in how we can attract young people to our area.

From the SWOT analysis performed, it has arisen different factors of attractiveness connected to the strengths and opportunities elements, as these are considered the main aspects that allow to identify which are the drivers for creating attractive rural areas for the already established rural population and to attract new entrants to rural areas.

The availability of basic public services has usually been considered the pre-condition for allowing the development of the rural areas. It has also been highlighted in this exercise (see table 2).

There is a view to have available primary and secondary education services, without educational services at least in the primary and secondary levels of education it will be difficult to allow rural areas to retain its population and attract new entrants as this is a pre-condition for families to decide where to establish and develop their project of life. New education models based on ICT's has as well, been considered, not only related to formal education also for life-long learning purposes to allow to reduce the digital adoption divide between urban and rural areas.

The availability of primary medical and day care services for dependants are of high relevance, with a special view of the application of novel technologies to provide e-health services to cope with the difficulties to provide these specialized services in rural and remote areas and allow to improve the capacities of these areas to be more attractive.

The importance of developing good public transportation system, with a consideration of both rural-urban and intra-regional transportation services, mainly to hospitals has arisen from the swot exercises. The use of novel technologies to develop new transportation services (transportation on demand and car sharing) is seen as a factor of relevance.

In relation to recreational factors, it has been raised the importance of the spaces to meet for young and elderly people. So as for the access to commercial services (shops, supermarkets and restaurants) (table 3).

Other factors of attractiveness are connected to the quality of life, mainly oriented to the availability of housing conditions with an affordable price. And aspects related to the absence of political and social conflicts through the integration of migrants and foreign population, with low levels of criminal offences.

The economic development and business development opportunities are considered of high importance factors increase the attractiveness of rural areas. Mainly through the creation of the framework conditions for the entrepreneurship, start-ups and new business development through the availability of business ecosystem support services with dedicated specialized people and financial instruments. The innovation ecosystem enhancement is as well considered among those factors of relevance for attracting innovative business and the development of lively communities.

The sustainable agriculture, forestry, aquaculture and fisheries and their side economic activities (e.g.: energy, environmental business, short food chains, service contractors), are seen as important factors of attractiveness of rural areas.

Different cross-cutting aspects have been raised along the different pillars for which SWOT was developed. It is raised from the survey and from the participatory process, the importance of public goods as environmental resources. This is connected to the fact that rural areas are rich in natural resources (water, forest, landscapes) and thus, this considered as a factor of attractiveness with a view to different aspects: public services, recreational purposes (availability of green and cultural areas and sports and resorts centres), quality of life, economy and business development: Green economy opportunities with a consideration of circular economy and renewal energy, sustainable tourism and gastronomy).

Different aspects related to digitisation of the society have been considered as crucial factors for enhancing the attractiveness of rural areas with a cross-cutting consideration. There is a pre-condition based on having a good internet connectivity in all the territory, to increase the capacities of rural areas to develop. And promote the attractiveness through increasing teleworking opportunities and other ICT related activities (e.g.: e-health, e-learning and e-recreational activities for young people).

Finally, a growing trend of urban rurality and capacity to attract new entrants and talented people. So as, the importance of increase the presence of women and young people in rural areas and their participation in different activities (social, economic and political).

Table 2. Pillar 1 Availability of public and other services. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
There is an adequate primary and secondary education service in the territory with possibilities to education (higher and professional education, lifelong learning. SPAIN, FINLAND, IRELAND, N. MACEDONIA, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education. SPAIN, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE	Development of higher and vocational education and learning opportunities in the area ITALY, SPAIN, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE	Abandonment of rural youth in search of higher education opportunities. SPAIN, GREECE
There are good schools (kindergarten and primary) in the area. (SLOVAKIA, BELGIUM, FINLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA,	Intra-regional differences in capacities of kindergartens and elementary schools, endangered general education in peripheries, capacity insufficiency in suburbs (CZR)	Existing government efforts to promote higher education of the rural youth, by introducing dispersed high education studies N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN	Lack of good teachers and professionals due to their low financial remuneration, generational change (CZR)
There are good daycare facilities in the area. FINLAND, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA	Lack of adequate day care facilities in the area N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA	Funds and services for early childhood, modernization of primary and secondary schools ITALY, N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN	Lack of funds from municipal budgets to increase the capacity of kindergartens, primary schools, retirement homes CZR, N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN
Sufficient public transportation connection with the main region's/subregion's centre POLAND, CZR, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE,	Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services. ITALY, SPAIN, BELGIUM, SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, IRELAND, ISRAEL, N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA	New technologies available/using to enhance quality of public transport infrastructure, (services on demand, car sharing) CZR, SPAIN, BELGIUM, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Closure of train stations and train station counters in rural areas (BELGIUM)
Good intra-regional public transportation is available (N. MACEDONIA)		Development of public transportation network among remote areas and improving accessibility of all remote areas to airports and ports. GREECE, LATVIA	
There is sufficient public transportation to hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises. (SLOVAKIA)	Low intraregional transportation connectedness POLAND, CZR, FINLAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA, N. MACEDONIA	Policy measures for financial support for rural infrastructure N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	
There is a good internet/telecom connectivity SLOVAKIA, BELGIUM, FINLAND, CZR, POLAND, N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA	Limited broadband access. SPAIN, CZR, IRELAND, FINLAND (some areas), GREECE, IRELAND, LATVIA	With better development of the digitalization situation and work from a distance more people will settle in the region. GREECE, ISRAEL, SPAIN	Limited ICT skill levels. SPAIN, IRELAND, GREECE, LATVIA
Public services are available in rural areas or in nearby areas BELGIUM, POLAND, ITALY,			A decline trend and aging population will pose increased risks to reduction in the offer of services for citizens following rationalization of spending policies, CZR, SPAIN, ITALY, GREECE, LATVIA

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Good access to online public services (e-healthcare, e-education, e-daycare) FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA	Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning Services). IRELAND, ITALY, SLOVAKIA, CZR, N. MACEDONIA, ISRAEL, SPAIN	Development of public e-services POLAND, GREECE, SPAIN	Lack of public funds for further improvement of the accessibility & quality of public services POLAND, FINLAND, GREECE, LATVIA
			The healthcare and well-being service business has difficulties to find employees. (FINLAND)
Teleworking opportunities are good (FINLAND)	Lack of telework opportunities in the area. SPAIN, IRELAND, CZR, N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA, GREECE, LATVIA	Development of teleworking may favor the location of new professionals in rural areas. SPAIN, CZR, FINLAND, GREECE	
	There are no sufficient good medical services SLOVAKIA, CZR, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	Development of new online health services based on new technologies. SPAIN, CZR, GREECE	The corona crisis may limit the available medical capacities even further. N. MACEDONIA, GREECE
	Underdevelopment of electricity infrastructure – risk of electricity blackouts and poor access to water management system among rural inhabitants POLAND, SPAIN		The amount and complexity with some public services' bureaucracy prevent from starting entrepreneurship's career. FINLAND, GREECE, SPAIN
	The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care) FINLAND, GREECE, SPAIN		
	SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours. FINLAND, GREECE, SPAIN	Public-private service function to develop RD facilities FINLAND	
		There are a lot of different instruments for public funding (EU-level, national, regional) FINLAND, LATVIA	
		More active promotion of the rural area & availability of suitable off-farm work opportunities and schemes. IRELAND, SPAIN	
		CAP reform - LEADER & European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Farmer Groups. New CAP policies may provide incentives for access to land. IRELAND, GREECE	

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
		Increased participation and influence of LOCAL ACTION GROUPS to coordinate the different development policies (SPAIN)	
		Joint services for small villages (SPAIN)	

Table 3. Pillar 2 Recreational and social activities. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Elderly people are offered activities and a space where to meet. SLOVAKIA, SPAIN, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses) ITALY, POLAND, N. MACEDONIA, BELGIUM, LATVIA	Increased attention to personal services and issues of social inclusion (ITALY)	
Significant diffusion of associations operating in the social field ITALY, in particular a lot of women deal with social activities in their areas GREECE			
Good selection of recreational activities FINLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people POLAND, SPAIN, SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA	New forms of leisure and entertainment for young people based on new technologies. SPAIN, GREECE	Loss of young population. FINLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SPAIN,
	Lack of well-organized structures of leisure (e.g. thematic parks) . GREECE, SLOVAKIA, CZR, ISRAEL, SPAIN		
Extra curricular activities for children are accessible in the area. FINLAND, SLOVAKIA, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Insufficient and little diversified offer of extracurricula for children SPAIN, N. MACEDONIA		
Sport centers or sport resources (Ski) FINLAND, ISRAEL, GREECE	Certain types of recreation require specific infrastructure which is not possible in rural areas due to environmental constraints (e.g. paved paths) BELGIUM, SPAIN		Conflicts between different types of recreation (e.g. hikers and cyclist) (BELGIUM)
Acces to commercial services such as restaurants, shops, car maintenance, etc. SLOVAKIA, POLAND, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, ISRAEL,	Commercial services in the area are insufficient and poorly diversified. (SPAIN)		
Compared to urban areas there are more green open areas in rural areas BELGIUM, GREECE, ISRAEL		People who want to live in green areas (BELGIUM)	Too many people from urban areas who come to rural area for recreation BELGIUM, ISRAEL
Diverse natural and cultural-historical attractions CZR, GREECE, SPAIN, FINLAND, ISRAEL		Take advantage of cultural and natural resources for leisure. GREECE, SPAIN	

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	Compared to urban areas less variety in recreation/social activities BELGIUM, SPAIN, IRELAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Growing support for the creation of service centres for the aggregation and animation of local populations ITALY, CZR, ISRAEL	Reduction of public resources dedicated to social services ITALY, POLAND, GREECE
		Civic activity as a way for expending cultural and recreational offer POLAND, GREECE	
		Modern ICT technologies as a tool for expending the cooperation with cultural organisations from other regions/countries POLAND, BELGIUM, GREECE	
		Further development of recreation activities can boost tourism in rural areas, (Birdwatching) BELGIUM, ISRAEL, IRELAND, FINLAND, GREECE	

Table 4. Pillar 3 Living conditions and quality of life. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
There are adequate housing conditions in the area. SPAIN, BELGIUM, FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE	Housing opportunities are limited & expensive. CZR, SLOVAKIA, IRELAND, LATVIA The quality of buildings is low ISRAEL	Affordable price of properties in peripheral parts of the region CZR, ISRAEL, SPAIN	
		Demand for specific housing types that are present in rural areas e.g., homesteads BELGIUM, ISRAEL	
People are proud of living in the area SPAIN, FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA, CZR, POLAND, IRELAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA		Growing trend of urban rurality (“citymaalaisuus”) (FINLAND)	If too many people come live in rural areas the rural character might disappear, also change in housing type (e.g. more apartments) (BELGIUM)
		Multi-locality in living and working ² . And functional countryside for permanent living, leisure as an environment for housing and business (FINLAND)	
Involvement of the foreign population as a resource in the management of production chains and personal services ITALY, SPAIN	The vulnerability of the new poor and widespread uneasy situations, especially among young people and among foreign residents ITALY, BELGIUM, GREECE, LATVIA	Presence of foreigners as an opportunity for the maintenance of basic services and as an opportunity to recover residential assets. ITALY, SPAIN	Insufficient integration of newly arrived foreign workers into local communities (CZR, LATVIA) Increasing scale of social exclusion (POLAND)
No political or social conflicts in the region CZR, SLOVAKIA, BELGIUM, FINLAND, LATVIA, SPAIN	Some problems with integration of new entrants POLAND, SPAIN, ITALY, SLOVAKIA, N. MACEDONIA, FINLAND, LATVIA,		
In general, good living conditions POLAND, SPAIN, BELGIUM, N. MACEDONIA, FINLAND, GREECE, IRELAND, LATVIA,	Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are not yet sufficiently considered of quality. SLOVAKIA, ISRAEL	Increased accessibility to social infrastructure (POLAND) Available power supply in rural areas (a well-developed transmission and distribution network) (LR) N. MACEDONIA	Increasing income inequality POLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL
High quality of environment, ISRAEL, CZR, FINLAND, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	Air pollution related to using of local fireplaces (namely in areas with no gasification) (CZR)		

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	People are not highly aware of the usage of renewable energy for business purposes and in everyday life N. MACEDONIA	The climate conditions are favourable for usage of renewable sources of energy in the direction of providing energy for the agricultural sector N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN, GREECE,	
The high standard of living increases the demand on tourism-, wellbeing and healthcare services. FINLAND	Living conditions in villages and rural areas (except in tourist areas) are seen as less attractive than in urban areas N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	Use of second residences to expand the offer of rural tourism in the area. SPAIN, GREECE	
	Weak activity or non-existence of regional or local institutions competent for rural development GREECE, N. MACEDONIA	Focus on wellbeing in new strategic documents related to the regional development (CZR), FINLAND, ISRAEL	
		Potential for smaller farms to add "public good" value GREECE, IRELAND	Possible conflict between agriculture and inhabitants (e.g., odour nuisance) (BELGIUM)
Low level criminal offences CZR, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN, N. MACEDONIA, IRELAND, BELGIUM, GREECE, LATVIA,			Presence of organized and non-organized crime CZR, SPAIN
			Brexit & CAP reform threats to existing quality of life IRELAND

Table 5. Pillar 4 Demographic and human capital. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Significant number of women in the territory CZR, POLAND, SPAIN, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, IRELAND, LATVIA,			Lack of public participation in community decision-making. SPAIN, SLOVAKIA
There are enough young people in the area. SLOVAKIA, POLAND, CZR, IRELAND,	Low youth population SPAIN, FINLAND, BELGIUM, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA	Existing policy measures to attract young people to work and live in rural areas (N. MACEDONIA, ISRAEL)	Young people today are more mobile and less emotionally related to the land and country-side N. MACEDONIA, IRELAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SPAIN
	There are not enough babies born in the area N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN, SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, GREECE, LATVIA	High birthrate in comparison with other regions (CZR)	Abandonment of the rural environment of families with babies due to lack of resources that allow family life balance. (SPAIN)
Increase in the foreign population residing in the territories (ITALY)	Low level of local identity of newcomers (especially in suburban areas) (CZR)	Increase in the number of immigrants in the area employed in manual work ITALY, SPAIN	
Important presence of associations and volunteering in social services and social cooperatives ITALY, FINLAND, IRELAND	Activity of the citizens insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth POLAND, SLOVAKIA, N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN, GREECE, LATVIA	Social and cultural diversification of population (BELGIUM)	
		Existing initiatives (e.g. Rural Development Network) aimed to mobilise rural communities as agents of local development and as participants in rural policy (N. MACEDONIA)	
	The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly). SLOVAKIA, N. MACEDONIA, POLAND, BELGIUM, FINLAND, LATVIA	Possible arrival of new settlers in rural areas looking for a healthier and safer place to live BELGIUM, SPAIN, CZR, LATVIA	The interest among young people for programs for financial support of young farmers is very small (N. MACEDONIA)
Low unemployment rate in comparison with other regions. (CZR)	Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions ISRAEL, SPAIN, ITALY, CZR, FINLAND, GREECE, IRELAND, LATVIA		
	People have not enough working potential. The education structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses ISRAEL, N. MACEDONIA, BELGIUM, GREECE, LATVIA	Interest of talented people from abroad for work in the region (CZR)	Insufficient or total lack of education of people in rural areas - Low rates of enrolled and graduated students (LR) (N. MACEDONIA)

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	Limited opportunities to develop family plans. N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN, ITALY, GREECE	It is possible to find marriage and dating partners from the area. SLOVAKIA, SPAIN	
	New entrants and migrants may have difficult to get to know people, difficult to become a part of the community. FINLAND, LATVIA		It may be difficult for newcomers to adapt the community . (FINLAND)
	A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants ITALY, SPAIN, BELGIUM, GREECE, LATVIA	Institutional strategies and public aid aimed at the demographic challenge. SPAIN, LATVIA	Increasing unemployment as a factor for diminishing human capital POLAND, ISRAEL
		Retired older people in rural municipalities feel active and want social participation. SPAIN, CZR	
	Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN, SLOVAKIA, BELGIUM, IRELAND, LATVIA	The aging people require and use the healthcare and well-being services. It provides the opportunity for business. FINLAND, SPAIN	

Table 6. Pillar 5 Business, economy and innovation. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses. FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN	The conditions for the development of new businesses are very limited (sources of financing and taxation schemes) particularly for start-up and innovative companies. SPAIN, ITALY, N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA, IRELAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA,	Reorganization of public services (opportunity to business) FINLAND, LATVIA	Tax systems that are not always favourable for businesses ITALY, N.MACEDONIA, SPAIN
		Functional food product development. (FINLAND)	Competition from less regulated countries always a threat (IRELAND)
		Training and research in water technology and know-how and export. FINLAND, ISRAEL	
Besides agriculture there are also other economic activities in rural areas (BELGIUM), renewable energy entrepreneurship/environmental business, tourism, wellness, horse economy, service business, contractors and wood processing in area (FINLAND), Manufacturing, engineering (CZR) and food industries (CZR, N. MACEDONIA), eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy) N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	The area does not favor eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy). (SLOVAKIA)	Ongoing transition to the circular economy Supporting of local production and shortening of supply chains. Opportunities for agrotourism (increasing of entrepreneurs in this field) CZR, FINLAND	The economic recession caused by the covid-19 may undermine business development in rural areas. SPAIN, N.MACEDONIA
	Competition between similar businesses (e.g., two bakeries in one town) (BELGIUM)	Recovery of traditional productive activities in a green economy key BELGIUM, SPAIN	Presence of economic activities other than agriculture can disturb the rural character (BELGIUM)
	The development of industry is constrained by the quality of road infrastructure and business-related infrastructure and increasingly by the shortages of qualified labour.N. MACEDONIA, ISRAEL, LATVIA	There is great potential for export for agro-processing industry (N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN)	Aging of farmers, no successor (BELGIUM, FINLAND, ISRAEL, N.MACEDONIA, SPAIN) Low competitiveness of economic activities in rural areas (for example, agriculture, forestry, fishery, food sector, rural tourism, service industry) N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN
		Investments in tourism, energy logistics, export-oriented manufacturing, food and beverage and expansion to new markets. GREECE, ISRAEL, SPAIN	

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>The area offers possibilities for economic activities related to sustainable tourism (cultural, natural heritage, gastronomy, etc.), as well as related to agribusiness and manufacturing. SPAIN, ITALY, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, FINLAND, LATVIA</p>	<p>Insufficient development of tourism attractions and facilities; Difficult access to tourism amenities, national parks and tourist sites; Lack of trained human resources; Lack of strategic planning and marketing of rural tourism resources and products N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN</p>	<p>Social networks can serve as a tool for promoting the territory to boost the tourism sector. SPAIN, ISRAEL</p> <p>Rural tourism development BELGIUM, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SPAIN</p> <p>Institutional support in promoting tourism in the territory as well as in the agri-food industry. (SPAIN)</p>	<p>Changing conditions in tourism services as a consequence of the social distance and other covid-19 requirements . (SPAIN)</p>
<p>The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry. SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SPAIN</p> <p>Great concentration in fisheries and aquaculture. GREECE</p>	<p>There is no institutional support for eco-companies, companies with sustainable business (organic production). Lack of seasonal labour; Lack of own capital and access to financial resources; Weak level of agro-food integration; Low level of integration of research in the development of agriculture N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA</p> <p>Specialisation in low tech activities in agriculture. GREECE, ISRAEL</p>	<p>Trainings of new and innovative techniques in the agriculture sector (BELGIUM, ISRAEL, SPAIN)</p> <p>Sustainable agriculture & forestry (which is underdeveloped). Social Farming & better cultivation Practices. Further scope to shorten local food supply chains. (IRELAND). Excellent conditions for the development of gardening, fruit growing and vine growing N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA</p>	<p>Tendency for low investments in new technologies and modernisation of companies/Enterprises in rural areas are predominantly labour intensive with a low level of technical and technological equipment N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN</p>
<p>Wide range of measures to support agriculture industry/farmers (BELGIUM) and funds for agribusiness N. MACEDONIA, BELGIUM, IRELAND</p>	<p>Credit & finance is expensive & limited. Small farm sizes. Land prices are a barrier to entry for new entrants. IRELAND, GREECE, LATVIA, N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA</p>	<p>Potential for smaller farms to add 'public good' value - Trails, walks, guide tours, local history IRELAND, GREECE</p>	<p>Investments in agriculture are less attractive for banks due to lower profitability of investments, collateral problems, and so on. (LR) (N. MACEDONIA)</p>

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
A large number of research institutes and the emergence of new research infrastructures (CZR, FINLAND, ISRAEL)	Low investing rates to RDI. (FINLAND)	Increase in EU financial resources to support research, innovation in agriculture, competitiveness and environmental sustainability ITALY, GREECE, ISRAEL, N. MACEDONIA	
		High RDI-knowledge and its opportunities to companies. (FINLAND, ISRAEL, SPAIN)	
	Lack of research- and product development facilities i.e. laboratories FINLAND, GREECE		
	Weak links between research and business sectors, inconsistencies between the main focus of private and public research CZR, GREECE, SLOVAKIA		
A few industries are very innovative (ISRAEL)	The area is not good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals. Lack of mature business ideas and entrepreneurial skills and knowledge; saturation of sectors that require low start-up capital (small retail shops, restaurants, communal services) ISRAEL, LATVIA, N. MACEDONIA)	Digital transition - opportunities for new economic activities and productivity growth CZR, FINLAND, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	Limited innovations potential (POLAND, SPAIN) Competition between High-tech industries that already exist in the region can create shortage of workers. (ISRAEL)
There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities FINLAND, SPAIN	There are no sources for financing innovative/new rural activities, high costs of starting up new businesses and of employing new workers N. MACEDONIA, GREECE		
Foreign companies play a more important role in the economy compared to other regions (CZR)	Endogenous business is not supported under same conditions as multinational companies (CZR)		
Good location and access to biggest cities FINLAND, SPAIN, GREECE	Distance of rural area to other industrial sites BELGIUM, ISRAEL	Utilising wellness and health services and know-how as export products. FINLAND, LATVIA, SPAIN	
The entrepreneurs know and use the public entrepreneurship services in order to develop their business FINLAND, SPAIN	The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care). FINLAND, GREECE, SLOVAKIA		

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours. FINLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SLOVAKIA	The joint ventures or networks of SMEs enable participation and provide resources to participate bid competitions (FINLAND, GREECE, SPAIN)	Difficulties in accessing credit discourage investments for production activities or the introduction of technological or process innovations (ITALY)
The migrants' interest to become entrepreneurs was high. Migrants were particularly interested in marketing and selling. (FINLAND)	No adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development POLAND, N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA, GREECE, LATVIA	Strengthening of youth entrepreneurship Innovative and creative vouchers as a financial tool to support local companies CZR, GREECE, LATVIA Migrants had business ideas. (FINLAND)	Lack of farming experience/expertise. No support schemes & information for newcomers. IRELAND, GREECE
Lively communities & citizen-driven local activities. (IRELAND)	There is a lack of entrepreneurship know-how and skills. (FINLAND), in peripheral parts of the region (CZR, GREECE, LATVIA) The lack of relevant and useful networks of entrepreneurs. FINLAND, GREECE, LATVIA, SLOVAKIA	Interest of talented people from abroad to work in the region (CZR) The Ministry of Economy via the Agency for promotion of SME supported the creation of a network of advisors and promoted voucher system of use of consultancy services (N. MACEDONIA)	No specific initiatives to allure potential entrepreneurs POLAND, GREECE
	General employment opportunities in the area are very limited. SPAIN, SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, ISRAEL, N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA		Loss of job opportunities in small municipalities "brain drain" to the capital city CZR, ISRAEL, GREECE, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN
	Jobs in the high-tech sector is very scare and difficult to get, especially for youngsters. ISRAEL, GREECE		Labour shortage in some businesses. FINLAND, LATVIA, SLOVAKIA
	Inadequate coordination of program and activities directed towards different economic sectors in rural areas N. MACEDONIA, GREECE	Explore synergies with other regions in terms of innovation infrastructure and technology transfer. GREECE, SPAIN	

Table 7. Pillar 6 Social and cultural aspects. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Women and men equally participate in decision making ITALY, SPAIN, CZR, SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, N, MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA,	Lack of gender equality in taking decisions and professional life (POLAND) Rural women have very low levels of decision-making in the family and leadership of family businesses, especially in the rural areas with predominantly Muslim population N. MACEDONIA), GREECE, ISRAEL,	Current thought can lead to greater empowerment of women and therefore to greater weight in decision-making bodies and the professional sphere. SPAIN, GREECE, ISRAEL	
Women and men equally participate in working life FINLAND, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA	High youth and female unemployment rate (ITALY)	Funding to incentivize the employment of women ITALY, SPAIN	Insufficient empowerment of women on the job market (POLAND, GREECE, Insufficient integration of newly arrived foreign workers into local communities (CZR)
Experiences and successful projects that have promoted social inclusion and active citizenship practices ITALY, ISRAEL	Social exclusion as an increasing problem POLAND, FINLAND (Young People), LATVIA	Propensity for active participation both in the inclusive and social sphere, as well as recognized associations, also by spontaneous groups / committees of citizens ITALY, SPAIN	It may be difficult for migrants to adapt the community. (FINLAND)
Social cohesion in rural areas BELGIUM, ISRAEL, SPAIN	Low Connections between urban & rural areas. IRELAND, ISRAEL	Community activities support the local identity CZR, FINLAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN	Insufficient activity of NGOs in the region (POLAND) poverty in rural areas (BELGIUM)
Rich and versatile rural culture. FINLAND, GREECE, LATVIA, SPAIN	The high percentage of the aging population does not facilitate the introduction of social and cultural changes. SPAIN, GREECE		Insufficient integration of newly arrived foreign workers into local communities (CZR)
Strong farming & rural community ethos, with farmers being custodians of the land, waterways and biodiversity (IRELAND)	Insufficient number of young people among professional decision takers POLAND, SLOVAKIA, GREECE, ISRAEL, SPAIN	Integration of new populations in the area. Many new community members have farming skills / interests. IRELAND, GREECE, SPAIN	
	Poor appreciation and social awareness of the importance of preserving the heritage elements. SPAIN, SLOVAKIA	Interest of people in heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g., small landscape elements) BELGIUM, GREECE, SPAIN	
		There are opportunities connected to the special historical heritage of the region that could be developed. ISRAEL, GREECE, SLOVAKIA	

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	There are no good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making ³ (N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, LATVIA)	Bringing life to local communities through the transition of new residents CZR, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA	
The cultural heritage is located in the rural areas and has the biggest development potential considering the diversity and quality of cultural and historical treasures and archaeological sites in the country N. MACEDONIA, SPAIN, GREECE	Building illegal phenomena, damage to historical and archaeological sites, environmental damage (ITALY)	Increasing interest in cultural tourism on the market (N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN)	

Table 8. Pillar 7 Environment and biodiversity. Compilation SWOT

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
The area has high value landscapes and biodiversity. SPAIN, ITALY, CZR, BELGIUM, SLOVAKIA, FINLAND, ISRAEL, N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, IRELAND, LATVIA	Rural landscape is highly fragmented (BELGIUM)	The area offers possibilities to attract bird watchers. ISRAEL, SPAIN	Environmental degradation by industrial facilities and widespread urbanization. SPAIN, ITALY
Clean water and ground water resources FINLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA	No specific environmental or biodiversity features (POLAND)	Adaptation to climate change CZR, ISRAEL, SPAIN	Risk of hydrogeological instability and desertification on significant portions of land (ITALY)
Forest areas and ecosystem services FINLAND, GREECE, SLOVAKIA		Climate Change Opportunities. Alternative energy sources. (IRELAND, GREECE, SPAIN)	Unsustainable land management, landscape water scarcity and biodiversity decline (CZR)
People living in rural areas highly value the rural landscape/environment BELGIUM, SPAIN, CZR, FINLAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SLOVAKIA	The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued. SPAIN, SLOVAKIA Lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection (N. MACEDONIA, LATVIA)	The need to protect environment and nature creates opportunities for business in rural e.g. circular economy (FINLAND, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN)	Not yet attracting adequate eco-firms & sustainable businesses. (IRELAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA)

³ Decision-making is the terminology used in rural development to refer to the participation of the population in decisions about local development strategy. In this case, it refers to the fact that young people have adequate possibilities to participate and contribute with their opinions on the strategies and measures that are applied in the territories. See the definition of LEADER on the web-site of the European Network for Rural Development https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/leader-clld_en

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Nature preservation, supporting of sustainability (CZR)	Environmental degradation phenomena in rural areas (ITALY) Some parts of the region as becoming pollutant. (ISRAEL)	Growing attention to the quality of the environment and the landscape, especially in the younger generations (ITALY, GREECE, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN)	Changing climate (e.g., in past two years severe droughts which impacted the agricultural sector in Flanders) (BELGIUM, SLOVAKIA, SPAIN)
High awareness of environmental issues POLAND, ISRAEL	Lack of informative actions regarding greening measures of CAP. GREECE, SLOVAKIA	Growing demand of renewable energy sources (FINLAND)	
The region has attractions for tourism- and well-being business. FINLAND, IRELAND, ISRAEL, LATVIA, SLOVAKIA		Initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agritourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas. GREECE, SLOVAKIA	
Excellent quality & green farming produce. Farms as 'public goods. Strong food certification system. (IRELAND)	Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations POLAND, N. MACEDONIA, SLOVAKIA, IRELAND environmental issues related to agricultural practices BELGIUM	Markets are moving towards green economy models ITALY, CZR, ISRAEL Encourage more farmers to take environment measures (BELGIUM)	Conflict between agriculture and nature sector BELGIUM, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA
	There are no efficient waste management practices by individuals and the business sector (64%) - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites N. MACEDONIA, GREECE, SPAIN	Available human resources in the private and civil sector, which have some experience and knowledge in sustainable environment management (N. MACEDONIA)	Lack o public funds for environment-friendly public investment (POLAND, GREECE, ISRAEL, SLOVAKIA)
	Very low percentage of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste N. MACEDONIA		General practice is collection of non-separated communal and non-hazardous industrial waste as well as non-hazardous and hazardous non-separated waste fractions (N. MACEDONIA)

3.3 Regional clustering based on needs assessment

Cluster analysis is a means of detecting the groups that naturally occurred in the survey's data set, where a pre-clustering was developed to allow a deeper analysis through qualitative techniques based on interactive workshops with the regional pilots stakeholder's panels. This has been done by analysing which needs and agreement factors attributes are the most highly prioritized for each of the seven identified pillars closely connected to the SWOT elements.

In addition, each pilot identified and prioritized the needs of their territory. This information, together with the common SWOT, allowed to establish 32 needs, divided into seven pillars, as a summary of the situation of the different pilots. That list of 32 needs was reviewed by the pilots, each one pointing out the needs with which they most identified. (highlighted in green in the figures 12-18).

3.3.1 Quality of life

This category includes those needs integrated in the Pillar 1: Availability of public and other services and Pillar 3: Living conditions and quality of life.

The prioritized needs with regard to the factors related to quality of life are mainly linked to the availability of public and other services are consistent with the concern raised from the survey results and the regional clustering. It is expressed a common need to enhance the infrastructures and public transportation system to improve the connections between rural and urban areas, in particular with the medical services, and other primary services (e.g. education,). Mobility as a service can have an effect on the social and economic functioning of villages in rural areas. It is as well considered that improved public transportation is vital to attain enough work force and to make rural businesses competitive employers.

The needs assessment exercise has allowed to raise the awareness on a factor linked to digitisation of the society and the economy. Digitalization is a basic condition for the sustainable development of the region and strengthening of its resilience. At this regard there is common concern on the need to have a good internet connectivity (broadband) in the whole territory, which is a framework condition for the further development of other digital services.

At this regard, in relation to digital services there is a need to enhance e-government and digital services by a number of regions. While other regions expressed the need to improve the digital capacities of the rural population to reduce the adoption divide which is consistent with existing statistics⁴. Finally, there is a need on the support of tele-working opportunities prioritized by only two regions, although COVID crisis effects are not reflected in this exercise, it is supposed how tele-working will have a stronger view for the future development of opportunities in the rural areas that cannot be neglected as some young people are coming back to the region since they can work remotely (Figure 12).

⁴https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20200207-1?utm_campaign=58cbcdfb73a6a3222e031399&utm_content=5e3d1e622086910001a312e1&utm_medium=smapshare&utm_source=linkedin

Figure 12. Pillar 1 prioritized needs cluster map: Availability of public and other services

PILLAR 1 Availability of public and other services		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece/ Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowiecki e / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Enhance the infrastructures and public transport system, in order to improve the connections between rural and urban areas, in particular with the medical centers and to the main cities in the region												
2	Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole territory												
3	Improved access to adequate medical services												
4	Need to enhance functional e-government/ public administration and other digital services, like remote assistance for families and businesses												
5	Improve the training of the population in the use of internet and digital services												
6	Need to enhance training opportunities for the population and strengthen the cooperation between education and business												
7	Need to create and support tele-working opportunities												

With regard to the needs connected to the quality of life there is also an aspect, prioritized by a number of regions, related to the support of the wellbeing of all inhabitants and the enhancement of the quality of life. In relation to this it is as well considered the need to diminishing income inequalities, improve the social services for elderly people, disadvantaged people and migrants and other minorities. And also, of importance the need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas prioritized by three regions. The costs / benefits of village settlement densification need to be compared with the negligence of old buildings such as farmhouses, churches and manors. There is as well a need to improve access to accommodation for people at risk of poverty. Housing is also affected by the very low possibilities of rental market, also legislation is not appropriate to support people moving to rural areas. A relevant need raised in this exercise is oriented to highlight the good feelings and emotions related to living in rural areas, which is connected as well to the pride of living in these territories extracted from the survey (see figure 13). This is as well consistent with the need expressed by eight regions in pillar 5 (Figure 15) to promote the transition to the circular economy.

Figure 13. Pillar 3 prioritized needs cluster map: Living conditions and quality of life

PILLAR 3 Living conditions and quality of life		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece/ Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowieckie / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Need to support wellbeing of all inhabitants and enhance the quality of life												
2	Diminishing income inequalities – especially in the context of educational opportunities, access to healthcare and access to public services and public goods												
3	Improve social services for elderly people, disadvantaged people, immigrants and minorities and promote the creation of nursing homes												
4	Actions to avoid conflicts between newcomers and minorities in rural areas and inhabitants of rural areas												
5	Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas												
6	Need to highlight the good feelings and emotions that are related to living in rural areas												

3.3.2 Social capital

This category includes those needs integrated in the Pillar 4: Demographic and human capital and Pillar 5: Business, economy and innovation

The needs related to social capital are mainly considered within those expressed in Pillar 4 on demographic and human capital through four priorities (figure 14): The most relevant to the regional pilots is the factor related to the need of finding more employment possibilities to reduce the dependency ratio. It is as well very relevant the need to create the conditions to attract new entrants. These needs are well connected to the ones prioritized in pillar 5 (Figure 15), where it is expressed the need to promote job creation in rural areas with a special view to women and youth which is consistent with the findings of Ruraljobs project⁵, where it was identified an employment's pattern change through age groups and gender: employment rates of youth and elderly are lower than the employment rate of prime-aged people. Employment rate of prime-aged women is generally lower than employment rate of prime-aged men. It is, as well, identified the need to encourage the creation of new business and entrepreneurship. While providing spaces for coworking and ecosystem support services.

It is as well identified the need to create the conditions to encourage people to become farmer, as a factor of attractiveness, mainly in rural areas where agriculture still have a strong economic share, although there is a need to improve the access to land for young, small and new farmers. Linked to the CAP is was raised the need to change the support provided, towards a support more oriented the added value and environmental sustainability of the agricultural practices performed at farm level, also with a view to promote the adoption of environmental and energy saving technologies within agricultural production systems.

So as, the need to simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms, it is linked to the need to restore local marketplaces and regional distribution networks. Finally, in relation to sustainable agroecological system, there is a need to promote healthy nutrition with special attention to schools, hospitals, social establishment that could procure directly from local farmers. Voluntary Groups are good at doing their own thing, but there is insufficient networking and sharing of ideas. There is a necessity of promoting volunteer policies among the population to develop services in an altruistic way where the private and public sectors have difficulty offering it.

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211605>

Finally, a very relevant need related to the creation of the framework conditions to improve the attractiveness of rural areas is connected to the development of a framework for coordinated program and activities towards different economic sectors in rural areas, which express the need to build the different policies based upon the coherence and strategic planning of the different policies, measures and activities with a holistic view.

Figure 14. Pillar 4 prioritized needs cluster map: Demographic and human capital

PILLAR 4 Demographic and human capital		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece/ Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowieckie / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Need to control of the main abandonment phenomena by implementing integrated development processes of production activities												
2	Need to boost the attractiveness of the region for new entrants by addressing various critical issues: education, day-care, extracurricular activities, employment and career prospects, social and recreational activities												
3	Find more employment possibilities for example in the healthcare and well-being services for elderly people to reduce dependency ratio												
4	Need to better develop community and voluntary sector focused on social needs												

Figure 15. Pillar 5 prioritized needs cluster map: Business, economy and innovation

PILLAR 5 Business, economy& innovation		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece/ Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowieckie / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Promote job creation in rural areas, for the general population, with special emphasis on youth and women,												
2	Encourage the creation of new businesses and entrepreneurship. Provide spaces for coworking and ecosystem support												
3	Encourage people to become a farmer and favor the profitability of the agricultural sector supporting precision agriculture and other innovative solutions, and shortening supply chains of local production												
4	Need to consider an adequate and diversified financial support for innovative and new rural activities. Support special taxation scheme to attract new businesses												
5	Need to promote the transtion to Circular economy and bioeconomy. Promote technological innovation linked to the Green Economy												
6	Promote economic diversification in a jointly organized way from the institutions and the private sector, through the tourist development of the area, taking advantage of the heritage and natural resources existing in the territory,												
7	Develop a framework for coordinated program and activities directed towards different economic sectors in rural areas												

3.3.3 Cultural diversity

This category includes those needs integrated in the Pillar 2: Recreational and social activities and Pillar 6: Social and cultural aspects

Within Pillar 6 two needs are expressed in (Figure 17). One related to the gender equality issues and the enhancement of rural population in decision making with a special concern to women and youth, as well of minorities. Masculinization is a general problem in rural areas, due to the abandonment of women looking for new opportunities in urban areas. This results in a society with a lack of capacity for social, economic and cultural progress. This also includes a loss of rural traditions, and minor identity and belonging feelings.

So, it is important to boost policies for the permanence of women in rural territories, and to promote their role in a broad sense (political, professional, social, etc.).

It is also essential to improve the integration process both with marginalized populations in the area and with new arrivals/immigrants, also through the creation of social enterprises. Need for activities for poverty reduction and social inclusion.

Within Pillar 2, a large number of regions expressed the need to promote leisure and recreational activities for the diversified population, taking into account taking into account preferences and characteristics of young people, disabled, children and old people.

It is being as well considered, the need to preserve cultural landscape and cultural heritage as a factor of attractiveness of rural areas (Figure 16) and to provide meeting spaces for people in order to increase the feeling of community and of belonging to the territory.

The advantage of rural areas is related to strong communities/community life and cultural and natural heritage, thus there is a need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions.

Figure 16. Pillar 2 prioritized needs cluster map: Recreational and social activities

PILLAR 2 Recreational and social activities		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece/ Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowieckie / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Promote leisure and recreational activities for the most diversified population, especially taking into account the needs of young people, disabled, children and old people.												
2	Provide spaces and green areas where population can meet and contribute to improve the quality of life.												
3	Need to preserve cultural landscape and cultural heritage												

Figure 17. Pillar 6 prioritized needs cluster map: Social and cultural aspects

PILLAR 6 Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece/ Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowieckie / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Need to sustain the gender equal society												
2	Promote the participation of the rural population in decision-making, particularly among women and youth, as well as minorities present in the territory. Promote coexistence and relationship between the different groups that live in rural areas												

3.3.4 Natural capital

This category includes those needs integrated in the Pillar 7: Environment and biodiversity.

Landscape and spatial transformations are strongly influenced by suburbanization processes. These changes consist in transforming arable land, often valuable in terms of agriculture and nature, into residential areas.

The needs related to the category of “natural capital” are mainly expressed in those prioritized in Pillar 7 (see figure 18), where a large number of regions identified different needs related to the conservation, improvement and valorization of the natural resources and landscape diversity of the territory. In close relation to this, there is a need to promote better waste management and using waste as a resource.

Eight regions over the twelve participating in this exercise expressed a strong need to promote the adoption of farming and fishing practices, with low environmental impact adapted to climate change. Efforts in controlling agricultural uses of pesticides and herbicides, as well as reducing the uses of chemical fertilisers are done.

In pillar 2, it was as well identified a need looking to provide green areas where population could meet to improve quality of life which is very well connected to the expressed concern related to environmental aspects raised from the survey by mainly all the regions (see figure 16).

Attention should also be paid to the effective transmission of information, bringing together those who need information with those who can provide it. Negative human influence on nature (Anthropogenic GHG emissions, sustainable food, waste management) tends to be the result of ignorance, not abuse or deliberate passivity.

There is a perceived need to integrate landscape character into a broad cultural-historical evaluation and protect valuable landscape (elements). Landscape care must take into account spatial quality (integral approach), involve multiple sectors (integrated approach) and include multiple stakeholders (participatory approach). Within this context, there is need to prevent devastation of forest and logging especially in national parks.

Figure 18. Pillar 7 prioritized needs cluster map: Environment and biodiversity

PILLAR 7		Apulia / Italy	Central Bohemian / Czech Rep.	Central Greece / Greece	Cuenca / Spain	Flanders / Belgium	Galilee / Israel	Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	Hame / Finland	Mazowieckie / Poland	Monaghan / Ireland	Slovakia	Vidzeme / Latvia
1	Conserve, improve and value the natural resources and landscape diversity of the territory												
2	Promote the adoption of farming and fishing practices, with low environmental impact and compatible with the adaptation with the climate change												
3	Initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects) and effective exploitation of high natural value areas.												

4 Challenges

The debate about rural development and rural policies is relatively recent in the EU (started from late 1980's) in relation to agricultural policies, which date back to the origins of the European Union (Saraceno, E. 2003). In parallel other different EU policies have been implemented with a view to promote regional development, mainly implemented through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and European Social Fund (ESF).

Different factors of attractiveness and needs arisen from the research performed have a cross-cutting consideration, and thus a sole policy or instrument does not have the capacity to provide an additive impact. After many years of developing of rural development policies and the continuous process of depopulation of these areas, there is a need to increase the capacities of these territories with a coherent and strategic view with regard to the different policies with a direct or indirect impact. At this regard from the overall vision of the analysis performed it can be highlighted that there is a specific need to include a rurality view in all the different policies and actions to be developed, as it has been promoted for other policies with regard to gender equality and environmental aspects. Indeed, one of the aspects that has arisen from the participatory discussions held, is the need to create an environment conducive to business in rural areas and for this, differentiated tax measures for rural areas are also called for in the debates, similarly for economic measures that positively discriminate against all those entrepreneurs who decide to settle in rural areas.

The inefficiency of the formulation of uncoordinated rural development policies has determined the need to adapt current rural strategies, which have often been based on sectorial approaches (mainly agricultural), and thus be able to take into account the different development needs of rural regions, many of which are based on the exploitation of specific local resources.

In relation to this, the concept of "rural proofing" emerged, which seeks to create a mechanism for the review of legislation, sectorial and economic policies from a rural perspective, since the "new rural paradigm" requires important changes in the way in which policies are conceived and implemented. Because currently, designing a rural development policy for different communities or territories implies pooling the knowledge of a wide variety of public and private actors.

In this sense, some work is already done. It is the case of the application of a "Rural lens" by the Canadian Rural Secretariat which states that the successful application of the Rural Lens did help lead to a number of new initiatives targeted for rural communities. This included funding dedicated for rural infrastructure (more than CAD \$427 million), while the Department of Health established an Office of Rural Health. Access was also improved to the federal government through increased Service Canada locations across the country. Likewise, the Community Futures program received additional investment and Community Futures Development Corporations expanded to additional rural communities (Rural Secretariat, 2001a). The Rural Secretariat and the Rural Lens were also instrumental in facilitating the

creation of Industry Canada's Broadband for Rural and Northern Development pilot program and the National Satellite Initiative (Rural Secretariat, 2003).⁶

Digitisation of the society and the economy is a process with no way back. This process can be an opportunity to reverse the depopulation process of the rural areas or by contrast, could accelerate it. From the research performed within this task, many different factors of attractiveness and needs connected to digitisation, have been identified, however, generic policies have not solved the urban-rural digital divide. The rural is in need of 'customized' policies, but telecommunications companies cannot serve every individual need (Salemink, K. et al, 2015). There is need to create the ecosystem support through different initiatives and activities to face the digital divide, to increase the capacity of rural population to make profit from novel ICT services and technologies, to improve and allow the creation of new businesses.

Recently, it was launched the European Green Deal⁷, which is a set of policy initiatives brought forward by the European Commission with the overarching aim of making Europe climate neutral in 2050. The plan is to review each existing law on its climate merits, and also introduce new legislation on the circular economy, building renovation, biodiversity, farming and innovation which have a direct impact on the different factors of attractiveness identified through the analysis performed in this task. It will be as well an opportunity for rural areas and valorise through new business model based on circular economy: renewable energy supply, water efficiency use, forestry valorisation and provision of ecosystem services and public goods for the benefit of the population in the rural areas (Montero Aparicio, A. 2008). At this regard, there is a challenge on capturing the value of the transition to a green economy for the benefit of the rural areas and rural population. Hence, the importance of promoting sustainable agriculture adapted to the new conditions linked to climate change.

Another aspect raised in the research performed is around the association between food, landscape and culture to promote rural areas and contribute to their growth by promoting the benefits for the communities that work and live in the area and the resources it contains which have been proven it success through different experiences in the EU (Piveri, C. 2018).

Finally, a consideration of the capacity to retain and attract women and young people in rural areas. This is a question that has raised the awareness of policy makers and researchers for a long time. There is a strong concern to increase the orientation of the different policies and initiatives towards this targeted population to increase the impact of the actions as they play a catalytic role towards achievement of transformational economic, environmental and social changes required for sustainable development (UN, 2019). Perhaps of relevance the creation of the conditions for entrepreneurship with advisory services as well as an adequate tax regime.

⁶ <http://ruraldev.ca/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/RuralProofinginCanada-HallGibson.pdf>

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_es

5 Conclusions

The differences among the European territories and population with regard to geographic, cultural, language and other factors, do not mean to be a weakness and could be identified as a strength due to the commonalities that arise from the detail study on the needs and factors of attractiveness for the rural areas.

However, there is a need to create the conditions to improve the attractiveness of rural areas connected to the development of a framework for coordinated program and activities towards different economic sectors in rural areas, which express the need to build the different policies based upon the coherence and strategic planning, of policies, measures and activities with a holistic view.

More than 80 needs were identified in this exercise; however, it was possible to reach to a common understanding of the most important needs with a total number of 32 needs finally assessed that have allowed to develop cluster maps per each of the 7 pillars and needs, integrated into 4 different categories: Quality of life; Social capital; Cultural diversity; and Natural capital (Figures 19-22).

The digitisation process of the society and the economy is well connected to the factors of attractiveness of rural areas. At this regard there is common concern on the need to have a good internet connectivity (broadband) in the whole territory, which is a framework condition for the further development of other digital services.

The sustainability and environmental aspects are strongly considered as factors of attractiveness of rural areas. All the regions highlighted the importance of these aspects in relation to different categories for the attractiveness: social capital, cultural diversity and natural capital.

One of the most relevant factors, is the one related to the need of finding more employment possibilities to reduce the dependency ratio and improve the conditions to attract new entrants, with a special view to women and youth. Gender equality and the participation of women and youth in business and in the society, is also relevant to consider future actions oriented to rural areas

Finally, the mobility rural-urban and the provision of public services (medical, educational and dependents care) are very relevant needs identified and prioritized through the exercise. These are considered of importance to improve the quality of life, avoid the abandonment of rural areas and attract new entrants.

The effects of COVID or BREXIT are not fully integrated in this report due to the time-lapse. Although not everything is affected by these effects, there are some aspects related to the conjunctural effects of these phenomena that have been analysed.

In the wake of COVID-19, there is a lot of insecurity in starting up businesses or continuing current activities such as farming. EU and State programmes like LEADER will be critical in rebooting this rural economy post COVID-19. The effects of the corona crisis on new rural

businesses (travel and hospitality businesses, experience industry etc.) will be significant and create new need for support and innovation.

COVID-19 has also affected the need to support of tele-working opportunities prioritized by only two regions. It is supposed how tele-working will have a stronger view for the future development of opportunities in the rural areas that cannot be neglected. Another effect is the one related to e-health, e-learning and other digital services, like e-commerce, that will allow to enhance the capacity to develop the factors of attractiveness of rural areas in the future.

Figure 19. Quality of life needs cluster map.

Figure 20. Social capital needs cluster map.

Figure 21. Cultural diversity needs cluster map

Figure 22. Natural capital needs cluster map.

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- https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_es

Annex 1. Survey about rural attractiveness in PoliRural pilot regions

- Country/Pilot (to be choice form the list):
- Municipality:
- Gender:
- Age group (18-25; 26-40; 41-55; 56-65; 65+):
- Email address (not compulsory in case of group survey e.g.: for elderly group of people, non-digital stakeholders):
- I belong to which category of stakeholder: (choice from: policy makers, rural population, recent entrants and potential entrants to rural areas, experts and innovators)
- Profession:
- Type of organisation (choice from: private enterprise; professional consultancy, self-employed; trade, business or professional association; NGO; Research or academia; Local authority (public or private); Regional/National public authority; Entrepreneur, other):
- Education:
- And other questions related to the acceptance of GDPR clauses and confidentiality matters based on the POLIRURAL GDPR and D1.3 recommendations. It is important that all the PoliRural surveys will include GDPR/privacy consent. If the survey tools do not allow following PoliRural privacy consent (i.e., for instance if the data is given to third party or deleting the data is not possible in accordance with respondent's request) they should not be used for any kind of pilot purposes. GDPR compliant surveys allow to send the consent before responding to a survey. According to GDPR, in order to collect personal data, it has to be ensured that the participant provides the consent to manage his or her personal data. Pilots are responsible to inform the respondents of the reasons why they collect personal data, where they store it, for how long they process it, and in which ways it will be use it in the future. Personal data refers information that makes possible to identify the respondents, such as name, email address, phone number, etc.

This personal data questions will be followed by a set of questions that covers the 7 pillars considered in POLIRURAL D1.3. The questionnaire has a core basis of questions, no more than 50 questions in total, that should be valid for all the regional pilots with the possibility of setting two optional questions per pilot region.

POLIRURAL SURVEY

PoliRural is a research and innovation project designed to advance rural policy development.
<https://polirural.eu/>

With this survey, we want to collect your opinion, to identify which are the main characteristics, that define the rural attractiveness of your area.

Thank you for answering the following questions and click on the "submit" button at the end to be able to pick up your answer correctly.

I accept that my answers are used in PoliRural project and the data are not used in other purposes.

*This survey instructions and questionnaire should be translated into the national/local languages prior to launch the survey. It should be respected the questions and its order to homogenise the data collection and allow the further analysis.

Table 9. Battery of proposed questions for the survey

Survey question proposed	SCALE 1=Strongly disagree,5=Strongly agree 0= Doesn't apply
1.Availability of public and other services	
There is sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises, schools, universities)	1-5
The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are sufficient	1-5
The connections between rural and urban areas (e.g., airports, train connection) are sufficient.	1-5
Good intra-regional public transportation is available in the area.	1-5
Public transportation is important to me.	1-5
There are good medical (primary care) services in your village/region	1-5
There are good schools (primary and second level) in the area	1-5
There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area	1-5
There are good daycare facilities in the area	1-5
There is a good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G/fiber)	1-5
There is adequate public provision of online e-health, e-daycare and/or elearning services	1-5
There is enough support for tele-working opportunities in the area	1-5
I feel safe and secure in my region	1-5
2. Recreation / social activities	
I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.	1-5
There are enough recreational activities for young people in the area.	1-5
There are enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet	1-5

Survey question proposed	SCALE 1=Strongly disagree,5=Strongly agree 0= Doesnt apply
Extracurricular activities (e.g.: music, dance, arts) for children are accessible in the area.	1-5
Elderly people are offered activities and a space where to meet.	1-5
This area offers quality commercial services such as restaurants, shops, car maintenance, etc.	1-5
Recreation and social activities are important to me	1-5
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	
Housing opportunities are adequate in the area.	1-5
I am proud of living in the area	1-5
Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are high	1-5
There are problems of integration with some population in the territory (Minorities, new comers....)	1-5
There are important social or political conflicts in the area	1-5
4. Demographic & human capital	
There are enough young people in the area.	1-5
There are enough women in the area.	1-5
There are enough babies born in the area.	1-5
There are enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly).	1-5
Our community and voluntary sectors are well developed and address the social needs of our region and create opportunities.	1-5
It is possible to find opportunities to develop family plans	1-5
5. Business, economy & innovation	
The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses.	1-5
There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities	1-5
There is an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area	1-5
There are adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development with the provision of experienced services	1-5
The area is good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals.	1-5
The area favours eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy)	1-5
There are not enough possibilities for employment.	1-5
The area offers possibilities for sustainable tourism (cultural heritage, nature, sports, local food,...)	1-5
The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry.	1-5
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	
Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life.	1-5
Loneliness and isolation do not affect many people in the area.	1-5
There are good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making.	1-5
In the area exists lively communities and citizen-driven local activities.	1-5
There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area.	1-5
7.Environment & biodiversity	
The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery.	1-5
Nature in the area is diverse.	1-5
High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area.	1-5
Cultivation practices in the area are done in environmentally sound way.	1-5
Environment and landscapes are important to me	1-5

Annex 2. Guidance for SWOT analysis and needs assessment

In needs gathering task, pilots are seeking to understand what factors makes rural areas and professions attractive or unattractive, for established populations and recent or potential newcomers.

1.-Survey data collection and analysis (2/3/2020-12/03/2020) (since **the launch of the survey by latest 14/2/2020** (more time for translating the survey is needed, because final version was shared to pilots on 29/1/2020): Pilots should mobilize the targeted population to ensure the success of the survey and its consistency. Once the survey period is over, on Feb. 20th, until 06/03/2020, we should proceed with the data collection and analysis to get knowledge about rural reality.

2.-Desk research on existing literature and indicators (1/2/2020-1/3/2020): In parallel, as stated in the Work Plan for T4.3, for each pilot it will be considered the literature information, making use of D1.3 and D1.1, as well as different quantitative indicators to measure qualitative aspects related to the questions (it will be used the official data from public statistics). This will provide a comparison basis between the official data and the perception of the targeted population to develop a more accurate further analysis.

3.- Draft development of SWOT analysis and discussion with regional panels (09/03/2020-27/03/2020)

A SWOT analysis and needs assessment per pilot will be implemented. At this regard, the findings from the survey analysis will be summarised in a draft SWOT (strengths and weaknesses analysis). To the extent possible, the structured SWOT will be carried out on the 7 pillars set of the survey questions that covers the 7 pillars considered in POLIRURAL D1.3

In the SWOT, it must be collected meaningful information for each category to make the tool useful.

Strengths and weakness are frequently internally-related, while opportunities and threats commonly focus on the external environment. In this sense:

- Strengths: characteristics of the territory that give it an advantage over others.
- Weaknesses: characteristics of the territory that place it at a disadvantage relative to others.
- Opportunities: elements in the environment that the territory could exploit to its advantage.
- Threats: elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the territory development.

In order to have a coordinated framework, Pilots can find in this document, a common template to fill the SWOT related to its territory.

Furthermore, SWOT results will be discussed with regional panel (workshops, interviews) to define the list of Needs and factors of attractiveness of the territory. Pilots leaders should develop the regional panel meetings between 9/03/2020-27/03/2020, to discuss and enrich the swot results and needs gathering analysis between.

Pilots should be aware that Needs must be well-rooted in the SWOT elements, to serve as a consistent and solid basis, for the definition of future political rural development strategies.

It's very important that the list of Needs must be ranked according to priorities, which further allows the development of effective strategies to address the more crucial issues in the territory.

Templates for the List of Needs is also available in this document.

Pilots should also summarize the core ideas of the discussions in order to make possible in a second step, to identify commonalities and differences with regard to individual framework conditions of territories and policy challenges.

4.-Draft global SWOT with regional clustering (27/03/2020-17/04/2020): All the information provided by Pilots, will be used to drawing a global SWOT and list of needs, clustering the conclusions based on common needs rather than geography

5.-D4.2 Grass roots needs and factors of attractiveness (17/04/2020-20/05/2020):

The previous work on global swot development and clustering of pilots based on common needs, would allow to draft a first version of the deliverable D4.2 Grass roots needs and factors of rural attractiveness by 30/04/2020, with the integration of the regional pilot SWOTS and needs to allow the D4.2 reviewers and task participants a final review to end with the final report by 20/05/2020.

Table 10. SWOT

	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01	W1.01	O1.01	T1.01
	S1.02	W1.02	O1.02	T1.02
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01	W2.01	O2.01	T2.01
	S2.02	W2.02	O2.02	T2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01	W3.01	O3.01	T3.01
	S3.02	W3.02	O3.02	T3.02
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01	W4.01	O4.01	T4.01
	S4.02	W4.02	O4.02	T4.02
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01	W5.01	O5.01	T5.01
	S5.02	W5.02	O5.02	T5.02
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01	W6.01	O6.01	T6.01
	S6.02	W6.02	O6.02	T6.02
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01	W7.01	O7.01	T7.01
	S7.02	W7.02	O7.02	T7.02

Table 11. Comments to the SWOT

(You can summarize here the information that you consider relevant for the analysis with any further explanation about the SWOT elements. For example, you can comment how the opinions in the survey match with the literature information and indicators. Please also include the indicators used to confirm the swot elements.)

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services					
2. Recreation / social activities					
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living					
4. Demographic & human capital					
5. Business, economy & innovation					
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
7. Environment & Biodiversity					

Table 12. List of Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01	Eg: established populations, new	e.g.: 1	e.g.: W1.01, T3.01
	N02			
2. Recreation / social activities	N03		e.g.: 3	e.g.: W1.01 ,O1.02, W5.01
	N04.....			
3. Living condition, quality of life and				
4. Demographic & human capital				
5. Business, economy & innovation			e.g.: 2	e.g. : W7.01, T5.02.....
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas				
7. Environment & Biodiversity				

Table 13. Results of the Discussions with Panel: (Mainly ideas)

	Comments
1. Availability of public and other services	
2. Recreation / social activities	
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	
4. Demographic & human capital	
5. Business, economy & innovation	
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	
7. Environment & Biodiversity	

Annex 3. Links to regional pilot surveys

REGION/COUNTRY	SURVEY LINK
Segóbriga Cuenca (Spain)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/a4c6b8d4-d744-0ed7-908a-fbe9292e1827
Central Bohemia (Czech Republic)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/b052cff2-3962-9259-9d30-6cceb9be4323
Hame (Finland)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/PoliRural_Survey_Finland
(Slovakia)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/poliruralSurveySK
Central Greece (Greece)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/b34fd88d-e0a8-c454-8f09-714191c6732b
Monaghan (Ireland)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Monaghan
Vidzeme (Latvia)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/AREISurvey2020
Apulia (Italy)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Pugliasurvey
Strumica/Gevgelija (North Macedonia)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Pilot11RegionMK
Mazowieckie (Poland)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/8923932
Migal (Israel)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/af6d7aca-f176-f9a1-931a-84002f64acef
Flanders (Belgium)	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/PoliRuralVlaanderen

Annex 4. Survey tool guide

To create a survey, on the EU Survey platform, it is necessary to follow the following instructions:

- 1) In order to create a survey, you must register a user. To achieve this, you must access the following link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>
- 2) Inside the portal we will see an option that, when registering, is located just below the Login button.

- 3) By clicking the link: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/cas/eim/external/register.cgi> they will ask you for the account information to create.

Create an account

[Help for external users](#)

First name

Last name

E-mail

Confirm e-mail

E-mail language

English (en)

Enter the code

By checking this box, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the [privacy statement](#)

Create an account

- 4) After registering the user and validating the account via e-mail, it is an extremely important requirement that they enter a validation method, which would be the mobile number.
- 5) Every time you will enter to your survey you'll received a different code in your mobile by SMS.

- 6) Then, after completing the entire registration and validation process, we will proceed to login. We click on the login button and we will be asked for the data shown in the image followed:

Connect to EUSurvey using:

- 7) At this point, they must select the type of account we have created.
 8) It is important to always keep in mind that every moment that access is required, you must provide the validation data (password and mobile number).
 9) Upon entering, we will have the following portal.

- 10) To create a survey, just click on the “New survey” button.

- 11) When creating a new survey, the following form will appear, asking for the basic data. These data, from the type of survey, identification, title, security in the survey, language of the survey, contact information, accept the clauses of the platform and finally, click on accept.

New Survey

*Type	<input type="radio"/> Standard Survey <input type="radio"/> Quiz This setting can be changed later in the properties again.
*Alias	<input type="text" value="8d356965-9a62-6903-76a6-b7e36a2297dc"/> Please choose a meaningful alias (e.g. ACCABCSurvey2020) as it will be part of the URL of the survey. The alias should have less than 256 characters.
*Title	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p> B <i>I</i> <u>U</u> S [List Icons] [Link/Code Icons] </p> <p> Font Sizes A Font Family </p> <hr/> <div style="height: 100px;"></div> </div>
*Security	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Open <input type="radio"/> Secured
*Pivot Language	<input type="text" value="English"/>
*Contact	<input type="text" value="E-mail"/> <input type="text" value="matmontalvo@socialinn.com"/> Please enter your contact email or the URL of a contact form of yours
*Confirmation	<input type="checkbox"/> I confirm that we will inform the EUSurvey Team (digit-eusurvey-support@ec.europa.eu) if we expect a very high number of responses to this survey (50.000+), so that potential impact can be assessed and measures put in place to deal with the peak traffic.

12) After creating the survey, we will see the editor of the survey.

13) The editor allows you to create the content, separating it by sections and adding all kinds of elements to conduct a survey.

14) The editor has 6 sections, to manage the creation of a survey.

15) Navigation (#1): In this section, we can see in a structured way, how the elements are formed within the survey.

16) Toolbox (#2): This section includes the elements that can be used to create the surveys.

17) Development area (#3): In this section, the Toolbox elements are dragged and created sequentially to shape the final survey.

Hello

Single Choice Question
 Answer 1 Answer 2 Answer 3

18) Element Properties (#4): This section is where we can see the details of each element dragged into the Development area.

19) Editor toolbar (#5): This section of the editor, allows you to perform actions on the elements, ranging from changing position, deleting the element on the Development area, copying and pasting an element that is within the Development area.

20) Settings toolbar (#6): Finally, in this last section we can enable or not, the tools offered by the editor. Also, we can see the properties of the survey, which the tool offers us.

21) As a final result, by combining the use of the aforementioned sections, we could get to have this simple example that we have below.

22) Within the options bar that we have available, for the configuration of the surveys, we have the following options:

23) Each of these options allows you to perform actions or configurations for the use of the survey. We have the following options such:

- a. Overview: This option presents the status of the survey, whether it is published or not, what is the URL, owner, start and end date and whether or not it has results.

b. Editor: This option allows the user to edit and create the surveys.

c. Test: This option allows to visualize the survey that we have selected, given a preview of the survey and its content.

d. Results: This option allows to have per section / question, the answers received by the participants.

Source Test Answers Search Reset filter Export

For performance reasons you can only set a maximum of 3 filters

Actions	Single Choice Question
All Values ▾	

No contribution to display

- e. **Participants:** This section can create lists of participants, after creating the list, participants must be added through the contact list or through a generated token.

Create new Guest List

Name	Type	Participants	Invited	Created	Actions
------	------	--------------	---------	---------	---------

No guest list created

- f. **Privileges:** In this section you can add users and define the actions they can have on the created survey. The permissions we can grant range from being able to preview the form, view the results, administer the form and manage the guest list.

Add User

User/ Department	Type	Access Form Preview	Results	Form Management	Manage Invitations	Actions
------------------	------	---------------------	---------	-----------------	--------------------	---------

No privilege configured

- g. **Translations:** In this section we can add the different translations of the components that are part of the survey form.

Edit Translations

<input type="checkbox"/>	Language	Title	Status	Actions	Export
<input type="checkbox"/>	EN	Text_Creation_Survey	Pivot Language		
<input type="checkbox"/>	ES	Prueba_Creación_Encuesta	Published		

- h. Properties: This section has all the settings that can be assigned to a survey, these range from basic information (name, title, language, etc.), advanced settings (notifications, automatic publications, reference documents and useful links), security (type of privacy, allow users who respond to surveys to be able to modify their contributions, etc.) and appearance (multiple paging, style, logos, automatic numbering, etc.).

Basic	Alias	Survey_Text
Advanced	Title	Text_Creation_Survey
Security	Pivot Language	EN
Appearance	Contact	matmontalvo@socialinnolabs.org
Publish Results		
Special Pages		
Quiz		

- i. Activity: This section is a history of those who have taken some kind of action on the survey.

Date	LogID	User	Object	Property	Event	Description	Old value
From - To							
29/01/2020 09:32:12	201	n00345bj	Draft Survey	n/a	Opened	Survey successfully loaded	
27/01/2020 18:04:41	223	n00345bj	Draft Survey	Translation	Enabled	Existing translation enabled	
27/01/2020 18:04:37	227	n00345bj	Draft Survey	Translation	Modified	Translation modified	ES 6e7e3054-1ee4-49ed-ad eb5a6dde154f: Respuesta n
27/01/2020 18:04:37	227	n00345bj	Draft Survey	Translation	Modified	Translation modified	ES 6cd861bb-282e-437e-aa02-29b47cb2dcbf: Respu 1

Good News!!!! You can also have a look to the online training course provided by the Commision. It's a bit outdated but it helps!!!!

Online surveys made easy with EUSurvey!

Annex 5. Survey results

Table 14. Numbers of responses by age and gender

PILOT / COUNTRY	AGE 18-25:Nº Responses	AGE 26-40:Nº Responses	AGE 41-55:Nº Responses	AGE 56-65:Nº Responses	AGE >65:Nº Responses	GENDER Male:Nº Responses	GENDER Female:Nº Responses
Slovakia	52	43	33	18	11	80	77
Central Greece/ Greece	0	9	10	8	4	23	8
Hame / Finland	2	14	41	25	8	25	65
Vidzeme / Latvia	21	143	174	87	14	101	338
Monaghan / Ireland	1	15	36	20	6	39	39
Central Bohemian Región / Cze	0	18	18	2	3	25	16
Cuenca / Spain	8	15	20	11	2	32	24
Flanders / Belgium	2	32	37	24	8	66	37
Galilee / Israel	0	5	9	3	8	17	8
Apulia / Italy	1	9	9	6	4	20	10
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	13	50	41	13	2	75	44
Mazowieckie / Poland	2	32	37	24	8	66	37
	102	385	465	241	78	569	703

Table 15. Numbers of responses by category / organization

PILOT / COUNTRY	CATEGORY Policy Maker	CATEGORY Rural Population	CATEGORY Recent entrants to rural areas	CATEGORY Potential entrants to rural areas	CATEGORY Experts	CATEGORY Innovators	CATEGORY Others
Slovakia	5	58	14	17	13	6	44
Central Greece/ Greece	2	20	2	1	2	2	2
Hame / Finland	4	57	14	7	21	3	1
Vidzeme / Latvia	31	247	25	16	23	7	90
Monaghan / Ireland	0	48	2	1	6	1	20
Central Bohemian Región / CZR	9	23	0	1	5	1	2
Cuenca / Spain	7	30	1	0	2	0	16
Flanders / Belgium	5	76	3	2	9	1	6
Galilee / Israel	0	5	1	0	7	6	6
Apulia / Italy	2	9	1	1	5	2	11
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	7	61	4	5	27	2	13
Mazowieckie / Poland	5	76	3	2	9	1	6
	77	710	70	52	129	32	217

PILOT / COUNTRY	ORGANISATION Private Enterprise	ORGANISATION Professional consultancy	ORGANISATION Self-employed	ORGANISATION Farmer	ORGANISATION Business or Professional Association	ORGANISATION Entrepreneur	ORGANISATION Research or Academia	ORGANISATION Local Authority	ORGANISATION Regional Authority	ORGANISATION National Authority:	ORGANISATION NGO:	ORGANISATION Other
Slovakia	12	2	12	20	1	3	21	16	3	2	7	58
Central Greece/ Greece	3	1	4	16	1	0	1	1	3	0	0	1
Hame / Finland	9	3	5	10	1	9	10	2	13	3	11	19
Vidzeme / Latvia	85	7	46	28	1	10	7	137	12	19	17	70
Monaghan / Ireland	5	3	7	2	7	0	5	4	0	5	12	27
Central Bohemian Región / CZR	5	0	2	5	0	0	2	15	0	0	7	5
Cuenca / Spain	8	0	5	2	1	1	0	21	0	1	1	16
Flanders / Belgium	10	5	5	11	4	0	12	5	16	2	7	18
Galilee / Israel	1	1	0	0	1	1	18	2	1	0	0	0
Apulia / Italy	3	5	2	4	3	1					5	11
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	29	3	7	33	0	3	11	8	4	11	10	0
Mazowieckie / Poland	10	5	5	11	4	0	12	5	16	2	7	18
	180	35	100	142	24	28	99	216	68	45	84	243

D4.2 Grassroot Needs & Factors of Rural Attractiveness

First column: Strongly disagree (SD)
 Second column: Disagree (D)
 Third column: Neutral (N)
 Fourth column: Agree (A)
 Fifth column: Strongly agree (SA)
 Sixth column: Doesn't apply (DA)

Table 16. Number of responses by question's numbers

PILOT / COUNTRY	P1. Q1						P1. Q2						P1. Q3						P1. Q4						P1. Q5						P1. Q6					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	6	34	36	69	10	2	13	33	32	62	15	2	8	58	36	50	4	1	6	32	50	55	13	1	7	15	34	62	30	9	16	47	29	52	13	0
Central Greece/ Greece	0	7	15	5	2	1	0	8	11	10	2	0	1	13	12	4	1	0	0	12	8	9	2	0	0	2	7	18	4	0	3	4	15	9	0	0
Hame / Finland	35	36	4	9	4	2	28	33	11	11	6	1	27	41	11	7	3	1	29	45	9	3	2	1	3	14	21	25	11	16	8	20	15	27	17	3
Vidzeme / Latvia	36	110	89	138	51	15	59	139	66	104	40	31	53	166	88	96	23	13	40	152	103	94	29	21	35	50	99	98	83	74	42	118	73	157	46	3
Monaghan / Ireland	0	9	6	38	25	0	1	12	11	36	16	2	2	11	8	32	24	0	2	6	7	33	27	1	24	23	14	8	3	4	3	23	5	25	19	0
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	2	13	5	9	11	1	3	6	3	18	10	1	4	9	6	15	6	1	2	9	6	15	6	3	0	1	10	13	16	1	6	9	9	14	3	0
Cuenca / Spain	12	25	10	9	0	1	9	22	10	14	1	2	15	28	3	8	2	0	25	23	4	4	0	32	0	1	6	17	32	6	6	18	13	12	6	4
Flanders / Belgium	15	36	14	24	13	0	12	28	10	35	17	1	21	22	17	26	15	2	18	32	15	27	9	0	6	7	23	28	36	3	2	8	13	37	40	2
Galilee / Israel	9	13	1	0	1	1	6	11	6	2	0	0	9	11	1	2	0	0	5	10	6	2	0	0	2	2	3	12	4	1	2	17	3	2	0	0
Apulia / Italy	7	15	5	5	1	2	1	17	8	1	1	2	1	11	11	5	6	1	2	7	14	6	2	1	1	3	12	11	2	2	1	6	12	9	2	1
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	21	33	22	35	5	3	10	23	22	56	7	1	13	38	25	38	5	0	9	36	17	52	5	0	0	8	8	58	41	4	25	41	18	32	3	0
Mazowieckie / Poland	15	36	14	24	13	0	12	28	10	35	17	1	21	22	17	26	15	2	18	32	15	27	9	0	6	7	23	28	36	3	2	8	13	37	40	2
Total	158	367	221	360	136	28	154	360	200	384	132	44	175	430	235	309	98	21	156	396	254	327	102	60	84	133	260	378	298	121	116	319	218	413	189	14

PILOT / COUNTRY	P1. Q7						P1. Q8						P1. Q9						P1. Q10						P1. Q11						P1. Q12						P1. Q13					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	2	12	18	86	38	1	6	18	21	72	39	1	7	24	31	76	16	3	11	30	24	67	23	2	5	43	48	49	9	3	13	37	65	26	2	14	6	31	44	64	12	0
Central Greece/ Greece	2	3	5	18	3	0	4	13	7	3	3	1	2	15	6	6	0	2	0	1	9	20	0	1	0	9	18	4	0	0	3	15	11	2	0	0	0	10	6	13	2	0
Hame / Finland	7	12	10	32	19	10	6	9	9	35	24	7	4	6	15	19	18	28	7	15	15	32	20	0	4	11	20	35	14	6	4	12	12	30	19	13	0	1	2	33	54	0
Vidzeme / Latvia	16	34	61	215	104	9	36	73	68	183	68	11	37	99	124	86	20	73	33	69	183	84	4	15	50	135	164	44	31	40	122	132	72	20	53	34	67	110	165	60	3	
Monaghan / Ireland	31	33	7	0	3	2	11	30	10	19	6	0	10	23	13	21	6	4	4	24	6	15	26	1	1	5	18	24	18	7	0	7	17	30	18	4	11	37	12	10	4	1
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	4	6	4	17	10	0	12	9	6	10	2	2	2	4	6	22	7	0	6	7	8	14	6	0	12	5	10	3	1	10	4	13	8	5	4	7	1	0	6	16	18	0
Cuenca / Spain	7	12	8	23	4	1	19	20	8	7	1	1	27	17	3	6	1	1	23	17	7	8	1	0	22	20	12	2	0	0	36	16	2	1	0	4	9	21	13	9	4	0
Flanders / Belgium	2	13	18	27	41	2	9	18	12	35	22	4	0	2	14	39	34	12	0	5	15	48	35	0	2	9	33	27	17	15	4	7	26	30	25	8	1	4	3	36	57	2
Galilee / Israel	0	4	7	10	3	1	0	10	4	7	4	0	0	3	7	9	3	2	1	6	4	9	4	0	1	10	6	7	0	1	0	7	9	5	2	1	2	0	3	8	11	1
Apulia / Italy	2	5	7	12	2	1	1	6	9	12	1	1	1	6	8	13	2	1	1	7	14	8	5	1	1	7	10	2	1	4	2	10	5	7	3	5	2	2	12	7	1	5
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	10	33	24	41	9	2	11	49	21	34	3	1	23	50	16	27	1	2	7	9	14	69	18	2	13	39	28	31	3	5	12	39	36	24	3	5	5	19	22	48	20	5
Mazowieckie / Poland	2	13	18	27	41	2	9	18	12	35	22	4	0	2	14	39	34	12	0	5	15	48	35	0	2	9	33	27	17	15	4	7	26	30	25	8	1	4	3	36	57	2
Total	85	180	187	508	277	31	124	273	187	452	195	33	112	251	257	363	142	140	93	188	197	521	257	11	78	217	371	375	124	97	122	292	349	262	118	122	72	196	236	445	300	19

D4.2 Grassroot Needs & Factors of Rural Attractiveness

PILOT / COUNTRY	P2. Q14						P2. Q15						P2. Q16						P2. Q17						P2. Q18						P2. Q19						P2. Q20					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	5	44	29	58	20	1	8	50	47	35	16	1	11	64	41	33	7	1	1	24	41	71	19	1	3	23	48	71	11	1	5	28	27	82	15	0	1	5	32	70	48	1
Central Greece/ Greece	1	7	14	9	0	0	2	13	6	8	0	1	2	3	12	13	1	0	0	4	8	15	3	1	0	12	7	10	1	1	0	4	13	13	1	0	0	2	3	20	6	0
Hame / Finland	2	15	21	36	16	0	12	26	20	17	4	11	13	27	17	17	3	13	5	20	15	28	8	14	6	16	18	24	9	17	8	22	12	40	7	1	1	6	15	44	21	2
Vidzeme / Latvia	8	75	63	196	96	1	19	113	100	142	49	16	22	157	104	112	24	20	11	40	58	205	106	19	14	50	99	180	55	41	29	107	77	176	48	2	3	7	55	215	149	10
Monaghan / Ireland	9	27	12	25	5	0	5	14	10	33	14	0	2	11	7	36	21	0	6	35	13	20	2	0	3	29	17	15	10	2	10	36	6	18	5	1	36	37	3	0	0	1
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	3	5	8	17	7	1	2	10	9	14	5	1	6	8	11	11	4	1	4	3	4	20	9	1	2	8	12	11	4	2	6	10	7	13	5	0	0	2	9	17	13	0
Cuenca / Spain	21	18	10	6	0	0	24	23	7	0	0	1	18	18	12	5	1	1	16	18	10	8	1	5	6	11	15	17	5	1	13	21	13	6	1	38	1	0	1	14	38	5
Flanders / Belgium	2	10	17	41	33	0	4	8	18	44	25	3	0	15	29	34	18	6	0	8	12	52	29	2	0	10	23	44	16	10	4	20	14	41	24	0	0	2	13	47	39	2
Galilee / Israel	1	10	3	8	3	0	2	9	8	4	1	0	5	5	8	4	1	2	1	4	7	10	1	2	0	2	4	16	2	0	1	4	8	11	1	0	0	0	4	13	8	0
Apulia / Italy	3	8	4	8	3	4	3	2	13	4	2	5	3	4	9	7	4	3	2	3	10	10	3	2	2	6	8	9	1	3	11	2	8	15	3	2	2	2	11	10	2	3
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	23	48	26	18	1	3	31	49	23	12	1	3	45	42	20	8	1	3	27	53	19	16	1	3	17	46	22	26	2	6	13	17	21	55	9	4	3	3	8	71	29	5
Mazowieckie / Poland	2	10	17	41	33	0	4	8	18	44	25	3	0	15	29	34	18	6	0	8	12	52	29	2	0	10	23	44	16	10	4	20	14	41	24	0	0	2	13	47	39	2
TOTAL	80	277	224	463	217	10	116	325	279	357	142	45	127	369	299	314	103	56	73	220	209	507	211	52	53	223	296	467	132	94	93	291	220	511	143	48	47	68	167	568	392	31

PILOT / COUNTRY	P3. Q21						P3. Q22						P3. Q23						P3. Q24						P3. Q25															
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA				
Slovakia	6	36	38	65	11	1	4	14	28	60	48	3	5	36	34	66	16	0	3	27	46	51	26	4	13	46	55	30	10	3										
Central Greece/ Greece	0	3	19	8	0	1	1	1	8	18	3	0	0	1	9	14	6	1	1	9	8	7	6	0	2	14	9	4	1	1										
Hame / Finland	2	16	13	32	23	4	0	5	8	21	52	1							6	3	21	34	21	5	6															0
Vidzeme / Latvia	95	194	57	76	7	10	9	9	61	191	164	5	16	83	107	159	71	3	19	100	152	81	25	62	91	162	101	42	12	31										
Monaghan / Ireland	0	20	14	25	16	2	33	33	5	5	0	1	13	35	14	12	2	1	14	41	11	5	2	2	14	23	19	20	0	1										
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	2	6	7	25	1	0	0	0	3	18	20	0	0	6	13	16	6	0	4	16	11	6	2	2	11	21	2	4	1	2										
Cuenca / Spain	6	11	17	15	5	32	0	1	6	15	32	8	4	6	13	23	8	4	14	16	12	5	4	3	24	12	10	4	3	1										
Flanders / Belgium	1	5	10	62	25	0	1	3	22	29	48	0	3	8	23	43	26	0	9	29	41	19	2	3	20	37	29	10	1	6										
Galilee / Israel	1	3	6	11	3	0	1	1	1	6	16	0	0	4	2	11	8	0	1	2	8	10	2	1	0	5	7	12	1	0										
Apulia / Italy	2	3	6	8	4	7	1	1	4	11	8	4	2	2	4	11	7	2	1	6	8	11	1	3	5	4	7	10	1	2										
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	6	21	32	53	3	4	5	12	27	51	16	8	12	20	29	43	12	3	10	40	34	25	4	6	7	26	38	36	8	4										
Mazowieckie / Poland	1	5	10	62	25	0	1	3	22	29	48	0	3	8	23	43	26	0	9	29	41	19	2	3	20	37	29	10	1	6										
TOTAL	122	323	229	442	123	61	56	83	195	454	455	30	58	209	271	441	188	20	88	336	406	260	81	95	207	387	306	182	39	57										

D4.2 Grassroot Needs & Factors of Rural Attractiveness

PILOT / COUNTRY	P4. Q26						P4. Q27						P4. Q28						P4. Q29						P4. Q30						P4. Q31					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	2	30	30	80	14	1	2	11	47	81	16	0	5	36	51	53	11	1	7	35	40	68	4	3	8	32	67	40	5	5	1	18	58	72	6	2
Central Greece/ Greece	0	6	13	11	1	0	0	6	11	1	1	0	0	18	6	6	1	0	1	9	7	13	0	1	1	9	18	2	1	0	1	6	17	7	0	0
Hame / Finland	15	36	16	18	3	2	2	10	35	34	4	4	15	42	22	5	0	6	7	39	23	19	0	1	2	7	16	45	19	1	3	5	20	16	5	41
Vidzeme / Latvia	52	172	76	120	16	3	13	37	113	233	37	6	67	186	80	82	20	4	46	167	97	110	12	7	49	153	135	75	11	16	28	92	137	145	26	11
Monaghan / Ireland	8	35	16	17	2	0	6	46	19	4	2	0	9	41	20	5	1	1	3	25	28	21	0	0	9	36	10	17	4	0	4	26	19	22	4	2
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	0	0	5	21	15	0	0	0	3	19	19	0	1	4	3	18	13	2	0	3	2	19	13	3	1	11	8	14	2	5	0	10	11	13	2	4
Cuenca / Spain	30	17	6	2	1	3	14	18	14	7	3	2	33	19	2	2		2	21	20	7	6	2	0	21	20	8	4	0	3	16	21	7	7	3	5
Flanders / Belgium	0	9	20	53	18	1	0	0	21	64	16	1	0	3	28	49	19	3	0	14	24	46	16	1	1	10	18	51	17	4	0	6	19	49	21	7
Galilee / Israel	0	12	4	9	0	0	0	2	10	12	0	1	0	4	7	12	0	1	1	9	5	10	0	0	1	7	7	8	2	0	1	7	9	6	1	1
Apulia / Italy	3	8	4	11	3	3	1	4	14	6	1	3	2	4	11	9	1	2	1	3	13	9	2	1	1	5	11	9	1	2	1	5	11	9	1	2
Geveljija-Strumica / FYROM	30	52	11	19	5	2	9	41	27	33	5	4	22	56	17	15	3	6	15	51	13	26	9	5	22	57	16	17	2	5	14	37	23	2	6	
Mazowieckie / Poland	0	9	20	53	18	1	0	0	21	64	16	1	0	3	28	49	19	3	0	14	24	46	16	1	1	10	18	51	17	4	0	6	19	49	21	7
	140	386	221	414	93	16	47	175	335	558	120	22	154	416	275	305	88	31	102	389	283	393	74	23	117	357	332	333	81	45	69	239	364	418	92	88

PILOT / COUNTRY	P5. Q32						P5. Q33						P5. Q34						P5. Q35						P5. Q36					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	10	48	53	38	2	6	17	48	61	26	2	3	23	56	57	10	1	10	18	45	57	29	2	6	8	28	48	53	17	3
Central Greece/ Greece	2	16	9	4	0	0	2	6	18	5	0	0	5	18	7	1	0	0	3	15	11	2	0	0	4	11	5	11	0	0
Hame / Finland	3	9	27	32	3	15	1	13	24	29	9	12	8	28	27	11	0	15	4	11	30	29	4	11	4	22	31	23	2	8
Vidzeme / Latvia	37	98	124	131	23	26	27	91	143	126	22	30	87	162	121	19	6	44	44	133	144	67	13	38	20	85	100	180	37	17
Monaghan / Ireland	2	37	18	14	4	2	0	39	14	19	3	2	0	11	27	27	7	5	0	31	18	16	6	5	4	28	21	17	4	3
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	10	12	4	4	0	11	6	13	9	8	0	5	15	11	1	1	0	12	11	15	2	3	0	10	11	8	5	8	0	7
Cuenca / Spain	18	17	5	10	5	4	20	15	14	3	4	1	30	15	6	3	1	3	25	18	6	4	3	18	4	5	9	18	18	13
Flanders / Belgium	0	16	20	42	19	6	0	11	31	38	11	12	1	11	53	9	7	21	1	12	42	25	8	14	2	13	37	35	7	9
Galilee / Israel	3	13	5	4	0	0	3	11	5	4	0	2	3	9	4	7	0	2	1	12	4	6	0	2	1	8	5	9	1	1
Apulia / Italy	1	4	12	9	1	2	1	4	6	7	4	6	1	5	11	5	5	2	2	3	12	9	3	12	3	5	8	12	1	1
Geveljija-Strumica / FYROM	7	31	29	48	2	2	10	34	37	34	0	4	13	41	43	19	0	3	10	48	39	18	1	3	13	44	39	21	0	2
Mazowieckie / Poland	0	16	20	42	19	6	0	11	31	38	11	12	1	11	53	9	7	21	1	12	42	25	8	14	2	13	37	35	7	9
	93	317	326	378	78	80	87	296	393	337	66	89	187	378	410	121	34	138	120	355	407	233	48	121	76	270	345	422	93	73

PILOT / COUNTRY	P5. Q37						P5. Q38						P5. Q39						P5. Q40					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	22	39	67	21	2	6	16	45	37	52	7	0	5	21	36	71	24	0	6	23	49	57	21	1
Central Greece/ Greece	2	5	6	16	2	0	3	17	10	1	0	0	1	3	9	15	3	0	0	3	7	18	3	0
Hame / Finland	5	20	36	18	0	11	15	39	21	11	2	2	4	4	16	48	19	1	1	2	7	43	31	6
Vidzeme / Latvia	37	85	156	112	22	27	86	183	73	82	9	6	9	46	83	226	71	4	8	31	59	242	77	22
Monaghan / Ireland	0	14	30	25	4	3	1	22	11	32	11	0	10	35	10	16	5	0	11	31	25	8	1	2
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	9	12	7	4	1	8	4	13	6	13	5	0	0	3	9	15	13	1	0	3	9	16	7	6
Cuenca / Spain	8	9	10	14	13	2	17	19	11	6	2	13	3	5	12	23	13	23	1	4	4	23	23	12
Flanders / Belgium	9	36	30	15	6	6	1	12	24	44	17	3	3	12	16	45	25	1	12	13	17	38	19	4
Galilee / Israel	0	6	12	5	1	1	11	12	1	1	0	0	0	4	3	12	6	0	0	1	6	13	4	1
Apulia / Italy	3	6	14	5	1																			16
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	2	13	17	69	16	2	11	37	37	26	6	2	8	25	26	51	6	3	4	24	24	57	7	3
Mazowieckie / Poland	9	36	30	15	6	6	1	12	24	44	17	3	3	12	16	45	25	1	12	13	17	38	19	4
	106	281	415	319	74	72	166	411	255	312	76	29	46	170	236	567	210	34	55	148	224	553	212	61

PILOT / COUNTRY	P6. Q41						P6. Q42						P6. Q43						P6. Q44						P6. Q45					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	3	33	344	71	11	5	6	37	49	54	3	8	10	35	50	56	4	2	4	30	42	69	10	2	3	19	56	67	8	4
Central Greece/ Greece	0	3	9	17	0	2	5	7	6	11	0	2	2	5	16	6	0	2	1	14	8	5	0	3	2	2	9	14	1	3
Hame / Finland	1	6	13	44	24	2	5	42	23	12	0	8	4	22	21	33	3	7	0	7	18	45	18	2	0	5	12	46	23	4
Vidzeme / Latvia	12	72	111	191	42	11	40	181	137	52	7	22	23	105	149	129	17	16	17	73	144	176	21	8	11	45	90	227	59	7
Monaghan / Ireland	4	35	14	16	6	1	3	4	4	46	20	0	2	12	23	31	9	0	8	38	15	13	2	0	7	45	12	10	2	2
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	0	4	6	19	7	5	0	4	10	22	4	1	0	1	6	29	4	0	1	5	7	23	5	0	1	5	25	10	0	0
Cuenca / Spain	2	14	11	17	12	2	12	19	11	12	2	6	7	22	11	10	6	4	6	22	11	12	4	6	5	12	17	16	6	24
Flanders / Belgium	2	20	22	47	10	2	1	36	26	28	8	4	3	18	26	42	12	1	0	12	27	50	14	0	0	2	17	62	22	0
Galilee / Israel	1	8	4	12	0	0	1	10	5	7	1	1	1	7	10	6	0	1	1	2	7	11	3	0	1	5	8	8	2	1
Apulia / Italy	1	4	10	4	4	6	1	5	5	10	5	3	1	5	8	9	5	1	1	5	6	16	1	1	1	3	7	15	2	1
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	11	21	29	50	3	5	19	38	25	27	3	7	16	47	34	17	2	3	21	49	35	10	2	2	9	35	23	43	5	4
Mazowieckie / Poland	2	20	22	47	10	2	1	36	26	28	8	4	3	18	26	42	12	1	0	12	27	50	14	0	0	2	17	62	22	0
	39	240	595	535	129	43	94	419	327	309	61	66	72	297	380	410	74	38	60	269	347	480	93	24	38	176	273	595	162	50

PILOT / COUNTRY	P7. Q46						P7. Q47						P7. Q48						P7. Q49						P7. Q50					
	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA	SD	D	N	A	SA	DA
Slovakia	1	6	25	73	52	0	0	12	20	75	50	0	6	30	61	39	16	5	13	36	67	32	7	2	1	4	9	41	102	0
Central Greece/ Greece	0	1	4	19	7	0	0	6	8	11	6	0	0	3	9	16	3	0	1	5	17	3	3	2	0	0	4	15	12	0
Hame / Finland	0	1	6	24	59	0	0	1	7	26	56	0	2	9	24	22	25	8	0	8	23	36	18	4	0	1	1	17	70	0
Vidzeme / Latvia	6	8	14	188	221	2	6	9	18	193	211	2	9	45	112	163	101	9	14	79	133	141	49	23	9	1	11	103	313	2
Monaghan / Ireland	31	37	5	4	0	0	19	41	5	8	1	1	7	25	13	22	3	7	3	16	24	28	4	2	51	22	2	1	0	1
Central Bohemian Region / CZR	0	2	6	18	15	0	1	5	5	16	14	0	4	2	8	10	7	10	5	19	10	4	2	0	0	0	0	10	31	0
Cuenca / Spain	4	4	7	17	24	17	1	3	9	25	17	2	8	18	16	8	2	12	4	8	16	14	12	34	2	0	2	18	34	0
Flanders / Belgium	9	23	13	36	22	0	9	23	12	41	15	1	8	12	30	29	19	3	19	26	31	14	8	3	0	1	1	15	84	1
Galilee / Israel	0	0	1	2	22	0	0	0	1	3	21	0	0	2	5	18	0	0	3	8	12	1	1	0	0	0	4	20	0	0
Apulia / Italy	1	4	5	8	5	7	1	1	6	10	5	6	1	3	5	14	2	4	2	3	12	10	1	1	1	3	8	9	6	1
Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM	1	2	12	69	34	1	1	3	12	69	33	1	11	36	23	40	7	2	9	41	28	33	3	5	0	3	3	50	62	1
Mazowieckie / Poland	9	23	13	36	22	0	9	23	12	41	15	1	8	12	30	29	19	3	19	26	31	14	8	3	0	1	1	15	84	1
	61	111	111	494	483	27	47	127	115	518	444	14	64	195	333	397	222	63	89	270	400	341	116	80	64	36	42	298	818	7

Annex 6. PILOTS' SWOT

Table 17. Flanders / BELGIUM SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Public services are available in rural areas or in nearby areas	W1.01 Public transport is not frequent in most rural areas	O1.01 Improvement of public transport availability	T1.01 Transport problem: traffic diversion due to general traffic jam problem in Flanders
	S1.02 Internet and telecommunication is widely available in Flanders	W1.02 Compared to urban areas less demand for public and other services	O1.02 Increase availability of other transportation types as for example car sharing	T1.02 Closure of train stations and train station counters in rural areas
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Compared to urban areas in Flanders there are more green open areas in rural areas of Flanders	W2.01 Due to less demand compared to urban areas less variety in recreation/social activities	O2.01 Further development of recreation activities can boost tourism in rural areas	T2.01 Conflicts between different types of recreation (e.g. hikers and cyclist)
	S2.02 In general: well developed network of bicycle/hiking routes	W2.02 Certain types of recreation require specific infrastructure which is not possible in rural areas due to environmental constraints (e.g. paved paths)	O2.02 Improvement of connectivity between rural and other areas will further increase recreation in rural areas	T2.02 Too many people from urban areas who come to rural area for recreation
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 availability/price of houses with gardens in green area	W3.01 Housing for elderly people (e.g. retirement homes) are often not located in rural areas, also low availability of social housing	O3.01 demand for specific housing types that are present in rural areas e.g. homesteads	T3.01 Possible conflict between agriculture and inhabitants (e.g. odour nuisance)
	S3.02 In general standard of living in rural areas is comparable to standard of living in urban areas	W3.02 poverty in rural areas	O3.02 people who want to live in green areas	T3.02 If too many people come live in rural areas the rural character might disappear, also change in housing type (e.g. more apartments)
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 Social control in rural areas	W4.01 Less working people (because more elderly people)	O4.01 Newcomers in rural areas	T4.01 Increase of number of elderly people in rural areas
	S4.02 Less crime in rural areas	W4.02 Less diverse population (e.g. skills)	O4.02 Social and cultural diversification of population	T4.02 Less youth in rural areas
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 besides agriculture there are also other economic activities in rural areas	W5.01 competition between similar businesses (e.g. two bakeries in one town)	O5.01 rural tourism development	T5.01 presence of economic activities other than agriculture can disturb the rural character
	S5.02 Wide range of measures to support agriculture industry/farmers	W5.02 distance of rural area to other industrial sites	O5.02 trainings of new and innovative techniques in the agriculture sector	T5.02 aging of farmers, no successor
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 social control in rural areas	W6.01 smaller communities compared to urban areas of Flanders	O6.01 newcomers	T6.01 loneliness of elderly people
	S6.02 social cohesion in rural areas	W6.02 less diverse cultural landscape (e.g. theatre, dance performances etc.)	O6.02 interest of people in heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g. small landscape elements)	T6.02 poverty in rural areas
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Large open green areas in rural Flanders	W7.01 rural landscape is highly fragmentated	O7.01 availability of open space	T7.01 conflict between agriculture and nature sector
	S7.02 People living in rural areas highly value the rural landscape/environment	W7.02 environmental issues related to agricultural practices	O7.02 encourage more farmers to take environment measures	T7.02 changing climate (e.g. in past two years severe droughts which impacted the agricultural sector in Flanders)

Table 18. Central Bohemian / CZECH REPUBLIC SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Functional connection with the capital city Prague		O1.01 High density/network of roads across the region	
	S1.02 Functional connection with the capital city Prague, which is the natural centre of the Central Bohemian Region	W1.02 Weak interconnection between/among local centres/towns		
		W1.03 Full capacity of railway lines to commute to the capital city Prague		
	S1.04 Good transport accessibility to most parts of the region to both Prague and regional centres		O1.04 New technologies available/using to enhance quality of public transport infrastructure	
			O1.05 Willingness of inhabitants to prefer public transport	
		W1.06 Insufficient institutional coordination in the healthcare sector with the capital city Prague Indebtedness of some hospitals whose financial problems		T1.06 An aging population will pose increased risks to existing systems and services Limited role and competence of the region in health policy
		W1.07 Intra-regional differences in capacities of kindergartens and elementary schools, endangered general education in peripheries, capacity insufficiency in suburbs		T1.07 Lack of funds from municipal budgets to increase the capacity of kindergartens, primary schools in some locations Lack of good teachers and professionals due to their low financial remuneration
				T1.08 Lack/declining of teachers and professionals due to the generational change
		W1.07 Intra-regional differences in capacities of kindergartens and elementary schools, endangered general education in peripheries, capacity insufficiency in suburbs		
	S1.10 High number of ICT service providers	W1.10 Insufficient high-speed internet infrastructure in the whole Central Bohemia Region	O1.10 Starting of 5G pilot activities in the Czech Republic	T1.10 High number of small municipalities whose representatives do not appreciate the importance of ICT/high-speed internet infrastructure
		W1.11 Low involvement of municipalities, lack of standardization of e-government, insufficient information of citizens about existing possibilities	O1.11 Using of assistive technologies, telemedicine and IT technologies for monitoring, target person support and management of the involvement of carers and relatives of health and social services started	
	S1.12 Importance of work-life balance is more discussed	W1.12 Willingness of employer to offer remote working is still low (changes due to current situation with COVID-19 are expected)	O1.12 Development of flexible employment and digitalisation can start moving people to the countryside (in the case of the Central Bohemia Region moving to its outer peripheral areas)	
	S1.13 Low level criminal offences			

PILLAR	STRENGTHS		OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Diverse natural and cultural-historical attractions (including UNESCO sites)		O2.01 Number of community activities	
				T2.02 Insufficient systematic financial security of local cultural activities
			O2.03 Using of buildings owned by the municipality for various purposes	
		W2.04 Low quality of services in peripheral areas of the region		
			O2.05 Community activities support the local identity	
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 The most populous region in the Czech Republic and the most profitable in terms of population in the long term	W3.02 High price of properties in part of the region close to Prague	O3.02 Affordable price of properties in peripheral parts of the region	
	S3.02 Strong local identity			
	S3.03 High quality of environment	W3.03 Air pollution related to using of local fireplaces (namely in areas with no gasification)	O3.03 Focus on wellbeing in new strategic documents related to the regional development	
		W3.04 Selective inner migration to certain parts of the region, polarity in population growth		T3.04 Insufficient integration of newly arrived foreign workers into local communities
	S3.05 No political or social conflicts in the region			
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 Relatively young age structure of population compared to the rest of the Czech Republic		O4.01 Diversified age structure of inhabitants in municipalities	
	S4.02 Equal gender structure of inhabitants			
			O4.03 The Central Bohemian Region has one of the highest birthrate in comparison with other regions of the Czech Republic	
	S4.04 Low unemployment rate in comparison with other regions of the Czech Republic and EU regions The labour market in the Central Bohemian Region and Prague is functionally interconnected, functioning uniformly regardless of administrative division	W4.04 Selective migration to certain parts of the region, polarity in population growth	O4.04 Interest of talented people from abroad for work in the region	
		W4.05 Low level of local identity of newcomers (especially in suburban areas)		
				T4.06 Insufficient systematic financial security of local activities and services
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 A large number of research institutes and the emergence of new research infrastructures	W5.01 Weak links between research and business sectors, inconsistencies between the main focus of private and public research	O5.01 Interest of talented people from abroad to work in the region	
		W5.02 Weak innovation demand of the public sector - the state and public administration do not support innovative		

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS	
	S5.03 Foreign companies play a more important role in the economy compared to other regions of the Czech Republic	W5.03 Endogenous Czech business is not supported under same conditions as multinational companies			
		W5.04 Low and stagnant rate of entrepreneurial activity in peripheral parts of the region			
			O5.05 Strengthening of youth entrepreneurship <i>Innovative and creative ventures as a financial tool to</i>		
			O5.06 Ongoing transition to the circular economy Supporting of local production and shortening of supply chains Opportunities for agrotourism (increasing of entrepreneurs in this field)	T5.06 Loss of job opportunities in small municipalities ("brain drain" to the capital city Prague)	
		S5.07 Manufacturing, especially the automotive, engineering and food industries, has a key role in the economy		O5.07 Digital transition - opportunities for new economic activities and productivity growth	
				O5.06 Ongoing transition to the circular economy in agriculture (including energy recovery) Supporting of local production and shortening of supply chains Opportunities for agrotourism (increasing of entrepreneurs in this field)	
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Equal gender structure				
			O6.02 Qualitative change of "typical citizen of retirement age" - active in both social and economic life		
	S6.03 Low level criminal offences				
			O6.04 Bringing life to local communities through the transition of new residents	T6.04 Insufficient integration of newly arrived foreign workers into local communities	
			O6.05 Number of community activities <i>Community activities support the local identity</i>		
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Quality natural environment				
	S7.02 Diverse natural and cultural-historical attractions (including UNESCO sites)				
	S7.03 Nature preservation, supporting of sustainability	W7.03 Inconsistent attitude towards interventions against bark beetle in protected areas			
			O7.04 Increasing number of entrepreneurs in the field of bioproduction	T7.04 Unsustainable land management, landscape water scarcity and biodiversity decline	
	S7.05 High number of community activities in the field of protection of environment		O7.05 Adaptation to climate change		

Table 19. SLOVAKIA SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	There is sufficient public transportation to hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises.	The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are not sufficient.	The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are not sufficient.	There is not
	There is sufficient public transportation to secondary and vocational schools and universities.	The connections between rural and urban areas (e.g. airports, train connection) are not sufficient.	There is no adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services.	
	There are good schools (kindergarten and primary) in the area.			
	There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area.	There are no sufficient good medical (primary attention) services in your village/region.		
	There are good day care facilities in the area.			
	There is a good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G/fiber).			
	The security is not a problem in the area.			
2. Recreation / social activities	Extracurricular activities (e.g.: music, dance, arts) for children are accessible in the area.	There is not plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.	Recreational and social activities are important.	
	Elderly people are offered activities and a space where to meet.			There are not enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet.
	This area offers quality commercial services such as restaurants, shops, car maintenance, etc.			
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	People are proud of living in the area.	There are problems with the integration of some part of populations (minorities, new entries)	Housing opportunities are not yet sufficiently adequate in the area.	
	There are no social or political conflicts in the area.		Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are not yet sufficiently considered of	
4. Demographic & human capital	There are enough young people in the area.	The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend		
	There are enough women in the area.	There are not enough babies born in the area.	It is possible to find marriage and dating partners from the area.	
		Community and voluntary sector are not well developed focused on social needs and creation of new		
5. Business, economy & innovation		There are not enough possibilities for employment.	The area is good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals.	
		The area does not favor eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry.	There are not many instruments for financing innovative/new rural activities.
				There is not an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area.
				There are no adequate services for entrepreneurial support with the provision of experienced services.

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life	In the area do not exist sufficiently lively communities and citizen-driven local activities.	Loneliness and isolation affect quite a few people in the area.	There are no good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making.
	There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area.			
7. Environment & Biodiversity	The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery.		High Nature Value Areas are not yet well valorized in the area.	Cultivation practices in the area are not done in environmentally sound way.
	Nature in the area is diverse.		Environment and nature play an important role.	

Table 20. Häme / FINLAND

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Possibilities to education (higher and professional education, lifelong learning) ^{1,3,4}	W1.01 Public transportation ^{1,3,4}	O1.01 Short distance to Russia and St. Petersburg by rail transport from Päijät-Häme ⁵ (or O5.01?)	T1.01 Weakening of public finance and its consequences ³
	S1.02 Internet connections are good ¹	W1.02 Mobility possibilities between rural and urban areas ¹	O1.02 There are a lot of different instruments for public funding (EU-level, national, regional) ⁶	T1.02 The amount and complexity with some public services' bureaucracy prevent from starting entrepreneurship's career. ⁶
	S.1.03 Teleworking opportunities are good ¹	W1.03 Broadband networks lacking in some rural areas ³	O1.03 The policy, strategy and practices of the public procurement enables and invites also the SMEs to participate the bids. ⁶	
	S1.04 Good access to online public services (e-healthcare, e-education, e-daycare) ¹	W1.04 Low level of education in Päijät-Häme ⁵ (4 th lowest in Finland ⁵)	O1.04 There are RDI know-how (O5.03) but lack of RDI facilities. Is this a possibility to develop new public-private service function? ⁶	
	S1.05 The public entrepreneurship advisory services support and guide the beginning entrepreneurs ⁶	W1.05 The competition on public funding for the start-ups and SMEs is hard ⁶		
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Good selection of recreational activities ¹	W2.01 Not enough recreational activities for young people ^{1,7}	O2.01	T2.01
	S2.02 Extra curricular activities for children are accessible in the area. ¹	W2.02 Lack of public and private services in rural areas ⁷		
	S2.03 Lot of summer cottages and summer residents in area ³			
	S2.04 Four sporting centres in Päijät-Häme and their possibilities to wellness business ⁵			
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 Rural areas are considered as safe and comfortable places to live ^{1,7}	W3.01	O3.01 Growing trend of urban rurality ("citymaalaisuus")	T3.01
	S3.02 Housing opportunities are considered good ¹	W3.02	O3.02 Multi-locality in living and working ² . And functional countryside for permanent living, leisure as an environment for housing and business ³	T3.02
	S3.03 People are proud living on the area ¹		O3.03 The provision of residential and tourist areas by the water ⁵	
	S3.04 Dense urban network in the Häme region. ³			
	S3.05 The high standard of living increases the demand on tourism-, wellbeing and healthcare services. ⁶			
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 A lot of active village associations and other associations to address the social needs of the region and create opportunities. ¹	W4.01 Not enough young people living in rural areas ¹	O4.01 An opportunity to build networks and get peer support ⁶	T4.01 The healthcare and well-being service business has difficulties to find employees. ⁶
		W4.02 Not enough babies born in the area (low birth rate) ¹	O4.02 The aging people require and use the healthcare and well-being services. It provides the opportunity for business ⁶	

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
		W4.03 Not enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly). ^{1,3}		
		W4.04 Closed community, difficult to get to know people, difficult to become a part of the community ^{6,7}		
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 Häme region offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses. ¹	W5.01 More incentive schemes (e.g. taxation schemes) are needed to attract new businesses to area. ¹	O5.01 Reorganization of public services (opportunity to business) ³	T5.01 Decrease of milk and meat production ³
	S5.02 There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities ¹	W5.02 There are not enough possibilities for employment ^{1,7}	O5.02 Digitalization e.g. in marketing and selling ³	T5.02 Labour shortage in some businesses ³
	S5.03 Versatile business; strong sectors in food processing, renewable energy entrepreneurship/environmental business, tourism, wellness, horse economy, service business, contractors and	W5.03 Entrepreneurs have no willingness letting to grow their business ³	O5.03 High RDI-knowledge and its opportunities to companies ^{3,4}	T5.03 Aging of entrepreneurs ³
	S5.04 Good land for farming ^{3,4} (The agricultural sector of Kanta-Häme is characterised by extensive crop cultivation. The arable land used for cultivation in the province	W5.04 Low investing rates to RDI ⁴	O5.04 Utilising wellness and health services and know-how as export products ⁵	
	S5.05 Good location and access to Finland's biggest cities ^{3,4}	W5.05 There is a lack of entrepreneurship know-how and skills ^{6,7}	O5.05 Functional food product development ⁵	
	S5.06 The entrepreneurs know and use the public entrepreneurship services in order to develop their business ⁶	W5.06 The access on additional funding (support, not loan) - ref. S5.02 ⁶	O5.06 Training and research in water technology and know-how and export ⁵	
		W5.07 The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care) ⁶	O5.07 The joint ventures or networks of SMEs enable participation and provide resources to participate bid competitions – ref. W5.11 ⁶	
		W5.08 SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours. ⁶	O5.08 There are RDI know-how (O5.03) but lack of RDI facilities. Is this a business option? ⁶	
		W5.09 Lack of research- and product development facilities i.e. laboratories - ref. O5.03 ⁶		
		W5.10 The entrepreneurship is not a realistic, possible nor inspiring option (human aspect) ⁶		
		W5.11 The lack of relevant and useful networks of entrepreneurs ⁶		
		S5.07 The migrants' interest to become entrepreneurs was high. Migrants were particularly interested in marketing and selling. They felt that it was their strength. ⁷	W5.12 Migrants had doubt about their entrepreneurship competences ⁷ Ref. W5.05	O5.09 Migrants had business ideas. ⁷
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Women and men equally participate in decision making ¹	W6.01 It may be difficult for newcomers to adapt the community ¹	O6.01	T6.01
	S6.02 Women and men have equal possibilities to work and do business ¹	W6.02 It may be difficult for migrants to adapt the community ^{1,7}	O6.02	T6.02

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	S6.03 Rich and versatile rural culture ³	W6.03 Social exclusion of young people ³		
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Beautiful, clean nature and diverse landscapes ¹	W7.01	O7.01/O5? Growing demand of renewable energy sources ³	T7.01
	S7.02 Environment and nature are important to people ¹	W7.02	O7.02 The need to protect environment and nature creates opportunities for business in rural e.g. circular economy ⁶	T7.02
	S7.03 Clean water and ground water resources ^{3,4,5}			
	S7.04 Forest areas and ecosystem services ³			
	S7.05 Three National parks and one government owned hiking area locate in Häme region ³			
	S7.06 The region has attractions for tourism- and well-being business. ⁶			

Table 21. Central Greece / GREECE SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Sound infrastructure of national transport networks and proximity to airports and ports. Sufficient public transporting connection among remote areas and main big cities.	W1.01 Inadequate intra-regional public transportation network. Difficult accessibility to remote areas due to the topography and the old road network.	O1.01 Development of new online services (health, education, administration) based on new technologies	T1.01 Abandonment of rural youth in search of higher education opportunities.
	S1.02 Good medical system (primary care).	W1.02 Insufficient opportunities for higher, professional education and training and reeducation of existed population (agriculture sector). Low level of regional research institutions and Low level of ICT diffusion	O1.02 Improve education services (higher and professional education, lifelong learning, courses for immigrants and vulnerable groups)	T1.02 Lack of public resources for education, health, and social security insurance
		W1.03 Specialisation in low tech activities in agriculture	O1.03 Development of public transportation network among remote areas and improving accessibility of all remote areas to airports and ports	T1.03 Lack of background for the adequate use of new technologies (adoption gap)
		W1.04 Limited medical stuff and equipment		
		W1.05 Lack of telework opportunities and adequate remote services in the area		
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Important cultural treasures (famous archaeological sites), natural resources (thermal springs, Natura 2000 areas) and religious destinations.	W2.01 Lack of well-organized structures of leisure (e.g. thematic parks)	O2.01 Take advantage of cultural and natural resources for leisure	T2.01 Inadequate motives to attract young population
	S2.02 A lot of women deal with social activities in their areas (agro-tourism enterprises)	W2.02	O2.02	T2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 Housing opportunities are considered good	W3.01 Low annual income	O3.01	T3.01 High amount and complexity of public services' bureaucracy
	S3.02 Rural areas are considered safe and comfortable places to live	W3.02 Inadequate educational structures for immigrants and vulnerable groups	O3.02	T3.02
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 There are women in the territory, although there is masculinization of the area	W4.01 Low percentage of births and young people	O4.01	T4.01 Depopulation
	S4.02	W4.02 Not enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly).	O4.02	T4.02 Demographic/Aging
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 The area offers possibilities for economic activities related to sustainable tourism (cultural, natural heritage, gastronomy, etc.), logistics as well as related to agricultural production, agribusiness and manufacturing (strong secondary sector).	W5.01 High percentage of unemployment	O5.01 Modernisation of the agro-food sector and linkages with other sectors along the value chain	T5.01 Lack of start-ups and innovation culture within firms
	S5.02 The area is suitable for the development of sustainable agriculture, livestock and forestry production	W5.02 There are not enough sources of financing for the creation of innovative companies	O5.02 Improved support to upgrading SMEs technological capacity	T5.02 Shortage of higher education/ skilled employees in some businesses

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	S5.03 RES capacity (solar, wind, hydro)	W5.03 Tax system	O5.03 Promotion of environmental and energy saving technologies (RES) linking to agriculture production.	T5.03 Further decline of agricultural sector and abandonment of specific crops due to reduction of subsidies
	S5.04 Great concentration in fisheries and aquaculture	W5.04 Lack of new businesses in the area	O5.04 Increased focus on agritourism promotion	T5.0
			O5.05 Explore synergies with other regions in terms of innovation infrastructure and technology transfer	
			O5.06 Investments in tourism, energy logistics, export-oriented manufacturing, food and beverage and expansion to	
			O5.07 Raise awareness among local entrepreneurs, concerning issues related to innovation and technology management	
			O5.08 Development of sustainable cultivation plans for new crops	
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Women and men have equal possibilities to work and do business	W6.01 Women and young people don't participate enough in decision making	O6.01	T6.01
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Important natural and cultural resources (Delfi, Thermopyles)	W7.01 Lack of informative actions regarding sustainable agriculture from central authorities	O7.01 Initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agritourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas	T7.01
	S7.02 The area has high value landscapes and biodiversity, well considered by the population	W7.02 Lack of informative actions regarding greening measures of CAP	O7.02 Digital technologies can enhance environmental agriculture practices and activities (Smart farmings)	T7.02
			O7.03 Develop activities towards Circular economy	

Table 22. Monaghan / IRELAND SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Good Local Primary & Secondary Schools.	W1.01 Public transport & mobility. Weak public transport infrastructure.	O1.01 More active promotion of the rural area & availability of suitable off-farm work opportunities and schemes	
	S1.02	W1.02 Local medical/primary care facilities. Weak public services, online services & teleworking facilities in rural areas.	O1.02 CAP reform - LEADER & European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Farmer Groups. New CAP policies may provide incentives for access to land.	
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Safe & secure local environment	W2.01 Internet/telecom connectivity. Limited broadband access, & ICT skill levels. Patchy coverage.	O2.01 Sustainable tourism.	
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 Local community pride & living conditions. Rural Innovation being supported through LEADER	W3.01 Not enough employment opportunities. New Communities often struggle to find suitable employment.	O3.01 Potential for smaller farms to add 'public good' value - Trails, walks, guide tours, local history	T3.01 BREXIT could lead to higher criminality in our border region.
		W3.02 Housing opportunities are limited & expensive.		T3.02 Concern about CAP post 2020 funding cuts due to BREXIT & focus on climate actions.
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 Many proactive women & young people in the population.	W4.01 Rural demographics. Profile of farmers is aging. Loneliness & Isolation.		T4.01 Many young people are choosing not to farm the land.
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 Lively communities & citizen-driven local activities. Well established rural & farming lobby supports, Teagasc, marts, CoOps, IFA etc & Entrepreneurship	W5.01 Credit & finance is expensive & limited. Small farm sizes. Land prices are a barrier to entry for new entrants	O5.01 Sustainable agriculture & forestry (which is under developed). Social Farming & better cultivation Practices. Further scope to shorten local food supply chains.	T5.01 Lack of farming experience/expertise. No support schemes & information for newcomers.
		W5.02 Inadequate support & taxation schemes to attract new business.		T5.02 Competition from less regulated countries always a threat
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Strong community & voluntary sector. Strong farming & rural community ethos, with farmers being custodians of the land, waterways and biodiversity	W6.01 Connections between urban & rural areas.	O6.01 Integration of new populations in the area. Many new community members have farming skills / interests.	T6.01 Financial insecurity of farming
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Open landscapes & beautiful diverse natural areas. Pristine rural area & environment / sustainability		O7.01 Climate Change Opportunities. Alternative energy sources.	T7.01 Many cultivation practices are not environmentally sound.
	S7.02 Excellent quality & green farming produce. Farms as 'public goods'. Strong Irish food certification system.			T7.02 Not yet attracting adequate eco-firms & sustainable businesses.

Table 23. Galilee / ISRAEL SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public transportation and other services	S1.01	W1.01 Buses are not frequent enough	O1.01 Although it heavily depends on number of travellers, there is an opportunity for special public transportation service.	T1.01 Students who are residents for a short time are bringing more cars to the region.
	S1.02	W1.02 There is no train connection to the region.	O1.02 There are programmes to connect Kiryat-Shmona to the train services, but it is still in planning status.	T1.02 If transportation will be too easy people may decide to live in the Centre and only come to Galilee for work.
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 The only place you can ski in Israel is the Galilee region.	W2.01 Very few recreation activities, no cinemas and theatres, very few performances.	O2.01 Possibilities to organise more activities regarding the bird watching Agmon Lake.	T2.01 Visitors from outside the region care less on the environment and are contaminating the streams and some camping areas.
	S2.02 Interesting activities of the Tel-Hai College in the programme "Town Square Academy" involve and activate many people in the region.		O2.02 Since the National Council for Higher Education see the potential, there are chances to get more budgets for additional activities.	T2.02
		W2.02 Since it is a small region almost no national performance are done in the region, except at Tel-Hai Museum.		
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 Because the area is of high environmental quality people are interested to settle in the Galilee if they can find employment.	W3.01 Since it is a remote region the living conditions are not high, services are not good enough and people have not enough working potential.	O3.01 With better development of the digitalization situation and work from a distance more people will settle in the region.	T3.01 If too many people will decide to build buildings in the region, it may ruin the special "green" character of the region.
	S3.02 As a result of the high cost of houses in the Centre of Israel and the possibilities to build a house in the Galilee, there are more young people who come to resident in the region	W3.02 The construction system in the Galilee does not coop well with the demand and therefore in same cases the quality of buildings is low.	O3.02	T3.02
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01	W4.01 Many of the young people are migrating to the Centre, since employment is there.	O4.01 If we will be able to further develop the digitalization infrastructure of the region we will be able to bring many youngsters back to the Galilee.	T4.01
	S4.02	W4.02 Since very few High-Tech companies exists in the region the brightest youngsters are leaving the region.	O4.02	T4.02
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 The activities at MIGAL, Tel-Hai College and Kinneret College is driving forwards innovative activities	W5.01 Employment is very difficult to get in the region, and most of the industries are the traditional ones.	O5.01 The Israeli government is trying now to accelerate more sophisticated high-tech industries, mainly in the Food-Tech sector.	T5.01 people are and will leave the region if they will not be able to find interesting jobs
	S5.02 A few industries, such as Shamir Optics, Netafim, BMC and Malinox, are very innovative and are marketing products all over the world.	W5.02 Once a person find a working place he will not easily change it even if he do not like his working place.	O5.02 There are several accelerators that are now developing in the region, and it may develop additional spin-offs.	T5.02 Competition between High-tech industries that already exist in the region can create shortage of workers.
		W5.03 Jobs in the high-tech sector is very scare and difficult to get, especially for youngsters.		
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Kibbutzim in the region have cultural activities and celebration of holiday, but this is locally.	W6.01 Few cultural activities except those concerning Tourism.	O6.01 There are opportunities connected to the special historical heritage of the region that could be developed.	T6.01

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 High level, compared to all other Israeli regions, from environmental aspects and biodiversity. The region spread from -200m below Sea Level to +1200m above Sea Level.	W7.01	O7.01 The recent development in the Agamon Lake will attract many bird watchers from all over the world because of its uniqueness.	T7.01 If many people decide to settle in the Galilee it will affect the environment.
	S7.02	W7.02 Some parts of the region as becoming pollutant	O7.02	T7.02 Agriculture development, using more pesticides and herbicides could ruin the environmental special conditions and the water quality in the Kinnert Lake.

Table 24. Apulia / ITALY SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Increase in the number of socio-educational structures capable of providing parenting support and child protection services	W1.01 Poor infrastructure connections	O1.01 There are higher and vocational education and learning opportunities in the area	T1.01 Submerged and inadequately assisted disability
	S1.02 Fair presence of socio-health and social-welfare services and high professionalism of the operators	W1.03 Insufficient diffusion of telematic technologies for families and businesses which hinders the streamlining of procedures and the progressive replacement of counter services	O1.02 Funds and services for early childhood	T1.02 Reduction in the offer of services for citizens following rationalization of spending policies, which can lead to further depopulation phenomena, especially for young age groups with more sensitive requests for services (school, health, etc.)
2. Recreation/social activities	S2.01 Existence of numerous associations and cooperatives that work with social agriculture, immigrants and the elderly	W2.01 Low presence of recreational and socialization infrastructures for disadvantaged and/or disabled people	O2.01 Growing support for the creation of service centres for the aggregation and animation of local populations	T2.01 Reduction of public resources dedicated to social services
	S2.02 Significant diffusion of associations operating in the social field	W2.02 Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, the disabled and immigrants	O2.02 Increased attention to personal services and issues of social inclusion	T2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 Good presence of social enterprises	W3.01 There are integration problems with some local populations (minorities, new arrivals, ...)	O3.01 Presence of foreigners as an opportunity for the maintenance of basic services and as an opportunity to recover residential assets	T3.01 Abandonment of small historical centres and a decrease in participation in the social and recreational life of the countries, which affects the quality of life of the inhabitants
	S3.02 Involvement of the foreign population as a resource in the management of production chains and personal services	W3.02 The vulnerability of the new poor and widespread uneasy situations, especially among young people and among foreign residents	O3.02	T3.02 Presence of organized and non-organized crime
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 Important presence of associations and volunteering in social services and social cooperatives	W4.01 A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	O4.01 Promoting technological, production and process innovations can favour the replacement of generation and the revaluation of ancient crafts	T4.01 Abandonment by the younger generations of the territories of origin, in particular of the internal areas
	S4.02 Increase in the foreign population residing in the territories	W4.02 Migration of young people to regions and/or nations with greater job opportunities	O4.02 Increase in the number of immigrants in the area employed in manual work	T4.02 Few opportunities to develop family plans
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 Tourism is evolving towards an experiential model with low environmental impact	W5.01 A low offer of incentives and support services for the creation of entrepreneurial initiatives and employment opportunities	O5.01 Increase in EU financial resources to support research, innovation in agriculture, competitiveness and environmental sustainability	T5.01 Difficulties in accessing credit discourage investments for production activities or the introduction of technological or process innovations
	S5.02 In the summer months, the increase in tourism activity generates jobs	W5.02 The production activities have a low propensity for innovation and to adapt to the new orientations of the global	O5.02 Recovery of traditional productive activities in a green economy key	T5.02 Tax systems that are not always favourable for businesses
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Significant mobilization of the female population in rural society	W6.01 High youth and female unemployment rate	O6.01 Propensity for active participation both in the inclusive and social sphere, as well as recognized associations, also by spontaneous groups / committees of citizens	T6.01 Anthropoc abandonment of rural areas
	S6.02 Experiences and successful projects that have promoted social inclusion and active citizenship practices	W6.02 Female occupation much lower than male	O6.02 Funding to incentivize the employment of women	T6.02
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Presence of two national parks, three marine protected areas, 16 state reserves and 18 regional protected areas	W7.01 Environmental degradation phenomena in rural areas	O7.01 Growing attention to the quality of the environment and the landscape, especially in the younger generations	T7.01 The increase in widespread urbanization and the construction of illegal construction cause a simplification of agro-ecosystems and a loss of the traditional agricultural and coastal landscape
	S7.02 Diversified ecosystem and climatic structure spread throughout the territory	W7.02 Building illegal phenomena, damage to historical and archaeological sites, environmental damage	O7.02 Markets are moving towards green economy models	T7.02 Risk of hydrogeological instability and desertification on significant portions of land

Table 25. Vidzeme / LATVIA SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Good primary & secondary schools	W1.01 Insufficient provision of mobility & accessibility services, including transport and road infrastructures	O1.01 Great willingness and necessity of inhabitants, esp. of rural areas & young generation, to use public transport	T1.01 Transport constraints via public transport availability and charges
			O1.2 Various instruments for public funding (EU funds, governmental, regional)	T1.2 Insufficient financing, flawed and inaccurate infrastructure planning
		W1.02 Insufficient intra-regional public transportation, i.e., between rural and urban areas.	O1.3 New technologies available/using to enhance quality of public transport infrastructure	T1.3 Decrease of population in rural areas
	S1.02 Good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G/fiber)	W1.03 Weak teleworking opportunities via shortcomings with ITC equipment; lack of appropriate digital skills, as well as lack of internet connectivity in some remote rural areas	O1.4 Various EU funds, governmental programs and support, as well as regional initiatives	T1.4 Weak financing and its consequences, as well as inadequate education & training, int al., lifelong learning (i.e., elearning) regarding ICT and digital skills
	S1.03 There are adequate public provision of online e-health, e- day-care and/or elearning services (survey results)	W1.04 Insufficient day-care facilities in rural areas		
	S1.04 Inhabitants feel safe and secure			
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Accessible to <i>extra-curricular</i> activities (e.g., music, dance, arts) for children	W2.01 Not enough and well provided spaces to allow young and adult people to meet	O2.01 Using of buildings & spaces owned by the municipalities for various purposes	T2.01 Depopulation and demographic imbalance in rural areas
	S2.02 Plenty of good and different recreational activities	W2.02 Low accessibility & quality of services in remote territories of the region, particularly in rural areas	O2.02 Implementation of mid- long-period funding, particularly for cultural events & activities	T2.02 Insufficient regular and continuous financing & funding of local cultural events & activities; Events & activities mainly are implemented on the year based project tenders (short-term financing)
	S2.03 Elderly people are offered activities and a space where to meet			
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility) are high	W3.01 Lack of housing opportunities (i.e., limited & expensive), esp., for new entrants and young generation; High price or properties	O3.01 Inclusion of housing-related solutions in regional strategic and planning documents	T3.01 Urban/towns residents purchase houses (with higher prices) in rural areas only for recreation
			O3.02 Various funding and support measures will allocated to solve the issue of housing availability & quality	
	S3.02 No important social or political conflicts in the area	W3.02 Problems of integration with some population (i.e., minorities, new entrants)	O3.03 Strengthening of local communities, social activities, i.e., social entrepreneurship', networking	T3.02 Insufficient integration of minorities and new entrants via undeveloped communities due to demographic imbalance, i.e., ageing of rural population
		W3.03 Low income level per household		
		W3.04 High risk of poverty		
	S3.03 Rural areas are considered as safe and comfortable places to live			
	S3.04 People are proud living on the area			
4. Demographic & human capital		W4.01 Not enough babies born or low birth rate	O4.01 More support, including intangible, for families with children	T4.01 Depopulation of rural areas and demographic imbalance

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	S4.01 Possibility to find opportunities to develop family plans	W4.02 Not enough young people in rural areas	O4.02 Re-emigration of citizens who left Latvia during the previous financial crisis	T4.02 Increase the number of elderly people in rural areas
		W4.03 Not enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly).	O4.02 New entrants in rural areas	T4.03 Less youth in rural areas
		W4.4 Community and voluntary sectors are weak developed, not address the social needs of region and not create opportunities		T4.04 Insufficient systematic financial security of local activities and services
	S4.02 There are enough women in the area (Table 2)	W4.05 Some imbalance of gender in Vidzeme households		
		W4.06 Weak level of education		
5. Business, economy & innovation		W5.01 Lack of an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area	O5.01 More incentive framework (e.g., tax system) are needed to attract new businesses	T5.01 Qualified & well-skilled labour shortage
		W5.02 Development of region's territories is very diverse among municipalities		
		W5.03 Lowest share of value added of all regions		
		W5.04 Weak implementation of digital technologies in business		
		W5.05 Lack of entrepreneurship know-how and skills	O5.02 Digital transition - opportunities for new economic activities and productivity growth	T5.02 Delayed education reform and inadequate education programs
		W5.06 Insufficient participation in adult education		
		W5.07 Lack of support (i.e., services and finances) for new entrants to the rural areas	O5.03 ICT infrastructures and the deployment of broadband coverage in rural areas	
		W5.08 Insufficient services for entrepreneurial support and new business development	O5.04 Strengthening of youth (i.e., new entrants) entrepreneurship; Innovative and creative vouchers as a financial tool to support local companies	T5.03 Insufficient or no access to additional financing (i.e. support, credit on very favourable terms)
		W5.09 The lack of relevant and useful networks of entrepreneurs	O5.05 Digitalization & cooperation (e.g., in marketing and selling)	
	S5.01 Preference is given eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy)	W5.10 Insufficient support for innovation or technology transfer & no support for eco-innovation.	O5.06 Financial support, ICT infrastructures and the deployment of broadband coverage in rural areas	
		W5.11 Lack of support (i.e., services and finances) for new entrants to the rural areas		
	S5.02 Possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry	W5.12 In conventional intensive and more productive farms (mainly large & with higher economic size) cultivation practices are not sustainable and environmentally sound	O5.07 Sustainable agriculture & forestry, using environmental friendly and climate change mitigating production methods and measures; Precision agriculture; Training of new and innovative techniques in the agriculture & forestry sector.	T5.04 Changes of the CAP policy and RDP support measures; Lack of programs (i.e., funds) and availability of training, particularly ICT and digital skills
		W5.13 Aging of entrepreneurs, particularly of farmers		
W5.06 Great potential and possibilities for sustainable tourism in rural areas	W5.14 Lack of job opportunities	O5.08 Sustainable tourism, esp., rural, culinary, agro-tourism, heritage, etc., recreation services, and social farming	T5.05 Complexity of RDP significantly reduces use of EAFRD funds for implementation of jobs creating projects	

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	S5.04 Following sectors of economic activity are indicated as priorities in Vidzeme strategy 2030:	W5.15 Sectors, which is indicated as strong have comparatively low share of value added		
		W5.16 Comparatively low salaries & wages in higher value added or priority sectors of economic activity	O5.09 Sustainable (resource effective) production of value added products, int al., for export	T5.06 An insufficient number of well-educated and qualified staff (i.e., ITC and advanced digital skills)
		W5.17 Insufficient provision of public services and weak innovation (i.e., ICT) implementation in sector	O5.10 Providing various types of health, rehabilitation & care services, the know-how of which is offered as export product	
			O5.11 Reorganization of public services (opportunity to business, i.e. social entrepreneurship)	
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life, as well as in various social activities	W6.01 Loneliness and isolation affect many people, esp., in the rural areas	O6.01 Strengthening of local communities, public (i.e., cultural) & social activities, i.e., social entrepreneurship, networking	T6.01 Depopulation & demographic imbalance in rural areas
		W6.02 Insufficient opportunities for young people & new entrants to participate in decision making	O6.02 Increased number of community activities, i.e., these activities that support local identity	T6.02 A small number of new entrants, esp. young people, choose to live and work in the countryside
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 Open landscapes & beautiful diverse natural areas	W7.01 Cultivation practices are not environmentally sound	O7.02 CAP Post 2020 measures, including agri-environmental & climate and related measures (i.e., Natura 2000, Water framework, etc.)	T7.01 Due to lack of supportive measures/funding agricultural practices stay not environmentally sound - unsustainable land management, landscape degradation & water scarcity and biodiversity decline
				T7.02 Lack of CAP support to implement mitigation and adaptive measures to the climate change
	S7.02 High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised (PoliRural survey results)	W7.02 Low generated value added from recreation activities	O7.02 Using of various funds und supporting programs to create value added products and services	T7.03 Lack of funding and support, ITC shortages, as well as inadequate knowledge and skills, int al., digital
		W7.03 Biological resources are mainly used for the production of low value added goods		

Table 26. Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 People feel safe and secure in the area they live in (57%)	W1.01 Lack of adequate day care facilities in the area (61%)	O1.01 Good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G /fiber) is available throughout the country (73%)	T1.01 Almost no investments for construction of retirement homes and centres for early child development (LR)
	S1.02 There are sufficient possibilities enabling mobility to the main city in the region (53%)	W1.02 Limited access to good medical (primary care) services (55%)	O1.02 Existing policy measures aimed at making the health care system more accessible to the rural population (LR)	T1.02 The corona crisis may limit the available medical capacities even further
		W1.03 There are no opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning (50%)	O1.03 Existing government efforts to promote higher education of the rural youth , by introducing dispersed high education studies (LR)	
	S1.03 Good intra-regional public transportation is available (48%)	W1.04 There is not sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference /specialized health care premises, schools, universities) – (46%)	O1.04 Policy measures for financial support for rural infrastructure (LR)	
	S1.04 Satisfactory accessibility to good primary and secondary schools (42%)	W1.05 There is no adequate public provision of online e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning Services (44%)	O1.05 High policy awareness for the importance of education and support of education (subsidizing) enabling development activity (LR)	
		W1.06 The connections between rural and urban areas (e.g. airports, train connection) are not sufficient (43%)	O1.06 Increased availability of free e-learning alternatives (LR)	
		W1.07 There is not enough support for teleworking opportunities in the area (43%)	O1.07 Increased investments in refurbishment and modernization of primary and secondary schools (LR)	
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 There are quality commercial services such as restaurants, shops, car maintenance, etc. (54%)	W2.01 There are not enough and adequate spaces to allow young people to meet (73%)		
	S2.02 There are adequate housing opportunities (48%)	W2.02 Extracurricular activities (e.g.: music, dance, arts) for children are not accessible (68%)		
		W2.03 There are not enough recreational activities for young people (67%)		
		W2.04 People disagree that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities (60%)		
		W2.05 Elderly people are not offered activities and a space where to meet (53%)		
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 There is basic infrastructure for normal housing (electricity, water supply and sewage system) (60%)	W3.01 People are not highly aware of the usage of renewable energy for business purposes and in everyday life (55%)	O3.01 Available power supply in rural areas (a well-developed transmission and distribution network) (LR)	T3.01 General population including rural are scared of the side effects from upcoming digital infrastructure (5G)
	S3.02 People are proud of living in the area they live in (56%)	W3.02 Living conditions in villages and rural areas (except in tourist areas) are seen as less attractive than in urban areas (LR)	O3.02 The climate conditions are favourable for usage of renewable sources of energy in the direction of providing energy for the agricultural sector (LR)	T3.02 Air pollution in the country is an issue, particularly in winter (LR)
	S3.03 There are high living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility) (46%)	W3.03 There are differences in social economic statuses between people in rural areas and the political divide is obvious and very intensive		
	S3.04 There are no problems of integration with some population in the territory (minorities, new comers....) (42%)	W3.04 Weak activity or non–existence of regional or local institutions competent for rural development (LR)		
4. Demographic & human capital		W4.01 There are not enough young people in the area (69%)		T4.01 Severe ‘aging population syndrome’ present

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
		W4.02 Our community and voluntary sectors are not well developed and do not address the social needs of our region and create opportunities (66%)	O4.01 Existing initiatives (e.g. Rural Development Network) aimed to mobilise rural communities as agents of local development and as participants in rural policy (LR)	T4.02 Young people today are more mobile and less emotionally related to the land and country-side (LR)
		W4.03 There are not enough babies born in the area (65%)		
		W4.04 There are not enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly) (56%)		
		W4.05 The demographic structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses in the rural area, including agribusiness (49%)	O4.02 Existing policy measures to attract young people to work and live in rural areas (LR)	T4.03 The interest among young people for programs for financial support of young farmers is very small (LR)
		W4.06 The education structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses in the rural area, including agribusiness (44%) - High long-term unemployment found in rural areas is related to the poor qualification structure of the unemployed (LR)		T4.04 Insufficient or total lack of education of people in rural areas - Low rates of enrolled and graduated students (LR)
		W4.07 It is not possible to find opportunities to develop family plans (43%)		
	S4.01 The difference between men and women is minimal and has no influence on the demographic imbalance (LR)	W4.08 There are not enough women in the area (42%)		
	5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 The area favours eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy) (71%)	W5.01 The area is not good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals (48%) - Lack of mature business ideas and entrepreneurial skills and knowledge; saturation of sectors that shops, restaurants, communal services) (LR) require low start-up capital (small retail)	O5.01 The country has a good climate potential for the development of agriculture; The large number of sunny days offers excellent conditions for the development of gardening, fruit growing and vine growing (LR).
S5.02 The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry (54%)		W5.02 Weak access to consultancy and extension services	O5.02 The Ministry of Economy via the Agency for promotion of SME supported the creation of a network of advisors and promoted voucher system of use of consultancy services (LR)	T5.02 Investments in agriculture are less attractive for banks due to lower profitability of investments, collateral problems, and so on. (LR)
		W5.03 There is not an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area (45%)		
S5.03 The area offers possibilities for sustainable tourism (cultural heritage, nature, sports, local food) (48%)		W5.04 Insufficient development of tourism attractions and facilities; Difficult access to tourism amenities, national parks and tourist sites; Lack of trained human resources; Lack of strategic planning and marketing of rural tourism resources and products (LR)		T5.03 Persistently underdeveloped tourism in rural municipalities as a result of the lack of work experience and tourism related activities of rural population (LR)
		W5.05 There are not enough possibilities for employment (40%) - Employment opportunities in rural areas are limited and dominated by agriculture as an economic sector (LR)		T5.04 Low competitiveness of economic activities in rural areas (for example, agriculture, forestry, fishery, food sector, rural tourism, service industry) (LR)
S5.04 There are good conditions for development of the agro-processing industry (42%) - Almost all of the food processing industry (except for meat processing and slaughterhouses) is located in rural areas (LR).		W5.06 In all regions the development of industry is constrained by the quality of road infrastructure and business related infrastructure and increasingly by the shortages of qualified labour (LR)	O5.03 There is great potential for export for agro-processing industry (LR)	
S5.05 Available credit lines especially targeted to agribusiness, i.e. individual farmers, rural households , agricultural, agro-processing and agro-export SMEs (LR)		W5.07 Credit lines for agribusiness not favorable, they require a guaranty and the administrative procedures are complex. Mortgages in rural areas are very poorly valued by the banks	O5.04 The EU pre-enlargement support can partly overcome some financial constraints in rural areas for profitable businesses (LR)	T5.05 Substantial changes in rural capital markets are less likely during economic recession and financial constraints (related to corona crisis) (LR)
S5.06 The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses (42%)		W5.08 Inadequate coordination of program and activities directed towards different economic sectors in rural areas (LR)		

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
		W5.09 There is no institutional support for eco-companies, companies with sustainable business (organic production) (47%) - Support for organic production is very limited given the potentials and possibilities provided by EU policy; Lack of seasonal labour; Lack of own capital and access to financial resources; Weak level of agro-food integration; Low level of integration of research in the development of agriculture (LR)	O5.05 Macedonian agriculture is traditional extensive agriculture , which is main precondition for development of organic production (LR); Organic agricultural production in Republic of Macedonia is one of the fastest growing agribusiness sectors (LR)	T5.06 Regarding organic production, there is a lack of organization, cooperation , it is necessary to create a policy or strategy (LR)
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life (45%) - Rural women have very low levels of decision-making in the family and leadership of family businesses, especially in the rural areas with predominantly Muslim population (LR)	W6.01 There is a lack of lively communities and citizen-driven local activities (59%)		
	S6.02 There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area (40%)	W6.02 There are no good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making (53%)		
		W6.03 Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area (48%)		
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery (87%)	W7.01 There are no efficient waste management practices by individuals and the business sector (64%) - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites (LR); Very low percentage of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste (LR)	O7.01 Large areas of agricultural land not polluted and not intensively cultivated (LR)	T7.01 General practice is collection of non-separated communal and non-hazardous industrial waste as well as non-hazardous and hazardous non-separated waste fractions (LR)
	S7.02 Nature in the area is diverse (86%) - The diversity of natural resources is still on a relatively good level (LR)	W7.02 Cultivation practices in the area are not done in environmentally sound way (42%)	O7.02 Available human resources in the private and civil sector, which have some experience and knowledge in sustainable environment management (LR)	
	S7.03 High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area (40% agree/ 39% disagree) - Currently, there are several rural settlements protected as monuments of culture and natural rarities (LR)	W7.03 Required development of the road infrastructure as most of the cultural heritage is located in outmost rural areas (LR)	O7.03 Increasing interest in cultural tourism on the market (LR)	
	S7.04 The cultural heritage is located in the rural areas and has the biggest development potential considering the diversity and quality of cultural and historical treasures and archaeological sites in the country (LR)	W7.04 Lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection (LR)		

Table 27. Mazowieckie / POLAND SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 Sufficient public transportation connection with the main region's/subregion's centre	W1.01 Lower than the Polish average access to water management system among rural inhabitants	O1.01 High accessibility to high speed Internet connection	T1.01 Lack of public funds for further improvement of the accessibility & quality of public services
	S1.02 Sufficient access to public services	W1.02 Low intraregional transportation connectedness	O1.02 Development of public e-services	T1.02 Underdevelopment of electricity infrastructure – risk of electricity blackouts
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Access to commercial enterprises such as shops and restaurants	W2.01 Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities for young people	O2.01 Civic activity as a way for expending cultural and recreational offer	T2.01 Lack of public funds to support social and recreational activities
	S2.02 Access to the quality culture and entertainment activities	W2.02 Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities for elderly people	O2.02 Modern ICT technologies as a tool for expending the cooperation with cultural organisations from other regions/countries	T2.02 Competition from agglomeration and weak participation in rural based cultural/social activities
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 In general, good living conditions	W3.01 Presence of important social or political conflicts	O3.01 Positive attitudes towards being a citizen of the region	T3.01 Increasing income inequality
	S3.02	W3.02 Some problems with integration of new entrants	O3.02 Increased accessibility to social infrastructure	T3.02 Increasing scale of social exclusion
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 Generally, better demographic statistics than for the whole Poland – more younger people	W4.01 Insufficient number of professionally active citizens	O4.01 Increasing human capital	T4.01 Increasing unemployment as a factor for diminishing human capital
	S4.02 Significant number of women in the neighbourhood	W4.02 Activity of the citizens insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth	O4.02 Increasing social capital	T4.02 Insufficient development possibilities for all groups of citizens
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 Significant number of citizens aware of funds for rural innovations	W5.01 Perception of relatively weak business development environment	O5.01 Consumption patterns and diet awareness – increase of demand for SFSC	T5.01 No specific initiatives to allure potential entrepreneurs
	S5.02 High level of self-employed and entrepreneurs	W5.02 Lack of complex services supporting entrepreneurs	O5.02	T5.02 Limited innovations potential
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 Social exclusion as an increasing problem	W6.01 Lack of gender equality in taking decisions and professional life	O6.01 New forms of dissemination the information about and access to cultural/social activities (ICT)	T6.01 Insufficient activity of NGOs in the region
	S6.02 Insufficient number of young people among professional decision takers	W6.02 Low inclusion of young people into civic society		T6.02 Insufficient empowerment of women on the job market
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 High awareness of environmental issues	W7.01 No specific environmental or biodiversity features	O7.01 Rural-Urban business connections increase	T7.01 Lack o public funds for environment-friendly public investment
	S7.02 Variety of cultural, environmental heritage facilities and places	W7.02 Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations	O7.02 Good law protecting the environment (one of three dim. of development in strategies)	T7.02 Pressure from urbanization to environment!

Table 28. Segóbriga / SPAIN SWOT

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
1. Availability of public and other services	S1.01 There is an adequate primary and secondary education service in the territory	W1.01 The primary health care service is limited and there are difficulties in transporting to the nearest hospitals.	O1.01 Development of new online health services based on new technologies	T1.01 Lack of capacities for the adequate use of new technologies (adoption gap)
	S1.02 There are no relevant security problems in the area	W1.02 Deficiente servicio de transporte tanto dentro del territorio como hacia las zonas urbanas	O1.02 New forms for mobility based on new technologies: Shared mobility services and public services on demand	T1.02 Continued population decline and aging can lead to a reallocation of public services or even their elimination.
		W1.03. Poor transportation service both within the territory and to urban areas		T1.03 Abandonment of the rural environment of families with babies due to lack of resources that allow family and work reconciliation
		W1.04 Insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education	O1.03 Development of new online training services based on new technologies	T1.04 Abandonment of rural youth in search of higher education opportunities.
		W1.05 Poor Internet access in the territory		
		W1.06 Lack of telework opportunities in the area	O1.04 Recent advances in the development of teleworking may favor the location of new professionals in rural areas	
2. Recreation / social activities	S2.01 Older people have spaces to meet	W2.01 There are not enough leisure activities in the area, particularly for young people	O2.01 New forms of leisure and entertainment for young people based on new technologies	T2.01 Loss of young population
	S2.02 The inhabitants of the area value and are concerned about leisure activities.	W2.02 Youth gathering spaces are insufficient and little diversified, as well as the offer of extracurricula for children is limited		
		W2.03 Commercial services in the area are insufficient and poorly diversified.		
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	S3.01 There are adequate housing possibilities in the area	W3.01 Sometimes integration problems of some minorities are identified	O3.01 Use of second residences to expand the offer of rural tourism in the area	T3.01 High number of second residences
	S3.02 The population is satisfied in terms of their quality of life	W3.02	O3.02	T3.02 Lack of public participation in community decision-making
	S3.03 There is a high feeling of roots and belonging of the population of the area			
4. Demographic & human capital	S4.01 There are women in the territory, although there is masculinization of the area	W4.01 Limited opportunities for family development in the area	O4.01 Institutional strategies and public aid aimed at the demographic challenge	T4.01.
	S4.02.	W4.02 Low child and youth population aggravated by a decrease in the birth rate in the territory	O4.02 Retired older people in rural municipalities feel active and want social participation	T4.02
			O4.03 Possible arrival of new settlers in rural areas looking for a healthier and safer place in the face of health problems linked to large urban agglomerations	
5. Business, economy & innovation	S5.01 The area is suitable for the installation of innovative companies and new professionals	W5.01 The conditions for the development of new businesses are very limited, particularly for star-up and innovative companies.	O5.01 Social networks can serve as a tool for promoting and advertising the territory to promote tourism	T5.01 The economic recession caused by the coronavirus may undermine business development in rural areas
	S5.02 The area offers possibilities for economic activities related to sustainable tourism (cultural, natural heritage, gastronomy, etc.), as well as related to agribusiness and manufacturing.	W5.02 General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	O5.02 Institutional support in promoting tourism in the territory as well as in the agri-food industry	T5.02 Possible shortening of the summer and tourist vacation period in 2020, as a consequence of the stoppage of activity by the coronavirus.
	S5.02 The area is suitable for the development of sustainable agriculture, livestock and forestry	W5.02 There are not enough sources of financing for the creation of innovative companies or a special tax regime for settling in rural areas	O5.03 Proximity to Madrid and around a connection axis of large regions in Spain	T5.03 Lack of ecosystems to support business development and entrepreneurship
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	S6.01 The participation of women in decision-making and social life in the area is important, although it can be improved	W6.01 There is no strong dynamic of social participation in the area, especially among young people	O6.01 Current currents of thought can lead to greater empowerment of women and therefore to greater weight in decision-making bodies and the professional sphere. In turn, they can promote greater ecological awareness promoted by young people	T6.01

PILLAR	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
	S6.02	W6.02 Solitude and isolation are a major problem in the area	O6.02	T6.02
		W6.03 The high percentage of the aging population does not facilitate the introduction of social and cultural changes		
		W6.04. Poor appreciation and social awareness of the importance of preserving the heritage elements		
7. Environment & Biodiversity	S7.01 The area has high value landscapes and biodiversity, well considered by the population	W7.01 The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued	O7.01 The population in general, and the rural population in particular, is aware of the value of ecosystems and the natural environment not only as a means of leisure but as a source of income.	T7.01 Environmental degradation by industrial facilities

Annex 7. Pilot's List of Needs

Table 29. Flanders / BELGIUM Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Improve (public) transport	All groups		W1.01, T1.01, T1.02
2. Recreation / social activities	N02 Further develop rural tourism	All groups		O2.01, O2.02, T2.01, T2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N03 Need for specialized housing and other services for elderly and poor people	Elderly people, poor people		W3.01, W3.02
	N04 Actions to avoid conflicts between newcomers in rural areas and inhabitants of rural areas.	Newcomers		S3.01, O3.01, O3.02, S3.02, T3.02, T3.01
4. Demographic & human capital				
5. Business, economy & innovation	N05 Encourage young people to become farmer	Young people		T5.02
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N06 Enhance and ensure the heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g. small landscape elements)	All groups		O6.01, O6.02
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N07 Find a balance between nature and agriculture in highly fragmentated rural landscape	All groups		W7.01, T7.01, O7.01, O7.02
	N08 Agricultural sector needs to deal with the challenges and opportunities related with climate change e.g. drought	Agricultural sector		W7.02, T7.02

Table 30. Central Bohemian / CZR Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP (Eg: established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other)	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
N1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region	Established populations new entrants, young people, companies	X X X X X X (6)	S1.01, O1.01, S1.02, W1.02, W1.03, S1.04, O1.04, O1.05
	N02 Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole region	N02 Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole region	N02 Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole	S1.10, W1.10, O1.10, Z1.10, W1.11, O1.11, O1.12, O5.06, O5.07
	N03 Need to reconstruct/build the transport infrastructure	Established populations, new entrants, companies	X X X X (4)	S1.01, O1.01, S1.02, W1.02, W1.03, S1.04, O1.04, O1.05
	N04 Need to strengthen the cooperation between education and business	Schools/universities, companies	X X X X X (5)	W1.07, T1.07, W1.07, T1.08
	N05 Need to create a resilient region	Established populations, new entrants, young people, companies	X X X X X X (6)	All
	N06 Need to establish functional e-government/ public administration and other digital services	Established populations, new entrants, companies	X X X X (4)	S1.10, W1.10, O1.10, T1.10, W1.11, O1.11
	N07 Need to establish integrated health and social care (especially related to aging population)	Established populations, aging population	X X X X X (5)	W1.06, T1.06, O1.11
2. Recreation / social activities	N08 Need to preserve cultural landscape and cultural heritage	Established populations, new entrants, visitors	X X X X X (5)	S2.01, O2.01, O2.05
	N09 Need for boosting of the attractiveness of the region for tourism and agrotourism	Visitors, established populations, new entrants	X X X X X X (6)	O2.01, O2.05
	N10 Need to develop and support community activities	Established populations, new entrants, young people	X X X X X (5)	S2.01, O2.01, T2.02, O2.03, W2.04, O2.05
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N11 Need to minimizing of intra-regional disparities	Established populations, new entrants	X X X X X X X (6)	All
	N12 Need to support wellbeing of all inhabitants	Established populations	X X X X X X (6)	All
	N13 Need to support the local identity	Established populations, new entrants, young people	X X X X X (5)	S3.01, W3.02, O3.02, S3.02, O3.03, W3.04, T3.04, S3.05
4. Demographic & human capital	N14 Need to boost the attractiveness of all parts of the region for new entrants	New entrants	X X X X (4)	All

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP (Eg: established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other)	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
	N15 Need to attract young professionals to work in high-tech/innovative companies and research organizations located in the region	New entrants, highly qualified professionals and experts	X X X X X X (6)	S4.01, O4.01, S4.04, O4.04, W4.05, T4.06
	N16 Need to have sufficient social and health services for aging population	Established populations	X X X X X X (6)	W4.04, T4.06
5. Business, economy & innovation	N17 Need to establish new high-tech/innovative companies and their connection with research organizations, support of develop start-ups	Established populations, new entrants, young people, companies, research	X X X X X X (6)	All
	N18 Need to implement the quadruple helix model and support of the cooperation between research organizations and municipalities	Established populations, companies, research, municipalities	X X X X X (5)	All
	N19 Need to shorten of supply chains and support of the local economy	Established populations	X X X X X (5)	All
	N20 Need to support remote working and other job opportunities related to the local economy	Established populations, new entrants, young people, companies, research	X X X X X (5)	All
	N21 Need to support of precision agriculture and other innovative solutions	Established populations, new entrants	X X X X (4)	All
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N22 Need for the coherent community	Established populations, new entrants	X X X X X (5)	O6.02, O6.04, T6.04, O6.05
	N23 Need to sustain the gender equal society	Established populations, new entrants	X X X X X (5)	S6.01
	N24 Need to develop open society and strong communities	Established populations, new entrants	X X X X (4)	S6.01, O6.04, T6.04, O6.05
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N25 Need for adaptation to the climate change		X X X X X X (6)	S7.01, S7.03, O7.04, S7.04, S7.05, O7.05
	N26 Need to use of soil and land in the sustainable way		X X X X X X (6)	S7.01, S7.02, S7.03, O7.04, T7.04, O7.05
	N27 Need for transition to the circular economy and bioeconomy		X X X X X X (6)	S7.01, S7.03, S7.03, O7.04, T7.04, S7.05, O7.05

Table 31. Slovakia Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Need to create and support tele-working opportunities.	established populations, new entrants, young people, women	5	e.g.: W1.01, T3.01
	N02 Need to improve the mobility possibilities to the main city.	established populations, young people, new entrants		
	N03 Need to improve the connections between rural and urban areas.	established populations, young people, new entrants		
	N04 Need to increase good medical (primary attention) services.	established populations, young people, new entrants		
	N05 Need to increase adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services.			
2. Recreation / social activities	N06 Need to improve availability and diversity of recreational and social activities.	young people, new entrants	4	e.g.: W1.01 ,O1.02, W5.01
	N07 Need to create enough and well equipped spaces to allow young people to meet.	young people, new entrants		
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N08 Need to find solutions for problems with the integration of some part of populations.	minorities, new entrants	3	
	N09 Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	new entrants, young people		
	N10 Need to improve the quality of living conditions.	established population, new entrants, young people		
4. Demographic & human capital	N11 Need to improve the dependency ratio by increasing the number of working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly).	young people, new entrants	6	
	N12 Need to better develop community and voluntary sector focused on social needs and creation of new opportunities.	established population, new entrants, young people		
5. Business, economy & innovation	N13 Need to increase decent employment possibilities.	established population, new entrants, young people	1	e.g. : W7.01, T5.02.....
	N14 Need to favor eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	established population, new entrants, young people		

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
	N15 Need to offer good opportunities for startups and creating new businesses.	established population, new entrants, young people		
	N16 Need to increase availability of instruments for financing innovative/new rural activities.	established population, new entrants, young people		
	N17 Need to consider an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses.	established population, new entrants, young people		
	N18 Need to develop adequate services for entrepreneurial support with the provision of experienced services.	established population, new entrants, young people		
	N19 Need to use the potential of the area for new, innovative companies and creative professionals.	established population, new entrants, young people		
	N20 Need to dwell suitable conditions for development of sustainable agriculture and forestry.	established population, new entrants, young people		
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N21 Need to create opportunities for young people to participate in decision making.	young people, new entrants	7	
	N22 Need to increase the sufficiency of lively communities and citizen-driven local activities.	established population, new entrants, young people		
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N23 Need to improve the cultivation practices to be done in an environmentally sound way.	established population, new entrants, young people	2	
	N24 Need to valorize more High Nature Value Areas as environment and nature play an important role.	established population, new entrants, young people		Imp

Table 32. Häme/Finland Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 To improve and secure accessibility of public services in rural areas. ¹	established populations	X X X X (4)	T1.01, W1.01, W1.02, S1.04
	N02 Improving the attractiveness of bioeconomy education and to find out if there are needs to modify education. ¹	new entrants, young people, universities		S1.01
	N03 Strengthening the linkage between education and business. ¹	Universities, businesses	X X (2)	S1.01, W1.08, O1.03
	N04 Improving high-speed broadband networks in some rural areas ³	NA, business	X X X X (4)	W1.03
2. Recreation / social activities	N05 Paying attention to summer residents in the area and their needs (social activities, services etc.) ³	new entrants	X X (2)	S2.03, S3.01, O3.01, O3.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N06 Improving possibilities to sustainable living in rural areas (new opportunities for sustainable living). ¹	Established populations, new entrants	X X (2)	S3.01, O3.01, O3.02
	N07 Supporting multi-locality in living and working. ¹	N/A	X X X X X X X (7)	S1.03, S1.04, O3.01, O3.02
	N08 Highlighting the good feelings and emotions that are related to living in rural areas. ¹	Established populations, new entrants	X X (2)	S3.01, S3.03
4. Demographic & human capital	N09 Inventing ways to get young people to live and work in Häme region. ²	New entrants	X X X (3)	W4.01, W4.03, W4.02
	N10 The ageing people require and use the healthcare and well-being services. It provides the opportunity for business ⁶	new entrants, business		O4.02
5. Business, economy & innovation	N11 Improving profitability of farms. ¹	established populations (new entrants)		W5.03, W5.04, O5.2, O5.01, T5.01
	N12 Supporting new business opportunities in farms and rural areas (in addition to traditional agriculture and forestry). E.g. carbon sequestration and ecosystem ¹	established populations, new entrants	X X X X X X (6)	O5.02, O5.01, O5.04, O5.05, O5.06, S5.02, S5.01, S5.05
	N13 Need to secure continuity (young farmers) and future opportunities of agricultural production. (Challenges to tackle: ageing, market demand, subsidy policy, traditions in farming). ¹	young people, new entrants		W5.03, T5.03, T5.01, O5.02, O5.01, W5.05
	N14 Improvements to research and product development facilities (i.e.laboratories).	N/A (business, universities, innovators...)		W5.09, O5.03

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
	N15 Decreasing the bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care) ⁶	Established population, new entrants	X X (2)	W5.07
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N16 Need to make it easier for newcomers to adapt the community. ²	New entrants	X X X (3)	W6.01, W4.04
	N17 Need to make it easier for migrants to adapt the community. ²	New entrants		W6.02, W4.04
	N18 Supporting farmers in challenges related to well-being and economy. ¹	Established population		T5.03, T5.02, W5.11
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N19 Developing carbon sinks, circular economy solutions and renewable energy solutions in farming. ¹	Business, universities, researchers	X (1)	O7.02, O7.01
	N20 More support to circular economy solutions in the field of bioeconomy (from field to field). ¹		X X X (3)	O7.02, O7.01
	N21 Encouraging tourism and welfare businesses to make use of clean environment and good location. Possibilities to increase international tourism. ³		X (1)	S7.06, S7.05

Table 33. Central Greece/Greece Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	Improve transportation and accessibility to medical centers and structures(e.g. pharmacies) from remote areas. Increase medical staff and supplies.	Elderly and sensitive groups, established populations, new entrants, young people, women.	8	W1.01, W1.04, T1.02
	Improve public transportation and accessibility between remote areas within the region		5	W1.01, O1.03
	Provide more training opportunities (e.g. seminars, e-learning courses, Lifelong learning training). Lack of educational and consulting services for gaining digital and technological skills in agriculture. Increase	Established population, older population, low education groups, old and young professionals.	2	W1.02, W1.03, O1.01, O1.02, T1.02, T1.01
	Guarantee of an adequate access to internet in remote areas and increase the number of free access hot-spots in public places (in ports, schools, sports/recreation areas, churches, etc.)	Established population, newcomers, professionals, tourists.	4	O1.01, T1.02, T1.03
	Remote services	Established population	19	W1.05, O1.01, T1.03
2. Recreation / social activities	Important culture treasures (famous archaeological sites), natural resources (thermal springs, Natura 2000 regions) and religious destinations. Further development and exploitation of recreation sites and existing structures	Established population, tourism businesses newcomers, tourists.	20	O2.01, SO2.01, SO2.02, W2.02, T2.01
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	More transparency and reduction of bureaucracy on public services	Established population, new entrant professionals.	21	T3.01
	Development of educational structures for immigrants and vulnerable groups	Young and old immigrants	14	W03.02
4. Demographic & human capital	Increase number of employees for supporting elderly people and sensitive groups	Elderly and sensitive groups, established populations	15	W4.02, T4.02
	Improvement of volunteering structures (NGO, infrastructure)	Established population	16	T4.02
	Increase of population especially young people		1	T4.01, T4.02, W4.01
	Assimilation of migrant groups		13	O1.02
5. Business, economy & innovation	Improve tax system for increasing business establishments and development of new entrepreneurships	Established population, new entrants, old and young professionals	9	W5.04, W5.03, T5.01, O5.03, S5.01

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
	The region is suitable for RES project development due to its ideal conditions for wind and solar energy exploitation. There is also availability of power infrastructure and transmission networks.	Established population, new entrants	10	S5.03, O5.02, O5.03
	Enhance the efficiency of funding opportunities (e.g. agricultural subsidies, agritourism)	Established population, new entrants	7	W5.03, W5.04, W5.02, T5.01, S5.01, T5.03
	Support of startup business and motivate young people to inhabit region		3	W5.01, W5.02, W5.03, O5.1-O5.8, T5.01
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	Increase the presence of women and young people in decision making and social activities	Established population, women, new entrants	12	W6.01
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Increase initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agritourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas.	Established population, tourism businesses newcomers, tourists.	6	O7.01, S7.01, W7.01, S7.02
	Development of environmental technologies and energy saving technologies	Established population, new entrant professionals.	11	O7.02, O7.03, W7.01, W7.02

Table 34. Monaghan / Ireland Needs

Monaghan Pilot	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 - Proactive promotion of the rural area to attract newcomers	New entrants.	3	O1.01,O1.02, O2.01, O3.01, O5.01,O7.01, S1.01, S2.01, S3.01, S4.01, S5.01, S6.01, S7.01, W3.01, W3.02, W4.01, W5.01, W5.02, T3.02, T4.01, T5.01, T6.01, T7.02.
	N02 - Provide better access to public services and public transport in all remote dispersed rural areas.	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	10	W1.01, W1.02, O1.01, O1.02, S1.01, O2.01, W2.01, S3.01, S5.01, T7.01.
2. Recreation / social activities	N03 -Improve broadband access & ICT skills.	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	9	W2.01, O2.01, S3.01, W3.01, W5.02, S5.01, S5.01, T5.01
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N04 - Increase employment opportunities in rural areas	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	7	O3.01, S3.01, W3.01, T3.02, O1.01, O2.01, O5.01, O6.01, O7.01, S4.01, S5.01, W5.01, W6.01, T4.01, T5.01, T7.02
	N05 - Address BREXIT uncertainty	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	5	T3.01, T3.02, O1.01, O2.01, O5.01, S5.01, S7.02, W1.02, W5.01, T5.02.
4. Demographic & human capital	N06 - Provide support schemes that encourage new entrants & young people into farming	New entrants, young people, women.	1	S4.01, W4.01, T4.01, O1.01, O1.02, O6.01, S3.01, S5.01, S6.01, S7.01, S7.02, W3.01, W3.02, W5.01, W5.02, W6.01, T4.01, T5.01, T7.02
5. Business, economy & innovation	N07 - Improve the financial security of farming through greater diversification, access to finance & alternatives to land purchase.	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	2	O5.01, S5.01, W5.01, W5.02, T5.01, T5.02, O1.01, O1.02, O3.01, S3.01, S4.01, S6.01, W2.01, W3.01, W3.2, W4.01, T3.02,T4.01, T6.01, T7.02.
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N08 - CAP reform, e.g. LEADER & European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Farmer Groups should be flexible enough to respond to local needs.	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	8	S6.01, O6.01, T6.01, T3.02, O5.01, O7.01, S3.01, S5.01,O1.02, S5.01.
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N09 - Encourage more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables & forestry development.	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	4	S7.01, S7.02, O7.01, T7.01, T7.02, O1.01, O5.01, S6.01, S7.02, T5.01, T6.01.
	N10 - More sustainable rural development planning, & proactive response to climate change.	Established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other	6	S7.01, S7.02, O7.01, T7.01,T7.02, S5.01, S6.01, O1.01, O1.02, O3.01, O5.01, W3.01, W4.01, W6.01, T3.02, T4.01, T5.01, T5.02, T6.01.

Table 35. Galilee/ Israel Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Develop a better transportation to the Centre, by trains and high ways	All citizens	10	W1.01,; W1.02
	N02 Better connection to the Tel-Hai College and the Kibbutzim	All citizens and students	9	W1.02
2. Recreation / social activities	N03 Improve the social activities in the region	All citizens	11	W2.01;
	N04 Find the resources to bring additional national performance to Galilee	All citizens	12	W2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N05 Find more employment possibilities in order to bring more young people to the Galilee	Young people as well as All citizens	1	W3.02; W3.03; W5.01; W5.02
	N06: Enable young people to purchase a house in the Galilee in better financial conditions	Young people as well as All citizens	5	W3.01; W3.02; W5.01; W5.02
4. Demographic & human capital	N07: Find more employment possibilities in order to bring more young people to the Galilee, and have more children in the kindergarten and	Young people	2	W3.01; W3.02; W5.01; W5.02
	N08: Enhance the activities and Governmental financial support at Tel-Hai College to bring more students to study in the region	Young people	6	W5.01; W5.02; W5.03
5. Business, economy & innovation	N09: Allocate more governmental support to businesses and especially to SMEs and youngsters with innovative ideas.	Young people as well as All citizens	3	W5.01; W5.02; W5.03
	N10: Give higher tax exempt to industries in the periphery	All citizens and the business community	4	W5.01; W5.02; W5.03
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N11: Support additional social and cultural activities in the region		13	W6.01
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N12: Enhance the environmental activites at the Agmon Lake	All citizens	8	
	N13: Preserve the environmental situation in the Galilee region and take special care of the Sea of Galilee conditions	All citizens	7	

Table 36. Apulia / Italy Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Encourage the creation of infrastructure connections between rural and urban areas, therefore towards the main city of the region	Established populations, new arrivals	3	W1.01, T1.02, W2.02, T6.01
	N02 Promote the spread of telematic technologies in order to promote remote assistance for families and businesses	Disadvantaged, disabled, new arrivals, immigrants, enterprises, families	3	W1.03, T1.01, T1.02, T2.01, W2.02
2. Recreation / social activities	N03 Strengthening local services aimed at leisure and the culture of the rural community in favour of the disadvantaged and/or disabled people	Disadvantaged, disabled, immigrants, new arrivals	3	T1.01, S2.01, W2.01, W2.02, T2.01, S4.02, O4.02
	N04 Identify and classify areas susceptible to recreational uses and urban greenery, to design and implement improvement works that contribute to the increase in the quality of life	Established populations, Disadvantaged, disabled, immigrants, new arrivals	3	S1.02, S2.01, S2.02, W2.01, W2.02, O2.01, T2.01, W3.01, S4.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N05 Promote social inclusion and improve the quality of life of disadvantaged people	Disadvantaged, young people, immigrants, new arrivals	4	T1.02, S2.01, S2.02, S3.01, S3.02, W3.01, W3.02, S4.01, S4.02
	N06 Promote the birth of social enterprises and the spread of social agriculture	Disadvantaged, young people, immigrants, new arrivals	3	S2.01, S2.02, S3.01, S3.02, S4.01, O4.02, O5.01
4. Demographic & human capital	N07 Control of the main abandonment phenomena by implementing integrated development processes of production activities in the internal areas	Young people, immigrants, new arrivals	4	T1.02, W3.02, T3.01, W4.01, O4.01, T4.01, T6.01
	N08 Promote generational change and development opportunities for family plans	Young people, immigrants, new arrivals	3	T1.02, T3.01, W4.02, T4.01, T4.02, W5.01, T6.01
5. Business, economy & innovation	N09 Promote technological innovation linked to the Green Economy	Enterprises, environment	3	S5.01, O5.02, O5.01, W5.02, W7.01, W7.02
	N10 Encourage the creation of new businesses and support youth and female entrepreneurship and the birth of innovative start-ups	Enterprises, young people, women	3	W5.01, O5.01, T5.01, T5.02, W6.01, O6.02, T6.01

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N11 Promote the employment of women and young people and the abandonment of rural areas	Young people, women	4	T1.02, T3.01, W3.02, W4.01, T4.01, W4.02, T4.02, S6.01, W6.01, W6.02, O6.02, T6.01
	N12 Encourage the creation of lively communities and local activities led by young people and women	Young people, women	3	W2.01, T2.01, S4.01, W4.02, S6.01, O6.01, S6.02
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N13 Promote the enhancement and protection of the historical-cultural-environmental heritage and protected areas	Environment, established populations	3	T6.01, S7.01, S7.02, O7.01, T7.02, W7.02
	N14 Promote the adoption of cultivation, fishing and aquaculture techniques in rural areas compatible with the natural landscape with low environmental impact	Environment, established populations	3	S7.02, W7.01, O7.01, O7.02, T2.02

Table 37. Vidzeme / Latvia Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Need to provide mobility & accessibility services, including transport and road infrastructures; As well as to provide intra-regional public transportation, i.e., between rural and urban areas	Inhabitants, especially youth	XXXXXXXX (7)	W1.01; O1.01; O1.2; T1.01; T1.2
	N02 Need of implementation new technologies available/using to enhance quality of public transport	All inhabitants, especially youth and working people	XXXXXX (6)	W1.02; O1.3; T1.3
	N03 Need to ensure availability of optimal cost and quality public services, including health, education and culture	All people	XXXXXXXX (7)	W1.04
	N04 Need to create system of lifelong learning and vocation training, including ICT and digital training that responds to people needs and allows the needed quality	All people, especially working age	XXXXXX (6)	S1.02; W1.03; O1.4; T1.4;
	N05 Need to assure broadband networks & internet connectivity in some remote rural areas	All people, especially families with schoolchildren, youth and working age inhabitants	XXXXX (5)	S1.02; W1.03; W1.04; O1.4; T1.4;
2. Recreation / social activities	N06 Need for well provided spaces to allow young and adult people to meet, as well as to gather, exchange ideas, cooperate and networking also for the business environment	Young people, working age people and entrepreneurs	XXXXX (5)	S2.02; W2.01; O2.01; T2.01
	N07 Need for accessibility & quality of services in remote territories of the region, particularly in rural areas	All people	XXXXXX (6)	W2.02; O2.02; T2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N08 Need to provide the option to rent or purchase qualitative housing at affordable prices	New entrants, young people	XXXXXXXX (7)	S3.01; W3.01; O3.01; O3.02; T3.01 S3.02
	N09 Need to integrate the minorities and new entrants via strengthening of local communities, social activities, i.e., social entrepreneurship' & networking	All people, especially minorities & new entrants	XXXXX (5)	S3.02; W3.02; O3.03; T3.02
	N10 Need to promote employment by offering job opportunities or encouraging the creation of new businesses & self-employment	Municipalities, working age people, entrepreneurs, self-employment	XXXXXX (6)	W3.03; W3.04
4. Demographic & human capital	N11 Need to attract both, high qualified and simple workers	Working age people, especially new entrants & young people	XXXX (4)	S4.01; W4.02; W4.03; O4.01; O4.02; O4.02; T4.01; T4.02; T4.03
	N12 Need to promote the acquisition of any kind of education (i.e., elearning): higher education, general secondary, vocational,	All people, especially in working ages	XXXXXXXX (7)	W4.06

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
	adults formal & non-formal & lifelong education and training, int al., via internet			
	13 Need for community activity coordinators/ local leaders	All people, esp. representatives of public, educational, cultural institutions & NGOs, entrepreneurs, farmers, etc.	XXX (3)	W4.4; T4.04
	N14 Need to develop community and voluntary sectors, which address the social (i.e., local) needs & create opportunities	All people, esp. representatives of public, educational, cultural institutions & NGOs, entrepreneurs, farmers, etc.	XXXXXX (6)	W4.4; T4.0
5. Business, economy & innovation	N15 Need to support creation of products & services with value added, int al., support for innovation or technology transfer & eco-innovation	R&D, Entrepreneurs, self-employment	XXXXXX (6)	S5.01; W5.08; W5.10; W5.11; O5.04; O5.05; O5.06; T5.03
	N16 Need to implement digital technologies in business Support to digital transition - opportunities for new economic activities and productivity growth	Entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment	XXXXXX (6)	W5.04; O5.02; T5.02;
	N17 Need to support participation in adult education	All people, particularly in working ages	XXXXX (5)	W5.05; W5.06; T5.02
	N18 Need to support sustainable tourism, esp., rural, culinary, agro-tourism, heritage, etc., recreation services, and social farming	Entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment	XXXXXX (6)	W5.06; W5.14; O5.08; T5.05
	N19 Need to attract tourists, esp. foreign, by developing competitive tourism destination	Entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment, municipalities	XXX (3)	W5.06; O5.08; T5.05
	N20 Need to support various types of health, rehabilitation & care services, the know-how of which could be offered as export product	R&D, entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment, municipalities, public institutions, NGOs, etc.	XXXXX (5)	S5.04; W5.11; W5.15; W5.16; O5.09; O5.10; O5.11; T5.06
	N21 Need to support sustainable (resource effective) production of value added agro-food, forestry & wood products, as well as other bio based products and services, int al., for export	R&D, entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment, municipalities, public institutions, NGOs, etc.	XXXXXXX (7)	S5.02; S5.04; W5.12; W5.13; W5.15; W5.16; O5.07; O5.09; T5.04; T5.05; T5.06
	N22 Need to attract investors to the region	Entrepreneurs, municipalities, public institutions, NGOs, etc.	XXXXX (5)	W5.16; O5.09; T5.06
	N23 Need to involve more young people (under 40) into the farming	Young people, farmers, public institutions, NGOs, etc.	XXXXX (5)	W5.13
	N24 Need for support systems for entrepreneurs, increasing export, innovations, cooperation clusters etc.	Entrepreneurs, municipalities, public institutions, NGOs, etc.	XXXXX (5)	S5.01; S5.04; W5.08; W5.09; W5.10 W5.15;
	N25 Need to support (i.e., services and finances) for new entrants to the rural areas	New entrants	XXXXX (5)	W5.04; W5.07; W5.08; W5.09; W5.11; O5.01; O5.02; O5.03; O5.04; O5.05; T5.03
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N26 Need to support community activities, i.e., these activities that support local identity	All people, representatives of public, educational, cultural institutions & NGOs, entrepreneurs, farmers, municipalities, etc.	XXXXXX (6)	S6.01; W6.01; O6.01; O6.02; T6.01 W6.02

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
	N27 Need to strengthening of local communities, public (i.e., cultural) & social activities, i.e., social entrepreneurship, networking	All people, representatives of public, educational, cultural institutions & NGOs, entrepreneurs, farmers, municipalities, etc.	XXXXXXXX (7)	S6.01; W6.01; O6.01; O6.02; T6.01 W6.02
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N28 Need for entrepreneurs to adapt and react on new politics (Green deal, F2F)	Entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment	XXXXX (5)	S7.01; W7.01; O7.01; T7.01; T7.02
	N29 Need to support generating value added from recreation activities	R&D, entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment	XXXXX (5)	S7.01; S7.02; W7.02; O7.02; T7.03; W7.03
	N30 Need to support usage of biological resources for the production of value added goods	R&D, entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment	XXXXXXXX (7)	S7.01; W7.01; W7.03; O7.02; O7.02; T7.01; T7.03
	N31 Need to support implementation of agri-environmental & climate mitigation & adaptation, and related measures (i.e., Natura 2000, Water framework, etc.)	R&D, entrepreneurs, farmers, self-employment	XXXXXXXX (7)	

Table 38. Gevgelija-Strumica /-FYROM Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	Need for adequate day care facilities in the area - construction of retirement homes and centres for early child development	established population (children, older people)	5	W1.01
	Improved access to adequate medical services	established population	2	W1.02
	Provide better opportunities for higher /professional education	new entrants, young people	1	W1.03, O1.03
	The public transport needs to be made more regular in order make public services (health/education) easily accessible for rural population	established population (children, older people)	4	W1.04, W1.06, O1.04
	Efficient digitization of public services in order to simplify the relationships of rural population with the administration	established population	3	W1.05
	Need to support teleworking opportunities	established population	6	W1.07, O1.01
2. Recreation / social activities	Provide spaces where young people can meet/co-working spaces	established population (young people)	4	W2.01
	Provide possibilities for children to attend extracurricular activities in the after-school hours	established population (children)	3	W2.02
	Offer variety of recreational activities/hobbies for young people and rural population in general, such as art, sports, music, dance, volunteering	established population	2	W2.03, W2.04
	Offer elderly people recreational activities and spaces to meet and socialize	established population (older people)	1	W2.05
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	Increase the knowledge among the population about environmental sustainability, circular economy, energy sources, renewable energy and also provide stimulations to motivate sustainable behaviour	established population	2	W3.01, T3.02
	Making rural areas more attractive, especially for young people	new entrants	4	W3.02
	Increase the compatibility in social and political interactions	established population	3	W3.03
	Establish institutions at local or regional level competent for different areas of rural development	established population	1	W3.04
4. Demographic & human capital	Develop a systematic approach to making rural areas more attractive for young people by addressing various critical issues: education, day-care, extracurricular activities, employment and career prospects, social and recreational activities	established population (young people), new entrants	1	W4.01, W4.03, W4.04, W4.07, T4.03, T4.04
	To support the non-profit sector and the existing initiatives aimed at mobilizing rural communities as agents of local development and as participants in rural policy	established population	2	W4.02, O4.01

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
5. Business, economy & innovation	Provide incentives for companies to become more interested in introducing innovations or adopting innovative business models	established population (business sector)	6	W5.01, T5.01, T5.04
	Provide consultancy services for entrepreneurial support (technology, finance, HR, marketing, sales etc)	established population	2	W5.02, O5.02
	Provide special tax incentives to attract new businesses in rural areas	established population	5	W5.03, W5.05
	Develop a strategic approach to planning and marketing of rural tourism; attract trained human resources; provide easy access to tourist sites	established population, new entrants	8	W5.04, T5.03, W5.05
	Address the problem of mismatch between demand and supply in the labour market (e.g. by introducing dual education)	established population, new entrants	3	W5.06
	Establish separate funds for financial support of innovative/new rural activities	established population, new entrants	4	W5.07, T5.05
	There is a need for development of coordinated approach among stakeholders in the process of the development of existing economic policies for rural development, resulting in matched measures with the real needs of rural population and economies	established population, new entrants	1	W5.08
	Develop a policy framework and provide adequate institutional support for sustainable business models/green businesses/eco-entrepreneurship	established population, new entrants	7	W5.09, T5.06
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	Inspire lively communities and citizen-driven local activities	established population	3	W6.01
	Create measures to encourage youth participation in decision-making and contribute to policy making	established population (young people)	1	W6.02
	Find ways to reduce isolation and loneliness which affects the quality of life of rural population, especially older people	established population (older people)	2	W6.03
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Need for implementation of appropriate and sustainable waste management techniques by households and businesses and efforts to minimize the amount of waste sent to landfills (recycling, reusing)	established population	2	W7.01
	Focus on cultivation practices that reduce environmental impacts (organic farming)	established population	3	W7.02
	Development of rural road Infrastructure	established population, new entrants	1	W7.03
	Invest in instruments for protection and promotion of biodiversity	established population	4	W7.04

Table 39. Mazowieckie / Poland Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	CONNECTION WITH SWOT ELEMENTS (Code)
1. Availability of public and other services	N01 Waste and water infrastructure	established populations, new entrants, society	3	W1.01, T1.01, T5.01 T5.02
	N02 Development of transportation network in remote areas	Established populations, new entrants	7	W1.02, T1.01
2. Recreation / social activities	N03 More diverse recreational and social offer for all the age groups, and most welcome of events joining different generations	Established populations, young people, elderly people	9	W2.01 and W2.02
	N04 Establishment of cooperation/new schemes to attract relevant stakeholders in the region with cultural offer, with a special focus on integration of women, youth and potential newcomers.	Women, youth and potential newcomers	3	W4.02, T2.02
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N05 Mediation for resolving, diminishing social and political conflicts	Established populations	5	W3.01, T2.02
	N06 Diminishing income inequalities – especially in the context of educational opportunities, access to healthcare and access to public services and public goods	Established populations	1	T3.01, T3.02, W3.02
4. Demographic & human capital	N07 Tackling unemployment	Established populations, young people	6	T4.01, W3.02
5. Business, economy & innovation	N08 Creating business-friendly environment	New entrants, established populations	4	T2.02 T5.01
	N09 - Provide support schemes that encourage new young people into farming	Youth	4	T5.01, S6.02, O7.01
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N10 Lack of gender and age equality in public decision-making	Established populations, women, young and elderly people	8	T2.02
	N11 Need to find solutions for problems with the integration of certain groups (young, senior policy) in remote areas	Excluded groups (young, women, older) in remote areas	2	W3.02, S4.01, S6.02, W6.02
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N12 Need to improve the farming practices and processing towards promotion of the environmentally-friendly food production.	Farmers, small processors	4	O7.02
	N13 Environmentally friendly business activities and public services	Established populations, new entrants	2	O7.02

Table 40. Segóbriga / Spain Needs

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	SWOT ELEMENTS
1. Availability of public and other services	N03 Guarantee quality internet access in the territory and improve the training of the population in the use of the internet and telematic services	Established population	3	W1.05 Poor Internet access in the territory T1.01 Lack of capacities for the adequate use of new technologies (adoption gap)
	N05 Improve the transport service both within the territory and from the territory to urban areas, with particular attention to transport to health services.	Established population	5	W1.02 Poor transportation service both within the territory and to urban areas
	N06 Improve the quality of health care service	Established population	6	W1.01 Primary health care service is limited
2. Recreation / social activities	N12 Promote leisure activities for the most diversified population, especially taking into account the needs of young people, as well as the creation of recreation areas (playgrounds) and sports	Established population, Youth	12	W2.01 There are not enough leisure activities in the area, particularly for young people. W2.02 Youth gathering spaces are insufficient and little diversified, as well as the offer of extracurricula for children is limited S2.02 The inhabitants of the area value and are concerned about leisure activities T2.01 Lack of young population
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living 3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	N08 Guarantee sufficient and quality services (nurseries, electricity, drinking water, waste treatment services, etc.).	Established population	8	W1.03. Lack of childcare and early childhood education services T1.02 Continued population decline and aging can lead to a reallocation of public services or even their elimination
	N13 Improve social services and promote the creation of nursing homes	Old people	13	W6.02 Solitude and isolation are a major problem in the area
4. Demographic & human capital	N01 Avoid the exodus of young people and women from the territory and fight against depopulation	Established population, youth, women	1	S3.01 There are adequate housing possibilities in the area W4.02 W4.02 Little child and youth population aggravated by a decrease in the birth rate in the territory S4.01 There are women in the territory, although there is masculinization in the area W4.01 Limited opportunities for family development in the area W2.03 Commercial services in the area are insufficient T1.03 Abandonment of the rural environment of families with babies due to lack of resources that allow family and work reconciliation T1.04 Youth leaving rural areas in search of higher education opportunities.
5. Business, economy & innovation	N02 Promote job creation in rural areas, for the general population, with special emphasis on youth and women	Established population	2	W5.02 General employment opportunities in the area are very limited W1.06 Lack of telework opportunities in the area O1.01 Recent advances in the development of telework may favor the location of new professionals in rural areas

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	SWOT ELEMENTS
5. Business, economy & innovation	N04 Facilitate business development and entrepreneurship	companies and entrepreneurs	4	W1.06 Lack of telework opportunities in the area W5.01 New business development conditions are very limited, particularly for star-up and innovative companies W5.02 There are not enough sources of financing for the creation of innovative companies or a special tax regime to settle in rural areas T5.01 The economic recession as a result of the coronavirus may hinder business development in rural areas T5.03 Lack of ecosystems to support business development and entrepreneurship
5. Business, economy & innovation	N09 Promote economic diversification in a jointly organized way from the institutions and the private sector, through the tourist development of the area, taking advantage of the heritage and natural resources existing in the territory, correctly defining a tourist package as well as promoting a complementary offer.	entrepreneurs, established population	9	S5.02 The area offers possibilities for economic activities related to sustainable tourism (cultural, natural heritage, gastronomy, etc.) T3.01 High number of second residences O3.01 Use of second residences to expand the offer of rural tourism in the area T5.02 The economic recession caused by the coronavirus may limit the influx of tourists to the territory or the period of their stay in the territory in the short-medium term.
	N10 Favor the profitability of the agricultural sector and promote economic diversification by promoting the development of agribusiness from existing raw materials, especially cereals with transformation, commercialization, organic products, local markets, etc-	Farmers	10	S5.02 The area is suitable for the development of sustainable agriculture, livestock and forestry T5.04 Gradual reduction in the need for labor on farms. S5.02 The area offers possibilities for economic activities related to sustainable tourism (cultural, natural heritage, gastronomy, etc.), as well as related to agribusiness and manufacturing
	N11 Promote from the administrations a differentiated taxation for rural areas.	established population	11	W5.03 There are not enough sources of financing for the creation of innovative companies or a special tax regime for settling in rural areas
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	N07 Promote vocational and higher education and training, particularly for young people and women	Youth,women, established population	7	W1.04 Insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education T1.04 Youth leaving rural areas in search of higher education opportunities.
	N15 Promote the participation of the rural population in decision-making, particularly among women and youth, as well as minorities present in the territory. Promote coexistence and relationship between the different groups that live in rural areas	Youth,women, established population	15	W6.01 There is no strong dynamic of social participation in the area, especially among young people S6.01 The participation of women in decision-making and social life in the area is important, although it can be improved W3.01 Sometimes integration problems of some minorities are identified T3.02 Lack of involvement of the population in community decision-making W6.03 The high percentage of the aging population does not facilitate the introduction of social and cultural changes. W6.04. Little appreciation and social awareness of the importance of preserving the heritage elements
	N16 Development of volunteer policies among the population to develop services in an altruistic way where the private and public sectors have difficulty offering it.	Youth,women, established population	16	W1.03. Lack of childcare and early childhood education services W2.02 Youth gathering spaces are insufficient and little diversified, as well as the offer of extracurricula for children is limited

	NEEDS	TARGET GROUP	RANKING	SWOT ELEMENTS
7. Environment & Biodiversity	N14 Conserve, improve and value the natural resources and landscape diversity of the territory	established population	14	<p>W7.01 The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued.</p> <p>S7.01 The area presents landscapes and biodiversity of high value, well considered by the population</p> <p>T7.01 Environmental degradation by industrial facilities</p>

Annex 8. Panel Workshop comments

	1. Availability of public and other services
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	Mobility as a service can have an effect on the social and economic functioning of villages in rural areas. Spatial adjustments may be required to achieve this effect to the full. Slow roads and neighbourhood roads are public spaces that contribute to the liveability of the countryside and the accessibility of the rural environment. This in turn raises questions concerning new forms of mobility and transport such as electric bicycles and larger agricultural vehicles, and in general on road safety . Neighbourhood services include a full network of maintenance services, childcare, local DIY work, ... etc. and are perceived as important for rural integration.
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	The proper accessibility of wide range of services is a key factor to sustain the proper development of the whole region. To achieve this goal is necessary to provide high-speed internet in all localities of the region with following digitalization and development of related processes. Digitalization is a basic condition for the sustainable development of the region and strengthening of its resilience.
SLOVAKIA	Need to simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms. Need to restore local market places. Need to encourage cooperation of different public sectors, such as agriculture, education, health, environment, regional development, transport etc. Need to promote healthy nutrition with special attention to schools, hospitals, social establishment that could procure directly from local farmers. Need to have a state run promotion of establishments for tourism based on making Slovakia attractive as tourist destination unknown to many.
HAME/FINLAND	N03: There is great need for increased co-operation between universities/ universities of applied science and businesses which would produce new products/innovations/employees and trainees/marketing and sales knowhow. Entrepreneur organisations can help to build these connections. N04: Broadband networks only in densely populated urban areas is not enough. Good internet connections should be available to all people, also in sparsely populated areas.
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Stakeholders mentioned lack of broadband internet, which is also confirmed by Q8.2. Furthermore, training opportunities regarding business development, digital technologies and promotion of agricultural products are required. Creation of online structures for health, education and remote services.
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	The attributes of a rural area are always obvious to the local inhabitants, who will make their own decisions about its relative attractiveness as a place to live and work in. But for potential newcomers, there is a need to market the rural area and make potential newcomers aware of what is available, the potential. We need to paint a picture of what living and working in our rural area will be like, should someone choose to move here. Models in Sweden and elsewhere demonstrate that a proactive approach is often needed to make people aware of what an area can offer and to help sustain a community. The challenge often articulated is how do we keep our young people in the area. This should be looked at differently; in how can we attract young people to our area.
GALILEE/ISRAEL	All participants agree that this is a drawback for developing the region
APULIA/ITALY	It is necessary to invest in transport to ensure a better connection between rural and urban areas as well as connections to the main city of the region, Bari. Furthermore, from a technological point of view, there is a low level of thematic work that can guarantee assistance to
VIDZEME/LATVIA	N01 Youth are used to be mobile by using alternatives to owning car, such as car sharing, cycling etc. It becomes challenging in rural areas with low public transport coverage. N03 Should be switch from hobby lifelong learning to practical, including entrepreneur ones. Possibly decreasing the places where its' provided in order to rise the quality, but then ensuring mobility is crucial. * Regional resources and unique characteristics should be taken into account.
Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM	Municipalities have significant problems to maintain the quality and access to basic services in small settlements - The provision of high schools is in the municipal headquarters and the pupils from villages depend on regular transport The Government is also subsidizing the costs for schooling in terms of provision of free books and educational material for all pupils, IT equipment and internet connections of schools and free transportation of the pupils in the rural area - The infrastructure of roads, water supply, sewerage and electricity is also seriously inadequate in many areas access to medication supply and pharmaceutical stores is limited in rural areas and is considered as problem by the rural dwellers Accessibility to primary schools is somewhat satisfactory for children from rural areas all the faculties are obliged to organize their classes outside Skopje no investments for construction of retirement homes and centers for early child development - The spread of the Internet has incredible growth in recent years
Mazowieckie/POLAND	The survey concentrated on daily life public services like transportation, education and health services. For both quality of life and economic activity also waste and water management as well as electricity are of extreme importance. Also the development strategy of Mazowieckie region strongly underlines these threats.
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	In relation to internet access, the panel of agents has considered that it was a necessity to be considered among the first prioritization positions. In addition, it was commented that the guarantee of having quality internet access in the territory must necessarily be accompanied by an improvement in the digital training of the population. In relation to transport, the panel pointed out that the needs of the territory in this matter are focused above all on transport to health centers and hospitals.

	2. Recreation / social activities
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	There is a perceived growing need for peace, quiet, lee and recreation which in turn influences the design and management of rural villages. Digitisation in rural areas seems an important strategic development to enhance participation of inhabitants in local organisations and local activities. The rural environment may play an important role for healthcare and general well-being. Many of the socio-cultural organisations are active in cities and not in rural areas.
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	The advantage of rural areas is related to strong communities/community life and cultural and natural heritage. It is necessary to preserve and protect it for future generations.
SLOVAKIA	Need to make rural areas more attractive for young people by providing them a space where they can meet each other and socialize. Need to have recreational space for families with children. Need to establish local supporting communities. Need to organize local projects driven and owned by local people. Need to organize excursions and trips for schools at local farms. Need to promote school gardens run by students and school community. Need to promote community gardens.
HAME/FINLAND	
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Development of recreational thematic parks by exploiting existing structures
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	Broadband is a necessity. The Irish government is forcing everything online, the Department of Agriculture, Revenue, this is an essential for every farm in the country. Coverage is very patchy in Monaghan, with many parts of the county with little or no service. From a social and economic perspective, this makes living in rural county Monaghan unattractive. In areas such as tourism, agriculture and forestry, we need to diversify agriculture in rural Ireland. Examples for sustainable tourism are eco, cultural and historical areas of interest, and specific example such as a cycle trail throughout the county, through Bragan Mountain. Another is Hope Castle in Castleblayney. There are many lakes throughout the county.
GALILEE/ISRAEL	It was not discussed too deeply since all are aware that the Galilee is a peripheral region and with such a small population it is difficult to develop these issue too much. All agree that this is needed and that efforts must be done to upgrade the social activities.
APULIA/ITALY	It is important to encourage recreational and extracurricular activities in the area, especially for the elderly and disabled as there is a strong shortage
VIDZEME/LATVIA	N06 Pandemic has shown that people can act based on solidarity and create support networks. N06. Should be more attention on alternative interest community building that would assist on implementing new trends, such as energy communities, permaculture farm unions etc.
Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM	I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area. - For those who live in rural areas, the problem of access to banking services face 36 %, access to postal services 24% and access to cultural facilities 20%. - For those who live in rural areas, 20% face the problem of access to cultural facilities.
Mazowieckie/POLAND	Landscape and spatial transformations in the voivodeship are strongly influenced by suburbanisation processes, i.e. increase in the functional importance of suburban areas. These changes consist in transforming arable land, often valuable in terms of agriculture and nature, into residential areas, single or multi-family. These processes are particularly visible in the western and south-western part of the Warsaw agglomeration, where residential and warehousing developments are introduced on arable land of first and second quality classes.
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	The panel clarified that the need for the territory in terms of leisure activities is not so much to have more resources (sports, parks, etc.) but rather to have a more diversified offer of leisure and culture, which especially takes into account the needs of young people..

	3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	Overall the standard of living is relatively high in the densely populated region of Flanders. As a net result there is active migration from urban to rural areas. New housing developments such as apartment buildings or housing estates have an impact on the experience and use of village spaces. The costs / benefits of village settlement densification needs to be compared with the negligence of old buildings such as farmhouses, churches and manors. In the wake of COVID-19, there is a lot of insecurity in starting up businesses or continuing current activities such as farming.
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	The Central Bohemian Region has according to vast majority of inhabitants a good place for living. There are good conditions for all generations - from establishes population to new entrants.
SLOVAKIA	<p>Need for activities for poverty reduction and social inclusion.</p> <p>Need to improve the access to land for young, small and new farmers.</p> <p>Need to finalize long lasting land consolidation schemes.</p> <p>Need to provide basic services, such as repairer, electrician, woodwork, leatherwork, hairdresser, babysitter etc.</p> <p>Need to improve access to accommodation for people at risk of poverty.</p> <p>Need for quality education for dignified life, work and economic growth and the balancing of social inequalities that aim to improve the quality of education and strengthen the social status of educators, strengthen inclusion and ensure equal opportunities, improve access to work, current and future needs, raising the level of lifelong learning, stabilizing talents and a skilled workforce.</p> <p>Need to take into account the challenges and trends in the vocational education system at secondary, tertiary and lifelong levels and improving the skills of graduates in the tourism sector, the availability of employment opportunities for all population groups will increase.</p>
HAME/FINLAND	<p>N06: An example of work towards sustainable living is Hinku network (Towards Carbon Neutral Municipalities (Hinku)) that brings together municipalities, businesses, citizens and experts to create and carry out solutions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The municipalities involved are committed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions more extensively and rapidly than EU targets require.</p> <p>N07: This, combined with improved public transportation, is vital to attain enough work force and to make rural businesses competitive employers.</p>
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Creation of educational structures for sensitives groups
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	<p>Integration of new entrants can be done in rural communities through sports, schools and church activities. Lacking previous experience of how things are done here, they do not know how to avail of information about how to begin farming. There is a lot of fear and insecurity in beginning any business, including farming. There should be more protection for people who try to start up their own business from the State and local government.</p> <p>BREXIT introduces business uncertainty. SMEs are holding back on investments and adopting a wait and see approach. Now the COVID-19 pandemic is compounding the impact of business uncertainty, we could see a perfective storm effect in the Irish Border region. The scale of the impact won't be known for some time yet, however EU and State programmes like LEADER will be critical in rebooting this rural economy post COVID-19.</p>
GALILEE/ISRAEL	The region can offer high quality of life if employment will be available. Lately some young people are coming back to the region since they can work remotely, but this depends very much of we will be able to further develop the digitalization infrastructure.
APULIA/ITALY	It is essential to improve the integration process both with marginalized populations in the area and with new arrivals/immigrants, also through the creation of social enterprises.
VIDZEME/LATVIA	<p>N08 There are very low possibilities of rental market, also legislation is not appropriate to support people moving to rural areas</p> <p>N08 No access to housing (rental of credit for buying) has been expressed as main concern on limitations for people to move to rural Vidzeme</p>
Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM	<p>People living in rural areas are less satisfied with the quality of life than those living in urban</p> <p>no systematic regulation of wastewater to a large degree. Even though a large number of sewage systems are under construction in rural populated areas, households therein use septic tank systems to a great extent.</p> <p>the sector of agriculture is at the same time the second biggest producer of solid waste (animal and plant) after the mining sector.</p> <p>The climate conditions are also favourable for usage of renewable sources of energy in the direction of providing energy for the agricultural sector</p> <p>but only 10% of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste</p>
Mazowieckie/POLAND	The towns located in the vicinity of Warsaw form a metropolitan area and show a tendency to dynamic demographic and socio-economic development. This is related to the influx of people, the suburbanisation of Warsaw, the emergence of new housing estates and the development of communication and social infrastructure.
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	Regarding the living conditions, the agents of the territory clarified that it is essential to provide infrastructures to the fair spaces in order to promote the territory, as well as improve the waste treatment policy.

	4. Demographic & human capital
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	A number of pertinent questions were formulated in relation to this theme: What guidance is there in villages for the rapidly changing society? How do the elderly, young people and newcomers participate in village life? What are the options for increasing the participation rate of the different groups? How strongly are residents attached to their village? How does the identity debate live in the villages? What is the administrative and unifying importance of groups that originally represented the village such as farmers, guilds, small-scale trade, hunters, ...?
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	The region is dealing with aging population in the peripheral areas. On the other hand, there is a significant potential for expert and highly educated newcomers due to the capital located in the centre of the region.
SLOVAKIA	Need to support generation exchange in agriculture. Need to provide incentives for young people to come to live and work in rural areas through scholarships, providing accommodation in vocational schools etc.
HAME/FINLAND	
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Demographic and depopulation issues due to unemployment
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	Ageing Farmers need a scheme to help older farmers who want to stop farming. Older farmers are reluctant to sell their land or even to pass it on from father to son or daughter. There used to be an early retirement scheme for farmers which was an incentive for them to hand the land on to younger generation or sell it if they are bachelors. It needs to be easier economically for younger people to begin farming. Can you imagine having no history in farming and wanting to farm and going to any bank in the country to ask for a couple of hundred thousand to begin farming? You just wouldn't get it. It is the younger generation who will diversify farming because older farmers are not going to change the way they do things. A major threat is younger generations leaving the country for the cities. There is a lack of information for young people who are not from a farming background. We need to invest in young people. Provide education about the importance of continuing to farm locally. For example, explain the connection between farming and the arts such as felting and wool, school gardens for growing vegetables and fruit, get youth clubs involved in community gardens. Provide education through social farming opportunities in Transition Year or as part of overall education. Young people need to understand the importance of farming in different ways. Understanding the connection between art and farming can make farming more attractive to young people. There is a lack of empowerment for young people to take over farming. Policies and tax incentives already exist, however, to succeed farming must be made profitable and viable for young people or they will work off the farm. For those who want to begin farming or are new to farming. There are opportunities, but they need to be unlocked. Education is important. We have Monaghan Institute of Technology (MIT), but it does not offer many third level qualifications. We have Ballyhaise Agricultural College in Cavan, but MIT could begin to focus on an education in farming and agricultural diversity, the environment and tourism. Offer options locally to keep young people local.
GALILEE/ISRAEL	Efforts are done to bring 500,000 people to the Galilee by the KKL organisation (Relocation project) and we believe that this depends on availability of employment that is very much connected to available infrastructure.
APULIA/ITALY	From the discussion, it emerges that there are possibilities for future family plans even if, on the basis of the desk research, the migratory flow towards better realities is high. For this reason, it's important to invest in control of the main abandonment phenomena.
VIDZEME/LATVIA	* General lifelong learning and knowledge of people is important - there is currently a lack of information, attention should be paid to the effective transmission of information, bringing together those who need information with those who can provide it. Negative human influence on nature (Anthropogenic GHG emissions, sustainable food, waste management) tends to be the result of ignorance, not abuse or deliberate passivity. * Ability to make decisions in region is very important. Pandemic impact on the health system, public administration plays a major role in ensuring functions. Public sector intervention in various sectors. Without public intervention, successful development is not possible. Climate adaptation measures in the context of crisis management (floods, storms, etc.). * Youth are more frequent changing studies and jobs. More attention should be paid to "try-out" and vocational-kind of training already in primary and secondary schools, involving into the practical environments.
Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM	The primary producers in rural areas possess low adaptation capacity due to financial and know how limitations. The intensive migration of the young rural population, the low access to services and the social exclusion are another set of challenges and constraints - In the total population size, the number of male population is higher. However, the difference between men and women is - Rural Development Network, which aims to mobilise rural communities as agents of local development and as participants in rural policy A quite low rate of enrolled and graduated students - Considerable share (13,4%) of rural population above age of 15 has insufficient or total lack of education, 2,6% are illiterate and 10,9% have not completed primary education
Mazowieckie/POLAND	The Mazowieckie Voivodeship is the region with the largest demographic potential in the country. The voivodeship is inhabited by about 5.3 million people (over 14% of the Polish population) and this number is constantly growing. The inhabitants of cities constitute about 64.2% of the region's population. The remaining ones (about 2 million people) are the inhabitants of rural areas, constituting a significant potential for the development of agricultural production and food processing. In the Mazowieckie Voivodeship there is a strong concentration of population in the capital city's suburban zone (which is, inter alia, a result of suburbanisation processes), with the simultaneous depopulation of its peripheral zones (population loss occurs both in small towns and in rural areas). The demographic structure of the province's inhabitants is deteriorating. Since 2005, the number of people at pre-productive age (17 years and less) has been decreasing, and consequently the share of this group of people in the total number of inhabitants of the voivodeship has been decreasing. At the same time, the dependency ratio is constantly increasing. Hence the importance of social and health services aimed at the elderly is growing, however, there is an increase in private services with still limited access to public services in this area.
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	In relation to avoiding the exodus of young people and women from the territory and fighting against depopulation, the agents of the panel agreed that it was a first-rate need that had to occupy a prominent place in the prioritization ranking.

	5. Business, economy & innovation
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	Innovation and digitisation are two important pillars of the current strategic planning in rural areas to support rural economy, spatial development and participation of inhabitants. The rural economy offers opportunities for local employment and seeks innovation, also for existing agricultural and small businesses. The countryside is broadening its economic base through cooperation and openness to short-chain production networks, the circular economy and renewable energy Entrepreneurship and innovation are essential to achieve high-quality products with high(er) added value based on more sustainable production methods, healthy and new food products, agricultural/forest expansion, short and circular chain models, rural/urban agriculture and production for the biobased economy (food and materials).
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	The collaboration among research institutions, companies and municipalities is a key factor to boost local economy and development of innovative solutions. The active participation of inhabitants/citizens is also necessary. Better engagement of the public administration to research activities is needed.
SLOVAKIA	Need to regain self-sufficiency of agricultural and food production of a country once self-sufficient at over 90% that has become in recent three decades a country dependent on imports of food. Need to significantly increase the level of state aid for the agricultural sector as it is the lowest within the EU. Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises.
HAME/FINLAND	N12: Rural entrepreneurs and those considering starting a business need more information and access to business development services available in their municipalities and wider area. Business networks, partnerships and subcontracting need to be introduced as viable options. The effects of the corona crisis on new rural businesses (travel and hospitality businesses, experience industry etc.) will be significant and create new need for support and innovation. N14: Supply and demand in research and product development facilities (e.g laboratories) are mismatching N15: Especially in SME business
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Stakeholders mentioned lack of informative initiatives, regarding business activities, innovative actions, funding opportunities, CAP regulation. Furthermore, there is lack of well-structured agritourism businesses and promotion (marketing). Limited high skilled human resources and adequate background for adopting new technologies.
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	There is not enough available land in Monaghan, and there is a lot of insecurity in farming. There is limited credit and farming is an unreliable income. Younger people can make money easier in other ways and so are not choosing to farm. Credit and finance are expensive and limited. Loans require a good credit rating or collateral, like one's home. While Brexit may have a negative effect on job creation, sustainability and the farming economy, presently there is adequate employment in Monaghan. However, for many new entrants there is a lack of employment opportunities. There are several scheme jobs, but they do not provide lasting opportunities or lead to long term employment. There are not enough work placements and schemes do not work to their best ability. Farms in county Monaghan are relatively small in size and scale. This leads them to gravitate towards very traditional production types, beef production and dairy. Over a third of all suckler farms in the Border region are classified as vulnerable. Across Europe, farmers are starting to broaden their horizon on what a farm can produce. In countries like Germany and Sweden in particular, farmers with the support of EU funding and strong feed-in tariffs, are investing in biomass processing and gas and electricity production. Much more work needs to be done by policy makers to showcase the potential of such new farm opportunities. Feed-in tariffs for producers are effectively a green subsidy, designed to get such projects up and running and to remain viable over time. The investments made by governments helps them reach their environmental targets and not have to pay EU penalties. Entrepreneurship is strong in the county but needs continual support, especially those who find themselves unemployed and want to try out an idea for a business. With the economic impact of COVID-19 and the colossal rise in unemployment, their numbers will rise. Social Farming has massive potential, but many of the key players are reluctant to develop this area; there needs to be a more creative, multi-disciplinary approach in thinking about social farming. Social farming can be applied in many ways. It is particularly helpful for young offenders in England. In Co Mayo it has been used successfully to help asylum seekers integrate into the community offering shared learning potential. Social farming is non-threatening, and it is real life.
GALILEE/ISRAEL	All stakeholders agree that the level of innovation already exists in the Galilee academia and research institute is high but this is not (yet) enough for develop businesses and economic development
APULIA/ITALY	Given the increase in EU financial resources to support new start-ups and the green economy, it is essential to improve the link between investments and new activities in order to facilitate the birth of new green and innovative businesses.
VIDZEME/LATVIA	N24 Strengthening competitiveness of region, digitalization has very powerful possibilities, particularly in providing opportunities for telework (so people can be based elsewhere), providing services etc. * To start activities/businesses in sharing economy or innovations in rural regions takes a lot of courage as there is no proven data that it can work.
Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM	Poorly developed and diversified economic infrastructure and the consequent lack of quality jobs are common features of rural areas in the country - There is an underdeveloped SME sector in rural areas. - The efforts to promote entrepreneurship and crafts in rural areas are constrained by the poor educational status of the labour force and lack of professional experience. - Inadequate coordination of program and activities directed towards different economic sectors in rural areas - Employment opportunities in rural areas are limited and dominated by agriculture as an economic sector - There is a good potential for development of tourism in rural municipalities but it is still underdeveloped - Main characteristic of Macedonian agriculture is traditional extensive agriculture, which is main precondition for development of organic production. Although organic agricultural production in Republic of Macedonia is one of the fastest growing agribusiness sectors, there is a lack of organization, cooperation, it is necessary to create a policy or strategy

Mazowieckie/POLAND	<p>Mazowieckie Voivodeship is the most economically developed region of Poland. It is characterized by a high rate of economic growth and the highest share in the generation of the country's GDP among the voivodeships. The engine of Mazovian economy is Warsaw together with the metropolitan area, which plays a special role in building the competitiveness of the region. Territorial diversification of the level of economic development is best illustrated by the gross domestic product per capita. The Mazowieckie Voivodeship achieved the highest level of this indicator in Poland - in 2014-18 it exceeded the national average by 50-60%.</p> <p>Agriculture is still an important part of the rural development. A significant part of Mazowieckie voivodship is characterised by high and medium agricultural development potential determined, among others, by the level of potential of agricultural enterprises in communes, the occurrence and type of specialisation of agricultural production and the distribution of producer groups. In particular parts of the region agricultural specialisations have been developed. Meat and milk production dominates in the north and fruit and vegetable production in the middle and south.</p>
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	<p>Regarding economic diversification, the agents commented that it was necessary to define a well-defined territory marketing strategy, with adequately designed tourism products. In addition, the agents pointed out the importance of the agri-food industry as an alternative for economic diversification, promoting, for example, ecological productions. In addition, the agents of the panel confirmed the importance of promoting differentiated taxation compared to the urban environment.</p>

	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	Landscape is important for the qualitative development of the open space, also in relation to the built-up space and rural heritage . There is a perceived need to integrate landscape character into a broad cultural-historical evaluation and protect valuable landscape (elements). Landscape care must take into account spatial quality (integral approach), involve multiple sectors (integrated approach) and include multiple stakeholders (participatory approach).
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	It is highly recommended to support involvement of women into the research/academia sector.
SLOVAKIA	Need to change social thinking about employment in agriculture through targeted promotion. Need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions. Need to organize local social and cultural and artistic events and fairs, events for students, children, families and young generation. Need to promote access to the digitized heritage to the general public and business entities, taking into account the needs of disabled people. Need to motivate to use modern ways of presenting cultural heritage with the use of new technologies and progressive marketing methods. Need to involve local actors in commercial exploitation of cultural heritage. Need to support for cultural activities and creative industries with a view to strengthening the creation and distribution of cultural goods. Need to support the building of cultural infrastructure for the economic exploitation of creative activities linked to the tourism sector.
HAME/FINLAND	
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Actions for woman involvement in decision making are required
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	Loneliness and isolation are aggravated when people who are farming do not have the finances to spend on extra-curricular activities. Children often participate in the local rural GAA activities which are locally based and free. Farming families or single farmers are isolated due to the poor financial position of small farms and a lack of off farm employment. This is further aggravated due to a lack of public transportation. The men's sheds, community gardens and other community-based activities do have high participation precisely because they are local and if not free then are not expensive Social & Cultural impacts on the youth. They are left with nothing to do except local sports because of a lack of public transport. Integration of new entrants can be done in rural communities through sports, schools and church activities. The Volunteer and Community Sector is strong in county Monaghan but lacks a coordinated approach and a common sense of purpose. Groups are good at doing their own thing, but there is insufficient networking and sharing of ideas.
GALILEE/ISRAEL	No comments.
APULIA/ITALY	From a working point of view, a high female and youth unemployment rate emerges. For this reason, it is necessary to incentivize companies (for example through subsidies) to hire them or create the conditions for the creation of new businesses.
VIDZEME/LATVIA	* Empowerment of communities to implement long-term activities and vision is important in effective use of
NORTH MACEDONIA	the employment rate of rural women amounted to 34%, what is lower than the employment rate of men in rural areas (66%). rural woman faces various challenges in terms of gender equality in many areas such as: daily activities and households, receiving of incomes (in most cases the rural women occurs as unpaid workers), access to education, participation in decision making at the households level and employment representation in the decision making at local and national levels. Women and men of varying ethnic groupings have varying levels of socio-economic status, political participation, and access to resources, all of which affect their ability to cope with and respond to sustainable development challenges
Mazowieckie/POLAND	The cultural sector and the related tourism sector are not significant employment markets on a voivodeship scale. The ethnographic and cultural diversity of the voivodeship influences the weak sense of identity of its inhabitants. This results, among other things, from the complex history and distinct traditions of different parts of the region. The situation is intensified by the strong diversification of social and economic development within the voivodeship, as well as a very large number of inflowing population associated with the capital status of Warsaw.
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	The panel expressed as a necessity the importance of promoting volunteer policies among the population to develop services in an altruistic way where the private and public sectors have difficulty offering it.

	7. Environment & Biodiversity
FLANDERS/BELGIUM	With an innovative approach, rural villages want to encourage biodiversity and climate resilience through the maintenance and management of landscapes, landscape elements, blue-green connections and the associated partnerships: both with the usual actors (local authorities, regional landscapes, nature associations, farmers, private owners), but also with new actors and the rural inhabitants themselves. The actual strengthening and design of the open space requires more guidance and stimulating measures.
CENTRAL BOHEMIAN/CZR	The implementation of circular economy principles has a potential to create new job opportunities in the region.
SLOVAKIA	<p>Need to change the support in the agricultural area from per hectare basis on added value and environmental sustainability.</p> <p>Need to give more emphasis on domestic local production which is more sustainable and healthy respecting the local food traditions.</p> <p>Need to promote better waste management and using waste as a resource.</p> <p>Need to prevent devastation of forest and logging especially in national parks.</p> <p>Need to improve the management of water resources by promoting and creating conditions for capture and use of rainwater, supporting establishment of ponds etc.</p> <p>Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.</p> <p>Need for sustainable and planned urban and regional development, ensuring access to accessible mobility, energy, drinking water for environmental sustainability, adaptation to climate change, reducing pollution, protecting nature and biodiversity.</p>
HAME/FINLAND	
CENTRAL GREECE/GREECE	Link environmental technologies and energy saving technologies with agricultural production
MONAGHAN/IRELAND	<p>Opportunities in Cultivation Practices: There is a lack of horticulture. We do not produce a balanced human diet. EU agriculture policy needs to encourage greater levels of local food production, including horticulture. Like many other areas of agriculture for small to medium scale farmers, it lacks scale and not have the potential for sustainability. But for many smallholders with smaller parcels of land, it could represent an opportunity to diversify the agricultural product for the area, while at the same time reducing the air miles of the food we consume. But financial support would be required to kick start this sector.</p> <p>There may be potential for community shops in rural communities which are a marketplace for local farm produce and general groceries. Firstly, many rural people must travel long distances for shopping, which adds costs to living in a rural area. A shop acts as a key social hub in a rural area which can stimulate other activity. These can also be used as multi-service hubs.</p> <p>Opportunities in Forestry: This area needs a rethink. Smaller parcels of native woodland are more attractive to farmers. It provides natural shelter for animals and provides biodiversity for wildlife. The schemes are very restrictive. They are asking too much from many farmers. Timber companies are focused on short term economic gain. Native trees take longer to grow. They won't provide economic gain right away, but it helps the environment, even the smaller clusters.</p> <p>Alternative Energy Sources: There are no wind farms of any scale in County Monaghan. This is surprising given the drumlin nature of the county. Again, balance is needed, with sensitive selection of wind farm locations. The reality of alternative energy is that no one source will provide the solution, rather a mix of areas like biogas, green electricity, solar and wind will all need to play their part.</p> <p>There is also an opportunity in exploring rural village solar electricity grid projects (Smart Villages), using roof and shed tops as locations for photo-voltaic panels which are networked to a grid managed locally, which buy and sell locally produced electricity. This again requires policy blockages to be removed which allow greater access to sell onto the grid and indeed to development of private grids.</p> <p>Biomass can have many forms, but forestry is regarded as an important source. Rural communities must avoid been overcrowded by large scale forest plantation, instead opting for a reasonable balance. This needs close policy monitoring and control measures.</p>
GALILEE/ISRAEL	Many efforts are done to keep the Galilee's biodiversity and environmental conditions as high as possible, although economic development is threatening this high level. Efforts in controlling agricultural uses of pesticides and herbicides, as well as reducing the uses of chemical fertilisers are done.
APULIA/ITALY	Enhancing the territory with respect for the environment, flora and fauna are necessary to avoid a final pollution of the earth and water. It is, therefore, necessary to promote green activities and the protection of historical and natural heritage.
VIDZEME/LATVIA	<p>N28 All sectors should cooperate to develop support system, trainings, exchange of good practice and other activities to ensure taking action on adaption on climate change</p> <p>* Growing demand for bio products make it challenging to reshape the models of working, including new cooperation ties between farmers and producers, ensuring better costs options, common storages and logistic questions, adapting to marked needs..</p> <p>* Worrying, whether Covid's impact won't change EC priorities. It is argued that the climate may be relegated to revitalize the industry. Can we count on the same public funding? Many projects are already being suspended. There will also be increasing competition within the EU. Significant support for local producers, local distribution networks will be important, food self-sufficiency. Attention should be paid to local supplies in the region, thus less emphasis on imports.</p> <p>* Energy production is very important, which is the basis of jobs. * The role of agriculture in energy production and use is highly important</p> <p>* Ability to make decisions. Impact on the health system, public administration plays a major role in ensuring functions. Public sector intervention in various sectors. Without public intervention, successful development is not possible. Climate adaptation measures in the context of crisis management (floods, storms, etc.).</p>
Gevgelija-Strumica-FYROM	<p>In most of the rural populated areas, no collection and depositing of municipal solid waste is performed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites. - The condition of environment protection and management of the Southeast Planning Region is relatively good - The cultural heritage is located in the rural areas and has the biggest development potential considering the diversity and quality of cultural and historical treasures and archaeological sites in the country and the increasing interest in cultural tourism on the market
Mazowieckie/POLAND	<p>In Mazovia, as in the whole of Poland, cities have undergone an excessive territorial expansion, which results in disturbances of their internal structure. The area of Warsaw has more than tripled since 1939, and the number of inhabitants has increased by only 70%. The expansion of urbanisation areas both within the administrative boundaries of cities and in suburban rural communes is associated with the scattering of development and inefficient land management, as well as disturbance of spatial order and order in the region, generally referred to as the phenomenon of uncontrolled suburbanisation. This process generates excessive social costs and contributes to the degradation of the natural environment and landscape, thus wasting opportunities for sustainable development. As a result of chaotic development of buildings, caused, among other things, by the flawed legal regulations and the lack of local spatial development plans, energy consumption increases excessively and territorial self-government units' budgets are burdened with disproportionately high costs related to land development. As a result of the progressing changes, many centres are losing their functions. The quality of public space is deteriorating, which results in the deterioration of the inhabitants' quality of life and the value of property.</p> <p>Therefore, the policy related to the protection and shaping of public space is crucial.</p>
SEGOBRIGA/SPAIN	The panel confirmed the possibilities offered by the natural environment of the territory as a resource and attraction, to generate an economy related to sustainable tourism.

Annex 9 SWOT Indicators

Table 41. Flanders / BELGIUM SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services	Public services availability scored for whole Flanders via mobiscore	Score of accessibility of public services	Score from 1-10	2019	https://mobiscore.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/
2. Recreation / social activities	-Well developed bicycle routes in Flanders -GIS information of sport infrastructures in Flanders -vision statement on rural tourism and recreation	-	-	-	https://www.vlaanderen-fietsland.be/routeplanner http://www.geopunt.be/kaart https://www.toerismevlaanderen.be/sites/toerismevlaanderen.be/files/assets/documents_KENNIS/
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	-housing for elderly people -poverty in rural areas				https://www.vlaamse-ouderenraad.be/sites/default/files/downloads/2018-03/Vergrijzing%20op%20het%20platteland.pdf http://www.armoedebestrijding.be/publications/Pocico/eindrapport.pdf
4. Demographic & human capital	-crime -social and cultural diversification of population -migration				https://www.statistiekvlaanderen.be/nl/geregistreerde-criminaliteit-0 https://www.vlm.be/nl/SiteCollectionDocuments/platform%20plattelandsonderzoek/Onderzoeksagenda%202.0_uitgebreide%20versie%20-%20kopie%20naar%20PF.doc.pdf (p47) https://www.vlm.be/nl/SiteCollectionDocuments/Platteland/Plattelandsbeleidsplan/Bijlage1.pdf (p 11)
5. Business, economy & innovation	-economic activities in rural areas -overview of (economic) support given to farmers				https://www.vilt.be/twee-op-drie-bedrijven-op-platteland-is-niet-agrarisch https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/gr_201612_ndnqiii_vrn_21x21_digi_6_versie_11_januari_2017.pdf
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	-rural landscape as cultural heritage				https://www.dagvandelandbouw.be/deelnemers https://www.vlm.be/nl/SiteCollectionDocuments/platform%20plattelandsonderzoek/Onderzoeksagenda%202.0_uitgebreide%20versie%20-%20kopie%20naar%20PF.doc.pdf
7. Environment & Biodiversity	-GIS information on natural value of 'green areas' in Flanders -environmental measures farmers				https://www.geopunt.be/catalogus/applicationfolder/biologische-waarderingskaart https://lv.vlaanderen.be/nl/voorlichting-info/publicaties-cijfers/studies/beleid/wat-denkt-de-landbouwer-over-agromilieu-en

Table 42. Central Bohemian / CZECH REPUBLIC SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	Year	Source
1. Availability of public and other services	Related to the circular economy and bioeconomy	Production of municipal waste	Production of municipal waste in EU countries	2019	https://www.czso.cz/documents/10180/61508184/370002180106.pdf/fa16c1f3-fd9f-4e88-bb5a-a14a499c6f25?version=1.0
	Related to transport and infrastructure	Road accident	Number	2019	https://www.czso.cz/documents/10180/90635242/33011119q4o3.pdf/7cc29c86-c5e1-4fd0-861c-d591eb77a884?version=1.7
	Related to ICT and high-speed internet connection	Households with internet access	percentage of total households in the region	2011, 2014, 2017	https://www.czso.cz/csu/xs/vyzkum-vyvoj-a-informacni-technologie-ve-stredoceskem-kraji-v-roce-2017

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	Year	Source
2. Recreation / social activities	Related to tourism	Long and short trips of Czech residents by destination	Trips made (thous.)	2019	https://www.czso.cz/documents/10180/90635242/33011119q4n3.pdf/2718c3c8-7f47-4933-9456-314f8015058f?version=1.1
	Related to tourism, natural and cultural heritage	UNESCO	Natural and cultural heritage	2019	https://whc.unesco.org/en/statesparties/cz
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	Related to quality of life	Living conditions of Central Bohemian households	Average number of household members in total and by economic activity, household income, average monthly housing costs	2019	https://www.czso.cz/csu/xs/zivotni-podminky-stredoceskych-domacnosti-v-roce-2019
	Related to resilience and safe environment	Criminality	Registered offenses	2019	https://www.czso.cz/documents/10180/90635242/33011119q4o1.pdf/08dfdf73-c85d-4823-bda8-e3478051280d?version=1.7
4. Demographic & human capital	Related to the population of the region	Increase of population	population	2019	https://www.czso.cz/csu/czso/nejvyssi-prirustek-obyvatel-byl-ve-stredoceskem-kraji-a-v-praze
	Related to the unemployment rate	Share of unemployed persons	Unemployed	2020	https://www.czso.cz/csu/xs/podil-nezamestnaných-osob-2020-ve-stredoceskem-kraji
	Related to the migration	Migration saldo	Number of persons	2019	https://www.czso.cz/documents/10180/90635242/33011119q4d06.pdf/c66a14d5-646f-4a9e-98f5-30de2882473c?version=1.7
5. Business, economy & innovation	Related to R&D&I	Selected data on research and development	Number	2019	https://www.czso.cz/documents/10180/90635234/33011019.pdf/79644736-e3e2-4948-b0fd-4172bb1fc9b0?version=1.9
	Related to the innovation	Regional innovation scoreboard	-	2019	https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sites/growth/files/ris_full_map.png
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	Related to the organic farming	Organic farming	Number of companies	2017	https://www.czso.cz/csu/czso/cesko-vynika-v-ekologickem-zemedelstvi
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Related to quality of environment	Zpráva o stavu životního prostředí	-	2018	https://www.mzp.cz/C1257458002F0DC7/cz/zpravy_o_stavu_zivotniho_prostredi_publicace/\$FILE/OPZPUR-Zprava_ZP_CR_2018_20200207.pdf

Table 43. SLOVAKIA SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source
1. Availability of public and other services	Access to land is the main obstacle hindering the rural development in the country, especially in relation to young, small and family farmers, as well as potential new entrants.				School System and Education (statistics.sk) Health (statistics.sk)
2. Recreation / social activities	Support of creative tourism and agrotourism				Culture (statistics.sk) Tourism (statistics.sk)
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living					Quality of life indicators (statistics.sk) National Accounts (statistics.sk)
4. Demographic & human capital	Map or web application of producers.				Population and migration (statistics.sk)
5. Business, economy & innovation	<p>Establishment of start-up Food Incubators.</p> <p>Informal virtual platform comprising a database of local producers, manuals of support, manuals of standard, manuals for school and producers and catalogue of producers and seasonal and traditional products.</p> <p>Need to gather sufficient, categorized and sex-disaggregated data on local production for objective and evidence based decision making.</p>				Organizational statistics
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	<p>Establishment of cooperation among relevant stakeholders in the region with a special focus on women, youth and potential/or newcomers.</p> <p>Empowerment of the stakeholders in the region on rural attractiveness issues.</p> <p>Strengthen the importance and contribution of agriculture to the local, regional and national economy. Increase attractiveness of rural areas and rural professions.</p>				Indicator of gender equality (statistics.sk) Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries (statistics.sk)
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Sustainable agriculture and rural development are the key for the sustainable future of communities and countries.				Environment (statistics.sk)

Table 44. Häme / FINLAND SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services	<p>Education: Häme region offers good opportunities for education especially in fields of natural resources, environment and food processing (higher and professional education).</p> <p>Internet connections: According to recent statistics, fixed broadband and mobile network coverage are on the same level with national statistics. In Päijät-Häme region availability of high-speed internet connections is higher than national average.</p> <p>Public transportation: Availability of public transportation especially in rural areas has been recognised as weakness in regional development programmes. Also National Travel Survey 2016 supports this statement. Päijät-Häme county and Riihimäki region from Kanta-Häme county were involved in this study.</p>				<p>Vihreän kasvun Häme, 2013: https://www.doria.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/93521/Raportteja_106_2013_HAMELY.pdf?sequence=10&isAllowed=y</p> <p>"Traficom map service: https://eservices.traficom.fi/monitori/area, FiCom: https://www.ficom.fi/ict-ala/tilastot/laajakaistaliittymien-saatavuus Study of broadband coverage in Europe 2018: https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/study-broadband-coverage-europe-2018"</p> <p>National Travel Survey 2016. Finnish Transport Agency, Traffic and land use. Helsinki 2018. https://julkaisut.vayla.fi/pdf8/lti_2018-01_henkiloliikennetutkimus_2016_web.pdf</p>
2. Recreation / social activities	<p>In 2018 Häme region had 44295 summer cottages.</p> <p>Four sporting centres in Päijät-Häme, clean environment and water resources offer possibilities to wellness business.</p>				<p>Rakennukset ja kesämökit, Tilastokeskus: http://pxnet2.stat.fi/PXWeb/pxweb/fi/StatFin/StatFin_asu_rakke/statfin_rakke_pxt_116j.px/table/tableViewLayout1/ Päijät-Häme 2040 regional programme: http://www.paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/J2013_A207_Paijat-Hame_2040_maakuntasuunnitelma.pdf</p>
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	<p>Multi-locality is a growing trend in Finland. Urban rurality (citymaalaiset) facebook group and community is actively promoting multi-local lifestyle. Due to COVID19 crisis many people are working from home and staying at their summer cottages.</p>				<p>Citymaalaiset: https://medium.com/@citymaalaiset/citymaalaiset-ovat-t%C3%A4%C3%A4ll%C3%A4-72249e7fb117</p>
4. Demographic & human capital	<p>The demographic dependency ratio has raised in the whole region between 1997-2017 and is above national average.</p> <p>Population is decreasing especially in rural areas. Also dependency ratio is higher in sparsely populated rural areas.</p>				<p>Suomen virallinen tilasto (SVT): Väestörakenne [verkkajulkaisu]. Väestöllinen huoltosuhte maakunnittain 1997–2017. : http://www.stat.fi/til/vaerak/2017/vaerak_2017_2018-03-29_tau_003_fi.html</p> <p>Vihreän kasvun Häme, 2013: https://www.doria.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/93521/Raportteja_106_2013_HAMELY.pdf?sequence=10&isAllowed=y</p>
5. Business, economy & innovation	<p>In Kanta-Häme, the bioeconomy accounts for approximately 15% of the value added in the regional economy, i.e. approximately EUR 650 million.</p> <p>The agricultural sector of Kanta-Häme is characterised by extensive crop cultivation. The arable land used for cultivation in the province is about 104,000 ha, which is about 18% of the total area of the region.</p> <p>Bioeconomy and sustainable use of resources is one of the five strategic priorities of Kanta-Häme regional programme (Regional Council of Häme).</p> <p>Within recent years in Päijät-Häme, the Lahti region has become Finland's most important environmental business hub alongside the Helsinki metropolitan area. About 12% of the industry's turnover is in the region.</p>				<p>Häme programme 2018+, 2017: https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf The Circular Economy Roadmap for Kanta-Häme 2020: https://www.hamk.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Kanta-H%C3%A4meen-kiertotalouden-nykytilan-kuvaus.pdf</p> <p>Päijät-Häme 2040 regional programme, 2013: http://www.paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/J2013_A207_Paijat-Hame_2040_maakuntasuunnitelma.pdf</p>
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	<p>In 2017, there were about 11,900 foreign citizens living in Häme. Approximately 61% of the foreigners in the region are EU citizens. The number of foreign-language speakers exceeded 17,000 in 2017, accounting for about 4.6% of the population in the entire region. In Päijät-Häme, the highest concentration of immigrant population is found in Lahti, whereas in Kanta-Häme, the highest number is seen in Hämeenlinna.</p>				<p>Integration.fi webpage, maintained by the Centre of Expertise in Immigrant Integration at the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment. https://kotouttaminen.fi/hame</p>
7. Environment & Biodiversity	<p>Water resources: There are a total of 299 groundwater areas in the area of the Häme ELY Center, of which 133 are important for water supply (2020). The total area of groundwater areas is about 1,100 km², which is about 10% of the land area of Häme region. In Kanta-Häme there are 785 lakes and ponds and areal percentage of inland waters is 8,9 % . Päijät-Häme has 975 lakes and ponds and areal percentage of inland waters is 17,3 % .</p>				<p>Järviwiki 2020: https://www.jarviwiki.fi/wiki/Kanta-H%C3%A4meen_maakunta , https://www.jarviwiki.fi/wiki/P%C3%A4ij%C3%A4t-H%C3%A4meen_maakunta</p> <p>Joint website of Finland's environmental administration, ymparisto.fi: https://www.ymparisto.fi/fi-FI/Vesi/Vesiensuojelu/Pohjaveden_suojelu/Pohjavesialueet/Pohjavesialueet_Hame(28432)</p>

Table 45. Central Greece / GREECE SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source
1. Availability of public and other services	<p>The pilot area is located at the centre of the four biggest cities of Greece (Athens, Thessaloniki, Larisa, Patra) and has a strong transport infrastructure on the Athens-Thessaloniki axis, as it crosses the Patra-Athens-Thessaloniki-Evzoni (PATHE) international highway as well as the Athens-Thessaloniki International Railway, sections of the International European Network. The transport network is supported by low capacity ports and ferries, but with significant upgrading capabilities. The time to cover the distances from Athens Eleutherios Venizelos Airport and New Aghialos Airport is up to 1 to 3 hours.</p> <p>Although the proximity of these infrastructures (airports, ports, railways), there are limitations to access them by using public transportation (this is confirmed by the survey too (Q1.3). It also highlighted by the stakeholder panel, that several remote areas have old road network and due to the topography (e.g. mountains) the accessibility is difficult and time consuming. According to the panel the connections to the main city are enough, as it is confirmed also by the survey (Q1.2.), but intra-regional public transportation (including remote areas) is not enough (according to the survey, Q1.4)</p>	Transportation infrastructure	<p>The total funding (national and EU) allocated to Central Greece for Accessibility to Infrastructures and services:19,47%</p> <p>Number of ports:4</p> <p>Connection roads:5</p> <p>Distance from airports and ports: 1 to 3 hours</p>	2007-2013	<p>ris3:http://espa2007-2013.stereaellada.gr/fileadmin/pages/5h_programmatikh/RIS3/RIS3_review_report_Stereia_Ellada__final_edited_2012_.pdf</p> <p>"ROP Sterea Ellada 2007-2013</p> <p>http://www.thessalia-stereaellada-hpeiros.gr/el/Pages/FinalReport.aspx"</p> <p>https://www.enterprisegreece.gov.gr/images/public/pdf-files/synergassia/Synergassia_2016_Profile_Central_Greece.pdf</p>
	<p>The higher education level is relatively low, ranking the region third to last nationally. There are good schools (primary and second level) in the area (Q1.7), but there are not enough opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area (this is also confirmed by the survey, Q1.8.).</p>	Education services	<p>Tertiary education: only 17.3% of the population aged 25-64</p> <p>Life-long learning courses: 1.2% of adults aged 25-64</p> <p>Number of University faculties: 12</p> <p>Number of 1st Degree of Education structures:720</p> <p>Number of 2st Degree of Education structures:224</p>	2007-2013 2011 2020	<p>ris3:http://espa2007-2013.stereaellada.gr/fileadmin/pages/5h_programmatikh/RIS3/RIS3_review_report_Stereia_Ellada__final_edited_2012_.pdf</p> <p>Directorate of primary and secondary education of Sterea Ellada:</p> <p>http://stellad.pde.sch.gr/old/index.php?option=com_k2&view=itemlist&layout=category&task=category&id=3&Itemid=11</p> <p>http://stellad.pde.sch.gr/old/index.php?option=com_k2&view=itemlist&layout=category&task=category&id=4&Itemid=10</p>
	<p>There are good medical (primary care) services in the area according to the survey (Q1.6.), but this is not the case for day-care services (Q1.10). Healthcare services are beyond reach for several citizens living in remote or isolated mountainous locations (Q1.1).</p>	Health services	<p>Number of Hospitals: 10</p> <p>Number of Health Centres: 16 (Medical personnel: 132</p> <p>Nursing personnel: 135</p> <p>Medical equipment: 152)</p>	2016-2018	<p>1.https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/2ede26de-740f-44cf-8c45-d4a5d735f31c</p> <p>2.https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/a88e1780-7b5a-4bfb-9866-c1d8d41959f1</p>

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source
		Public administration, education, health and social work activities	Gross Value Added of public administration, education, health and social work activities: 1.130 million euro 15,3 % in total GVA of the Region	2013	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hellenic Statistical Authority data processed by Enterprise Greece https://www.enterprisegreece.gov.gr/images/public/pdf-files/synergassia/Synergassia_2016_Profile_Central_Greece.pdf https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SHE06/-
2. Recreation / social activities	There are important cultural treasures (famous archaeological sites), natural resources (thermal springs, Natura 2000 areas) and religious destinations. According to survey the area provides enough spaces for young people to meet (Q2.3.) and extra-curricular activities for children (Q2.4), as well as high quality commercial services (Q2.6). On the other hand, the recreational activities are not enough for young people (Q2.1, Q2.2.), although the area's great potentials.	Cultural and Natural Treasures	Arts, entertainment and recreation; other service activities; activities of household & extra-territorial organisations and bodies :3.52 % in total GVA of the Region Archaeological sites: 113 Museums: 69 Natura 2000 regions: 28 Blue flag awarded beaches: 21	2009-2013	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://espa2007-2013.stereaeellada.gr/fileadmin/pages/5h_programmatikh/RIS3/RIS3_review_report_Stereae_Ellada_final_edited_2012_.pdf https://www.enterprisegreece.gov.gr/images/public/pdf-files/synergassia/Synergassia_2016_Profile_Central_Greece.pdf
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	The living conditions are good and there are adequate housing opportunities in the area (Q3.1, Q3.3). According to stakeholders and the survey there are not serious problems with integration of some population (Q3.4)	Percentage of Unemployment	Immigrant population=555,960 Poverty (annual income below 6.622,40€): 17% of region's population Percentage distribution of offences committed:3.4% of total area of Greece	2016-2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/2995521/9746862/1-29042019-BP-EN.pdf/329a9132-20c0-485b-aa22-b34864c22fde https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/12044283/elstat_publication_young_2018_gr.pdf https://www.inegsee.gr/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/Enhmerwsi_Martios-Aprilios_2018.pdf https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/14479704/LivingConditionsInGreece_0519.pdf/e74da3b7-4d60-4c91-a59b-e73749c259ca
4. Demographic & human capital	According to the survey, the majority of participants believe that there are enough young people (Q1.1) in the area. On the other hand, the distribution of young people is not the same among the different districts of the area, as highlighted from the panel. Some districts of the total region face ageing and depopulation issues. The woman population is sufficient (Q4.2), but the babies born in the area are not enough (Q4.3).	Human capital Ageing Depopulation	Women population:49% of the region Young people (aged 0-39): 42,3% of the region (2018) Dependent indicator: 55,2 (meaning that for every 100 working people correspond 55.2 dependent people (children and old)) Replenishment indicator: 78.9 in 2010 (meaning for every 100 people deaths, only 80 births had happened) Urban population: 46% of the region's population (2018)	2018/ "RIS3 document last modification: 2015 2019" 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "RIS3 2014-2020: https://www.espa.gr/el/Pages/elibraryFS.aspx?item=2214 Greek statistics: https://www.statistics.gr/greece-in-figures https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/file_import/2019-european-semester-country-report-greece_en.pdf https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/12044283/elstat_publication_young_2018_en.pdf/4e9354b6-d953-4007-9215-16d50ea79158 https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/16uRfLJwHXhjtG2pWFTNpIEV49jKS-2BBuesArdE8/edit#gid=0

Comments		RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source
		Investment Opportunities in the Region	Crucial secondary sector for the regional economy, 35.7% of the Regional Gross Value Added. GDP of primary production in Central Greece was 7% 1) Export activity of Central Greece Region:a) Metals 45%, chemicals and plastic 21%, food products 12% and 7% machines and devices (year 2012).2) Processing of plant production products in CentralGreece was active by a total of 531 companies. Among them, dominant are the oil mills (34.5%), packaging of fruit and vegetables (17.7%) and wineries (15.8%). 3)Central Greece accounted for 11% of total fish and aquaculture production,13% of total meat production, 15,6% of total honey production. 4) in terms of occupation: 17.5 % was occupied in plant and animal production, 15.3% with commercial, 5.8% with structure and 5.1% with tourism	2016 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.enterprisegreece.gov.gr/images/public/pdf-files/synergassia/Synergassia_2016_Profile_Central_Greece.pdf http://stereaellada.gr/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Implementation-report_2014GR16M2OP007_2016_1_el-1.pdf https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/guides/blue_book/blueguide_el.pdf https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/file_import/2019-european-semester-country-report-greece_en.pdf
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	The majority of the survey participants agree that women and men equally participate in decision making and working life (Q6.1), but not enough opportunities for young people to participate in decision making (Q6.3). Furthermore, in the area do not exist lively communities and citizen-driven local activities (Q6.4).	Social	An overview of the social enterprise landscape in Greece (2019) state that: - Greek social enterprises are a 'woman-centred' sector - Women's agritourism cooperatives: 100 coops -women make up more than 60% of the total workforce in a large part of existing social enterprises.	2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/4041d3f9-6a29-11e9-9f05-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-96090958
7. Environment & Biodiversity	The survey's participants and the stakeholder panel agreed to the abundance of natural resources and the high diversity of the area.		Central Greece is well known for its reach cultural heritage and historical monuments: 1)The famous Archeological site of Delphi, 2)Thermopiles in Lamia, 3)The Byzantine monastery of Osios Loukas, in Viotia	2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.enterprisegreece.gov.gr/images/public/pdf-files/synergassia/Synergassia_2016_Profile_Central_Greece.pdf
		Landscape	Central Greece is one of the most mountainous areas of Greece, 22% of its land is flat, 19% hilly and 59% mountainous. A variety of lakes are located in its western part, the largest of which is Iliki (19,1sq.km.). A number of artificial lakes can also be found in the area, such as the ones in Kremasta, Acheloos and Mornos. The largest river in the area is Acheloos, whereas smaller ones are		

Comments		RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source
			Agrafiotis, Gorgopotamos, Pindos, Mornos, Sperchios etc. 13.3% of land of Central Region is covered by forest. Agricultural land in Central Greece increased and reached 7.38%		

Table 46. Monaghan / IRELAND SWOT Indicators

Monaghan Pilot	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS Definition	Value & units	year	source
1. Availability of public and other services	Actively promote rural Monaghan to attract new entrants to farming, in line with O1.01, O1.02, S1.01, S2.01, S3.01, S4.01, S5.01, S6.01, S7.01, while addressing W3.01, W3.02, W4.01, W5.01, W5.02, T3.02, T4.01, T5.01, T6.01, T7.02.	LEADER projects in county Monaghan	62 projects,	2020	MIDL "LEADER Delivering for County Monaghan" https://www.midl.ie/index.php/news/165-leader-delivery-county-monaghan
2. Recreation / social activities	Improve Broadband Access, ICT skills and sustainable tourism, in line with O2.01, S1.01, S3.01, S5.01, while addressing W2.01, W1.01, W1.02, T7.01.	Broadband coverage in county Monaghan. Number of related courses locally in Monaghan.	20,000 homes & businesses have broadband access. 400 broadband distribution nodes, or 5% of those in Ireland. 28 (number)	2020 2020	https://www.independent.ie/business/technology/broadband-now/irelands-rural-broadband-coverage-34763430.html , https://fiberrollout.ie/rural-ireland/deployment-by-county/monaghan/ and https://www.eir.ie/broadband/coverage-map/ Ballyhaise College, https://www.teagasc.ie/education/teagasc-colleges/ballyhaise/ and also https://monaghaninstitute.ie/courses/
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	Increase employment opportunities in rural Monaghan, building on O3.01, S3.01, O1.01, O2.01, O5.01, O6.01, O7.01, S4.01, S5.01, while addressing W3.01, T3.02, W5.01, W6.01, T4.01, T5.01, T7.02.	Employed in county Monaghan. Farmers in county Monaghan.	29,380 (61.9%) 4,544 (number)	2016 2014	https://monaghan.ie/communitydevelopment/monaghan-economic-community-monitor
4. Demographic & human capital	Provide support schemes to encourage new entrants and young people into farming, building on S4.01, O1.01, O1.02, O6.01, S3.01, S5.01, S6.01, S7.01, S7.02, while mitigating W4.01, T4.01, W3.01, W3.02, W5.01, W5.02, W6.01, T4.01, T5.01, T7.02,	Young farmers in county Monaghan. Number of new entrants to county Monaghan.	700 (number aged 18 to 44)) 903 (1.5%) population increase over 5 years.	2016 2016 from 2011	https://monaghan.ie/communitydevelopment/monaghan-economic-community-monitor and https://www.revenue.ie/en/corporate/information-about-revenue/statistics/other-datasets/farming-sector.aspx
5. Business, economy & innovation	Support farming diversification through access to finance and alternatives to purchasing land, in line with O5.01, S5.01, O1.01, O1.02, O3.01, S3.01, S4.01, S6.01, while alleviating W5.01, W5.02, T5.01, T5.02, W2.01, W3.01, W3.2, W4.01, T3.02, T4.01, T6.01, T7.02.	Annual farming incomes in Monaghan. Farm Partnerships in county Monaghan.	€22,926 which was 64.5% of Monaghan's average income of €35,477. 28 (number)	2017 2019	https://monaghan.ie/communitydevelopment/monaghan-economic-community-monitor and https://www.revenue.ie/en/corporate/information-about-revenue/statistics/other-datasets/farming-sector.aspx Farm Partnership Register, https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/farmingsectors/newfarmpartnershipregister/
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	Support the integration of new entrants into the farming and rural communities of county Monaghan, building on O6.01, S6.01, O5.01, O7.01, S3.01, S5.01, O1.02, S5.01, while addressing T6.01, T3.02.	Number of non-Nationals in county Monaghan. Number of new entrants to county Monaghan.	6,762 - 11.1% of Monaghan's population of 61,386 903 (1.5%) population increase over 5 years.	2016 2016 from 2011	https://monaghan.ie/communitydevelopment/monaghan-economic-community-monitor
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Encourage more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables and forestry development, exploiting S7.01, S7.02, O7.01, O1.01, O5.01, S6.01, S7.02, while lessening T7.01, T7.02, T5.01, T6.01.	Agriculture in Monaghan. Forestry in Monaghan.	103,511 ha which is 1.5% of the 6.9m ha farmed in Ireland. 89 ha which is 1.4% of Ireland's 6,500 ha afforestation	2016 2016	https://monaghan.ie/communitydevelopment/monaghan-economic-community-monitor https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/media/migration/forestry/forests-service-general-information/ForestStatisticsIreland2017090318.pdf

Table 47. Galilee / ISRAEL SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services	The Upper Galilee municipality is paying attention to elevate their public services to the citizens	transportation		2019	https://www.galil-elion.org.il/service_list https://www.galil-elion.org.il/%D7%AA%D7%97%D7%91%D7%95%D7%A8%D7%94-%D7%A6%D7%99%D7%91%D7%95%D7%A8%D7%99%D7%AA-%D7%91%D7%92%D7%9C%D7%99%D7%9C-%D7%94%D7%A2%D7%9C%D7%99%D7%95%D7%9F
2. Recreation / social activities	As a result of social activities in the region the prehistorical museum was developed	Social activities		2017	https://www.lonelyplanet.com/israel/attractions/upper-galilee-museum-of-prehistory/a/point-of-interest/1579595/1001862
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	Participants in the workshops emphasised their concern regarding standard of living in Galilee	Standard of living		2019	https://www.oecd.org/israel/44345452.pdf https://santandertrade.com/en/portal/establish-overseas/israel/living-in-the-country
4. Demographic & human capital	There is a change in the demographic human capacity in the Galilee, and more young people are immigrating to the region	Relocation of young people to the Galilee		2019	https://yozmotatid.org.il/en/negev-galil/
5. Business, economy & innovation	Since few industries are located in the Galilee there are less jobs and very few SMEs are developed	Business in the Galilee			https://www.oecd.org/education/imhe/49012157.pdf https://yozmotatid.org.il/en/negev-galil/ https://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/business/.premium-galilee-an-easy-target-since-flavius-time-1.5317182 https://www.israel21c.org/top-reasons-2019-was-a-record-breaking-year-for-israels-economy/ https://yozmotatid.org.il/en/negev-galil/
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Environmental aspects				https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14266979 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/226594936

Table 48. Apulia / ITALY SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	Year	Source
1. Availability of public and other services	The caress of public connections and telematic services emerge, but also a good school and university service.	Number of schools, number of universities, difficulties in connecting with public transport, Degree of use of e-procurement in the PA	3132, 6, 29.7%, 10%	2018, 2018, 2018, 2015	https://www.istat.it/
2. Recreation/social activities	There are enough recreational activities but not enough for the elderly and disabled.	Persons aged 65-74 who in the past 12 months have participated in meetings in cultural, recreational or other associations, Persons aged 14 and over who have carried out at least one social activity, with serious and less serious limitation	8,5%, 20,5% and 8,8%	015, medium of 2016-2017	https://www.istat.it/
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	There are good living conditions compared to other southern regions but there are some integration problems with some local populations and immigrants.	Incidence of poverty, Families by judgment on crime risk in the area where they live by region, percentage of foreigners perform low-skilled work with respect to qualifications and skills	11,8%, 2,7%, 29,9%	2018, 2018, 2014	https://www.istat.it/
4. Demographic & human capital	The questionnaire shows that it is possible to develop future family plans and that there are quite young and born. Literature shows us the opposite.	Birth rate, Unemployment rate, Structural dependency index, Marriage rate	7,1%, 14,9% 54,6%, 3,5%	2019, 2019, 2020, 2019	https://www.istat.it/
5. Business, economy & innovation	There is no awareness of the opportunities to create innovative and green businesses. There is an increase in funding in this regard but it is necessary to encourage the meeting between new companies and the available financing.	Innovation rate of the production system, green investment	28,1%, 1,437 million euros	2015, 2016	https://www.istat.it/
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	The questionnaire shows that there are enough opportunities for young people and women. Literature shows us the opposite.	Female unemployment rate, youth unemployment rate	18%, 43.6%	2019, 2018	https://www.istat.it/
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Both from the questionnaire and from the literature it emerges that the natural-historical and cultural landscapes are not lacking in the territory. The literature, however, underlines the lack of valorisation of the same.	Number of interregional or regional parks, number of marine protected areas, number of state reserves and number of regional protected areas	2, 3, 16, 18	2020	https://www.istat.it/

Table 49. Vidzeme / LATVIA SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services					
S1.04 Inhabitants feel safe and secure in the region.	In Vidzeme is the lowest share of households identifying of crime, violence or vandalism in the area among other regions; and about twice lower than in Latvia's rural areas (2.3%)	Share of crime, violence or vandalism in the area	Share is 1.0%	2019	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
W1.01 Insufficient provision of mobility & accessibility services, including transport and road infrastructures	In Vidzeme low quality of roads				
	In Latvia's rural regions are low population density, which makes it difficult to sustain adequate public transport services. In Vidzeme the density of population is the lowest in country.	Latvia has quite low relative to other European countries. Vidzeme region's population density is very low, almost three times lower than in Latvia.	34.3 inhab./km ² 13.24 inhab./km ²	2019 2018	https://ruralsharedmobility.eu/insight-papers/latvia/ http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/SUPER/SUPER-InterregEurope-pasnovertejums-ekoninovacijuatbalsta-sistema-self-assesment-VPR-ecoinnovations_2018.pdf
	However, on Vidzeme region level it is planned that the demand for local public transport services in rural areas will decrease, 50% of all inhabitants affirm that public transport is very important.	Inhabitants 18-25	79% affirm importance of public transport	2017 2020	http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/TENTacle/Vidzeme_regional_mobility_investment_plan_2030_Latvian_language.pdf Results of PoliRural survey
W1.03 Weak teleworking opportunities via shortcomings with ITC equipment; lack of appropriate digital skills, as well as lack of internet connectivity in some remote rural areas	The second lowest share of individuals, which used a laptop, notebook, etc., to access the internet away from home or work, among EU MS	Individuals used a laptop, etc., to access the internet away from home or work	Share of rural residents is 14%	2019	https://digital-agenda-data.eu/
	In Vidzeme is the second lowest share of access to the Internet by households among other regions.	Access to the Internet by households at the beginning of the year	83.3% of total population in region	2019	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/zin
	In Vidzeme is the second lowest share of Internet usage by individuals among other regions	Internet usage by individuals at the beginning of the year	80.5% of total population within region	2019	
	In Vidzeme is the highest share of individuals who have security incidents among other Latvia's regions in all activities, except the latest. In this position Vidzeme is on second position.	Individuals who experienced security related incidents through using the Internet	% of Internet users: - fraudulent credit or debit card use – 1.4%; - loss of documents, pictures or other data due to a	2019	

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
			virus or other infection; – 2.1%; - misuse of personal information available on the internet resulting in, e.g. discrimination, harassment, bullying – 1.7%; - social network or email account being hacked and content being posted or sent without knowledge – 2.8%.		
	In Latvia the share of individuals with above basic level of digital skills are lower than in other EU MS, particularly in rural areas	Share of individuals with above basic level of digital skills	Share of individuals living in: - urban areas is 29.3%; -living in towns and suburban areas is 26.7%; -living in rural areas is 17.2%	2019	https://digital-agenda-data.eu/
S1.03 There are adequate public provision of online e-health, e- day-care and/or elearning services (survey)/ W1.03 Insufficient and weak digital skills	In Vidzeme is: - the second lowest share among other regions of obtaining information from web sites and downloading official forms; - the lowest share of submitting completed forms; - the highest share of not used for contacting or interacting with public authorities or public services	Contacting or interacting with public authorities or public services over the Internet by individuals for private purposes	Obtaining information from web sites - 50.9%; Downloading official forms - 12.9%; Submitting completed forms – 44.3%	2019	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/zin
2. Recreation / social activities					
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living					

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
W3.01 Lack of housing opportunities (i.e., limited & expensive), esp., for new entrants and young generation	In Vidzeme is the lowest scale among other regions of satisfaction with accommodation	Satisfaction with accommodation, average in scale from 0 to 10	The satisfaction scale is 6.2	2013	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
	Housing expenditure as % of disposable income in Vidzeme is the highest among all regions, as well as higher by 0.6 per cent points comparing with an average of all Latvia's households; In Latvia's urban areas the share (12.6%) is higher than in rural areas (11.4%).	Housing expenditure as % of disposable income	Share of disposable income – 12.8%	2019	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
	In Vidzeme dwellings supply in percent with cold water (water pipe), hot water, sewerage have the second lowest rate among other regions, but supply with town gas and natural gas is the lowest among regions, which is about 2 times lower than in other regions.	Dwelling supply with different amenities (%)	Cold water supply (water pipe) - 87.6%; hot water supply - 74.2%; sewerage - 82.2%; town gas and natural gas - 15.2%	2019	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
	In Vidzeme the share of households identifying several problems regarding noise is the third highest, but share regarding pollution is the second highest among regions.	Noise from neighbours flats, stairway, industrial enterprises or street Pollution, grime and/or other environmental problems in the area	Share of households – 9.8% Share of households – 16.1%	2019	
W3.03 Low income level per household	Households' disposable income in Vidzeme per household member per month is the second lowest among regions. Latvia's average - 505.84 EUR/month.	Households' disposable income per household member	430.99 EUR/month	2018	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
	The share of persons under minimum income level in Vidzeme is the second highest among other regions, and of 3.7 per cent points higher than Latvia's average.	The share of persons under minimum income level	Share of persons is 11.6%	2018	
W3.04 High risk of poverty	Average at-risk-of-poverty rate is second highest in Vidzeme among regions, but in age group 65+ - the highest rate	At-risk-of-poverty rate	Average rate is 34.6% In age group 65+ - 62.1%	2018	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
4. Demographic & human capital					
W4.01 Not enough babies born or low births rate	Crude births rate in Vidzeme (8.92) is lower than in Pierīga region (11.9) and Latvia (average) (10.0), but higher than in Zemgale and Latgale. Decrease of Vidzeme ratio from 2014 was -0.6 points. The highest negative balance of population per 1000 inhabitant: -14.13 among regions	The ratio of the number of live births to the average number of population, expressed per 1000 people.	Crude birth rate per 1000 people is 9.8	2018	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala https://raim.gov.lv/raim_resursi
W4.03 Not enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly).	Activity rate and employment rate in Vidzeme is the second lowest among other regions; but unemployment rate is the second highest among other regions	Population (15-74) by labour status and statistical region	Activity rate 66.3%	2019	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
			Employment rate 61.1%		
			Unemployment rate 5.2%		
In Vidzeme changes from 2011 until 2019 in the share of population are following: (i) under working age increases; (ii) of working age decreases, which is less than in changes in other regions (average); and (iii) over working age increases, which is lower than in average changes of other regions. In Latvia changes from 2011 until 2019 of population share: (i) under working age is 1.7 per cent points; (ii) of working age - 2.9 per cent points; and (iii) over working age - 1.2 per cent points, which is lower than in average changes of other regions.	The share of population: - under working age	Increases by 1.0 per cent point	2019/2011	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/iedz/	
	- of population working age;	decreases by -2.3 per cent points			
	-of population over working age	increases by 1.3 per cent points			
W4.05 Some imbalance of gender in Vidzeme households	In Vidzeme households in age group 16-24 and 25-49 males' ratio is higher than females, but in an age group 50-64 and over 65 age the ratio of females is higher than males ratio	Structure of households by household members age and gender	Age group: - 16-24, males ratio is 9.1%; females – 6.3%; - 25-49 males ratio is 32.1%; females – 24.8%; - 50-64 males ratio is 23.4%; females – 23.7%; - over 65 males ratio is 20.1%; females – 28.2%.	2019	https://www.csb.gov.lv/en/statistics/statistics-by-theme/social-conditions/households

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
W4.06 Weak level of education	In Vidzeme the share of active population: with higher education is third lower among regions, and lower than Latvia's average – 31%, share with general secondary education is lowest among regions, but share with basic education or less than basic education is third highest.	Share of population with higher education, general secondary education and basic education or less than basic education	Share with: - higher education is 29.1%; - general secondary education is 21.9%; - basic education or less than basic education is 10.5%	2019	https://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
	The content of vocational and higher education does not correspond to the development trends and needs of the bioeconomy.			2018	http://www.vidzeme.lv/lv/regionalie_petijumi/50/132513/
5. Business, economy & innovation					
W5.02 Development of region's territories is very diverse among municipalities	Index of Territorial Development (TDI) ⁸ level is negative, but higher than in other regions. TDI diversity is high among region's municipalities, from 0.462 in Cesis to -0.695 in Strencu municipality.		TDI - -0.214	2018	https://raim.gov.lv/raim_resursi
W5.04 Weak implementation of digital technologies in business	Business digitisation and e-commerce is low in Latvia Lagging behind in the adoption of e-business technologies, majority of businesses (over 55%) having simple website & few computers; low investments in digital technologies; less than 1.5% of Latvia's enterprises use 3D printing services	e-Commerce index	3 rd lowest among EU MS	2019	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/integration-digital-technology
		Business digitisation index	5 th lowest among EU MS		
		Digital Intensity Index 2018 (% of enterprises by level)	Very low index value - 0-3; highest - 12		
W5.05 Insufficient participation in adult education	The share of participation in adult education in Vidzeme was the lowest	Participation in adult formal and/or non-formal education by regions in per cent	Formal and non-formal - 8.2%; formal - 7.8%; non-formal - 8.3%	2016	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala
W5.10 Insufficient support for innovation or technology transfer & no support for eco-innovation.	Vidzeme region has very few support instruments for innovation or technology transfer and internationalization, and practically no support for eco-innovation.	Business digitisation index		2018	http://www.vidzeme.lv/lv/regionalie_petijumi/50/132513/

⁸ A territory development index (TDI) is a generalised indicator, which is calculated with determined weight coefficients by summing up standardised values of the most important basic indicators of statistics which characterise the development. It demonstrates higher or lower development of the territories from the average social economic development level of the state in the relevant year.

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS				
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)	
W5.15 Sectors, which is indicated strong and as priority have comparatively low share of value added	Lowest share of value added of all regions	Digital Intensity Index 2018 (% of enterprises by level)	6.33%	2017	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/ekfin/	
	Share of value added (per cents) by kind of economic activity, which has highest value added or are indicated as priorities, in Vidzeme	(A) Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	20.93%	2017	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/ekfin/	
		(B) Mining and quarrying	16.17%			
		(C) Manufacturing	9.78%			
		(I) Accommodation & food service activities	3.76%			
		(J) Information & communication	1.56%	2015		http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONA_ILGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf
		(M) Professional, scientific and technical activities	2.80%			
		(P) Education	9.21%			
(R) Arts, entertainment and recreation	5.71%					
W5.16 Comparatively low salaries & wages in higher value added or priority sectors of economic activity	In Vidzeme the average monthly gross wages & salaries is second lowest of the average in all regions. The average salary & wages as per cents of Latvia's average in economic activities, which has highest value added or are indicated as priorities in Vidzeme	the average salary & wages	80%	2019	http://data1.csb.gov.lv/pxweb/en/sociala/	
		(A) Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	80%			
		(C) Manufacturing	93%			
		(10) Manufacture of food products	96%			
		(16) Manufacture of wood and of products of wood	84%			
		(31) Manufacture of furniture	90%			
		(I) Accommodation and food service activities	80%			
		(J) Information and communication	57%			
		(P) Education	90%			
		(Q) Human health and social work activities	90%			
		(M) Professional, scientific and technical activities	70%			
(R) Arts, entertainment and recreation	76%					

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
7. Environment & Biodiversity					
S7.01 Open landscapes & beautiful diverse natural areas	928 applications were received for the Latvian landscape treasure trove, of which 333 were from Vidzeme.			2017	https://ainavudargumi.lv/saraksts/?section=3
S7.02 High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised	There are 188 specially protected nature territories and natural monuments in Vidzeme region (632 in Latvia), which together occupy 29.9% of the total area of specially protected nature territories. 87 out of 336 Natura 2000 sites in Latvia are located in Vidzeme region.			2015	http://www.vidzeme.lv/lv/regiona_attistibas_planosanas_dokumenti
W7.02 Low generated value added from recreation activities	The potential of biological resources for the development of nature-based services is underused			2020	jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/RDI2CLUB/VPR_Bioekonomikas-Ricibplans-2020.pdf
W7.03 Biological resources are mainly used for the production of low value-added goods				2020	jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/RDI2CLUB/VPR_Bioekonomikas-Ricibplans-2020.pdf

Table 50. Gevgelija-Strumica / FYROM SWOT Indicators

1. Availability of public and other services	
Comment	<p>There are sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises, schools, universities)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipalities have significant problems to maintain the quality and access to basic services in small settlements. Given the small size of the population the access to basic services of the population in small settlements is highly dependent on the quality and accessibility of the road infrastructure. - The provision of high schools is in the municipal headquarters and the pupils from villages depend on regular transport or lodging in the public internats if available. - As one of the measures to improve the literacy is the mandatory secondary education introduced in 2008. The Government is also subsidizing the costs for schooling in terms of provision of free books and educational material for all pupils, IT equipment and internet connections of schools and free transportation of the pupils in the rural area - The infrastructure of roads, water supply, sewerage and electricity is also seriously inadequate in many areas
Definition	<i>Comment: This is left out because we think that a definition for each indicator should be universal for all panels.</i>
Values	- The National Rural Development Program provides a measure of co-financing of local roads with a maximum length of 2 km which will contribute to linking rural settlements in order to develop all rural activities
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (Koteski et al., 2017)
Comment	<p>There are good medical (primary care) services in your village /region</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concerning the health infrastructure, The Ministry of Health does additional efforts to develop system for the primary health care network and bringing health care system to the population in order to accomplish policy for accessibility of health care. For this purpose 16 new health care facilities are built in rural areas and it is expected between 35-40 thousand people to receive services in primary health care. However, access to medication supply and pharmaceutical stores is limited in rural areas and is considered as problem by the rural dwellers
Definition	
Values	- 16 new health care facilities are built in rural areas and it is expected between 35-40 thousand people to receive services in primary health care
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
Comment	<p>There are good schools (primary and second level) in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In addition, the investments in refurbishment and modernization of primary and secondary schools were increased resulting in around 200 schools being refurbished and modernized in the rural areas including modernization and equipping the sports halls or building new sports halls for the schools which previously did not had such facilities. ... Accessibility to primary schools is somewhat satisfactory for children from rural areas, in terms of secondary education; distance negatively affects access to education
Definition	
Values	- 200 schools being refurbished and modernized in the rural areas
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
Comment	<p>There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As to promote the higher education of the rural youth, the Government introduced dispersed high education studies by which all the faculties are obliged to organize their classes outside Skopje (so called 'dispersed studies'). Two additional Universities were established in Stip, University "Goce Delcev" and in Ohrid - University "St. Apostol Pavle".
Definition	
Values	- Two additional Universities were established in Stip, University "Goce Delcev" and in Ohrid - University "St. Apostol Pavle"
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
Comment	<p>There are good daycare facilities in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All rural municipalities have elementary schools, but lack of pre-school facilities i.e. day care for children and kindergartens - There are almost no investments for construction of retirement homes and centers for early child development
Definition	

Values	- Poor, average and satisfying daycare facilities in the area
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
Comment	<p>There is a good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G/fiber)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The telephone network (fixed line and GSM) is covering the entire territory of the state, while the Internet is increasingly used. The spread of the Internet has incredible growth in recent years from 1,5% in 2000 to 58,3% of households in 2012. National and local television, including cable and satellite, and radio are available throughout the country
Definition	
Values	- The spread of the Internet has incredible growth in recent years from 1,5% in 2000 to 58,3% of households in 2012
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
2. Recreation / social activities	
Comment	<p>I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For those who live in rural areas, the problem of access to banking services face 36 %, access to postal services 24% and access to cultural facilities 20%.
Definition	
Values	- For those who live in rural areas, 20% face the problem of access to cultural facilities.
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017)
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	
Comment	<p>I am proud of living in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People living in rural areas are less satisfied with the quality of life than those living in urban areas, which have been a magnet for the migration of young people from the countryside, leaving behind a more vulnerable and poorer population in the villages. Therefore there is a need for rural development policies to increase investment in infrastructure to make the villages once again attractive places for young people and entrepreneurs to live and work - Living conditions in villages and rural areas (except in tourist areas) are seen as less attractive than in urban areas. This is an additional factor pushing young and educated people not only away from agriculture, but also from rural areas ... Apart from rural tourist resorts, which of varying importance in each of the countries, rural areas are less attractive due to less developed infrastructure and fewer employment and income opportunities
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low level of satisfaction for quality of life in rural areas - Low level of attractiveness to live in rural areas compared to living in urban areas
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (Swinnen et al., 2013)
Comment	<p>Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are high</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Southeast Planning Region has no systematic regulation of wastewater to a large degree. Even though a large number of sewage systems are under construction in rural populated areas, households therein use septic tank systems to a great extent. This system does not include treatment, so there is no methane treatment. - Industrial water treatment in the Southeast Planning Region is especially important if taking into account that there are a great number of micro producers and furniture manufacturers functioning here, i.e. wood industry, wine producers and can industry, which belong to the group of large polluters. In spite of the mandatory industrial water treatment, it is not of the required quality so as to reduce the negative impact on waters and soil - In the Southeast Planning Region the sector of agriculture is at the same time the second biggest producer of solid waste (animal and plant) after the mining sector. By applying good agricultural practice, the Southeast region may drastically change its image when it comes to pollution. This is as a result of the possibility to use animal and plant tissues, which are by-products, in the process of creation and exploitation of renewable energy. Unfortunately, the region does not pay enough attention to creating facilities which would treat and deposit such waste - The Southeast region has a good climate potential for the development of agriculture. The large number of sunny days offers excellent conditions for the development of gardening, fruit growing and vine growing. The climate conditions are also favourable for usage of renewable sources of energy in the direction of providing energy for the agricultural sector. The analysis shows that there are ongoing initiatives in the region for setting up such installations such as solar and photovoltaic systems in some of the commercial capacities, and that there is a basic gasification network which needs to be further developed - Most of the smaller settlements in the Southeast Planning Region (e.g. villages in rural areas) do not have any sewage system and septic tanks or uncontrolled discharge of wastewater is used. The share of rural population with public sewage is small and is estimated at 17,7% of total population. The total population in rural areas with no installation for waste water disposal is 8,9% (4% of total population)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Around 60% - 70% of the population in the Southeast Planning Region is benefiting from the public system for collecting waste performed by public enterprises, but only 10% of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste. General practice is collection of non-separated communal and non-hazardous industrial waste as well as non-hazardous and hazardous non-separated waste fractions - The power supply is available to 99,75% of the population in rural areas and is made possible by a well developed transmission and distribution network with sufficient capacity electrical energy sources (1 430 MW) which provide a regular supply. Electricity network in dwellings in rural areas is not modernized to withstand regular uninterrupted supply of energy to domestic devices
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Around 60% - 70% of the population in the Southeast Planning Region is benefiting from the public system for collecting waste performed by public enterprises, but only 10% of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste. - The power supply is available to 99,75% of the population in rural areas and is made possible by a well developed transmission and distribution network with sufficient capacity electrical energy sources (1 430 MW) which provide a regular supply.
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
4. Demographic & human capital	
Comment	<p>There are enough young people in the area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The primary producers in rural areas possess low adaptation capacity due to financial and know how limitations. The intensive migration of the young rural population, the low access to services and the social exclusion are another set of challenges and constraints - In the last thirty years, the country faces severe 'aging population syndrome'. From 1981 to 2012, the number of young people (0 to 19 years) declined from 41% to 23,9% in the total population, while population aged 65 and above increased from 8% to 12% (still lower than EU 27 average of 17,9 %). The rural areas have problems in retaining the young population. Unsatisfactory rural age structure is particularly found in the Pelagonija (14,9%), East (13,2%), Vardar (13,1%), Southeast (12,4%) and Skopje (12, 6%) regions - One of the major problems in the country's agricultural sector is the aging of the labour force. Only about 10% of the employed in agriculture are young (from 15-24 of age). Low incomes and unfavourable working conditions in agriculture, as well as deteriorating living conditions in rural areas discourage young people to start a career in agriculture. Young people are more mobile and less emotionally related to the land and country-side. According to AFSARD data, only 13,5% of the total number of agricultural holdings who applied for financial support in 2013 are managed/represented by young farmers aged between 18 and 40 years of age - The problems generate disparities in the human resources capacities, mostly in entrepreneurship, lower living standard and availability of services as well as a tendency of migration of the young population abroad. Migration in the rural areas is a serious threat which together with the migration of the professional and young working force poses a serious challenge for the development of the sector and the region (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - Unfavourable age and gender structure of rural population (18,9% of population in rural areas is older than 60 – women, and 65 years – men); (Grozdanic, 2013)
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From 1981 to 2012, the number of young people (0 to 19 years) declined from 41% to 23,9% in the total population, while population aged 65 and above increased from 8% to 12% (still lower than EU 27 average of 17,9 %). - Only about 10% of the employed in agriculture are young (from 15-24 of age) - only 13,5% of the total number of agricultural holdings who applied for financial support in 2013 are managed/represented by young farmers aged between 18 and 40 years of age - Unfavourable age and gender structure of rural population (18,9% of population in rural areas is older than 60 – women, and 65 years – men)
Source	(Cukaliev et al., 2018); (EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (Grozdanic, 2013)
Comment	<p>There are enough women in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the total population size, the number of male population is higher. However, the difference between men and women is minimal and has no influence on the demographic imbalance (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - Unfavourable age and gender structure of rural population (18,9% of population in rural areas is older than 60 – women, and 65 years – men)
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unfavourable age and gender structure of rural population (18,9% of population in rural areas is older than 60 – women, and 65 years – men)
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (Grozdanic, 2013)
Comment	<p>There are enough babies born in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (Southeast region): The total fertility rate in the region in 2013 amounted to 1,38 and it provides for renewal of population on the level of simple reproduction ... The natural population increase as a difference between the number of live births and the number of deaths, as well as the number of concluded and divorced marriages over the analysed period (2009 – 2013) shows a trend of stagnation in the region. This situation in the future will actually influence the dynamics of the economic and the overall development of the region. The region maintains its level of simple reproduction, but if the trend goes on, it will additionally condition the need for an increase in human and financial resources in the social and health care field, which would mean an additional encumbrance of institutions and the real sector
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The total fertility rate in the region in 2013 amounted to 1,38 and it provides for renewal of population on the level of simple reproduction
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014)
Comment	Our community and voluntary sectors are well developed and address the social needs of our region and create opportunities.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rural Development Network, which aims to mobilise rural communities as agents of local development and as participants in rural policy. It has 58 NGOs in membership; and works closely with about 1,500 rural leaders. The membership is very diverse, including associations which represent farmers, rural women, craftsmen, rural tourism workers, environmentalists, etc. The Network's aim is to mobilise rural communities to act as agents of local development and to participate in rural policy at local, regional, national and EU level
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rural Development Network aims to mobilise rural communities as agents of local development and as participants in rural policy. It has 58 NGOs in membership; and works closely with about 1,500 rural leaders
Source	(Empowering rural stakeholders in the Western Balkans, n.d.)
Comment	<p>The demographic structure of the working population is in accordance with the needs of businesses in the rural area, including agribusiness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People aged 20-60 years of age have the largest share in the total population. On the other hand, the mechanical brain drain of registered persons having left the region is insignificant, which does not significantly contribute to a decrease or an increase in the population size (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - What is important to be mentioned is the trend of stagnation in population increase, the quite high trend of population activity, the highest employment rate and lowest unemployment rate compared to other regions (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - Lack of seasonal labour, increased ageing and outmigration of the rural population, and a low level of education and management skills among the rural population. Moreover, the lack of own capital and access to financial resources, weak level of agro-food integration, and low level of integration of research in the development of agriculture limit the development of the sector
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People aged 20-60 years of age have the largest share in the total population.
Source	(Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017); (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (Bajramović et al., 2016)
Comment	<p>The education structure of the working population is in accordance with the needs of businesses in the rural area, including agribusiness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low rate of enrolled pupils in primary education of 7,8; Low rate of enrolled students in secondary education of 7,4; A quite low rate of enrolled and graduated students. The lowest number of graduated students 661 (year of 2013) (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014). - Considerable share (13,4%) of rural population above age of 15 has insufficient or total lack of education, 2,6% are illiterate and 10,9% have not completed primary education. Illiteracy is higher among women (4,5%) than among men (1,3%) and it is particularly worrisome among the female adult population as there are more than three times as many adult illiterate women as there are illiterate men. The educational problem is obvious among the unemployed, since only 16% of them have higher or university education, the majority (55%) has secondary education, and the remaining 29% are unqualified
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Considerable share (13,4%) of rural population above age of 15 has insufficient or total lack of education, 2,6% are illiterate and 10,9% have not completed primary education - The educational problem is obvious among the unemployed, since only 16% of them have higher or university education, the majority (55%) has secondary education, and the remaining 29% are unqualified
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017)
5. Business, economy & innovation	
Comment	<p>The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses, including agribusiness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generally, rural areas have certain problems about attractiveness to businesses for several reasons: lack of concentration of population, poorer educational levels, lesser flexibility of the potential workforce, and distances from potential markets (for both inputs and outputs), all putting businesses in rural areas at a cost disadvantage. Poorly developed and diversified economic infrastructure and the consequent lack of quality jobs are common features of rural areas in the country. These are also the main causes of development lag typical of these areas which need to play a role like a rural development poles (Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017)
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poor supporting environment for new businesses and startups
Source	(Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017)
Comment	<p>There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On the borrower's side, both farmers and rural entrepreneurs have generally low educational level, limited knowledge of commercial crediting (interests rates, repayment schedule, grace period, collateral etc.) and prefer to borrow informally..... Yet access to credit remains a significant problem for small and medium-sized agricultural producers and rural entrepreneurs, which limits their investment and reduces demand for grant support - Investments in agriculture are less attractive for banks due to lower profitability of investments, collateral problems, and so on. Substantial changes in rural capital markets are less likely during economic recession and financial constraints. The EU pre-enlargement support can partly overcome some financial constraints in rural areas for profitable businesses

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ACDF credit line is especially targeted to agribusiness, i.e. individual farmers, rural households, agricultural, agro-processing and agro-export SMEs as well as European Instrument for Pre-Accession Rural Development Program (IPARD) beneficiaries. It refines a range of credit products defined in three major categories: a) primary production loans (up to EUR 100,000) for investments in primary agricultural production - viticulture, horticulture, floriculture, livestock; b) agro-processing loans (up to EUR 300,000) for investments in agro-processing industry - dairies, mills, wineries, fruit, vegetables and meat processing capacities and c) agro-export loans (up to EUR 300,000) for expanding in agro-exports. - The Rural credit programs have been very successful, showing that there is a need to favour the expansion of the rural credit, and to combine advisory services (business plan preparation, etc.) to applicants and to the lending institutions (banks) in loan processing - Growth of rural bank branches and an increase in bank understanding of rural finance - presence of dynamic entrepreneurs; the first steps into cooperation in farming and in the food chain; the opportunities offered by heritage and tourism; very low take-up of IPA Rural Development (IPARD) funds - Access to credit and finance should be improved. The Government and the European Commission, when shaping the IPARD 2 programme, should analyse the reasons for low take-up of IPARD 1 and make changes accordingly. There is widespread need for advisory services, training and other aspects of capacity-building: leadership in this field should come from the Government, the Rural Development Network, municipalities and Local Action Groups.
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ACDF credit line is especially targeted to agribusiness, i.e. individual farmers, rural households, agricultural, agro-processing and agro-export SMEs as well as European Instrument for Pre-Accession Rural Development Program (IPARD) beneficiaries. It refines a range of credit products defined in three major categories: a) primary production loans (up to EUR 100,000) for investments in primary agricultural production - viticulture, horticulture, floriculture, livestock; b) agro-processing loans (up to EUR 300,000) for investments in agro-processing industry - dairies, mills, wineries, fruit, vegetables and meat processing capacities and c) agro-export loans (up to EUR 300,000) for expanding in agro-exports.
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015) ; (Swinnen et al., 2013); (Kovachev, 2014); (Hadzi Naumova-Mihajlovska, 2017); (Empowering rural stakeholders in the Western Balkans, n.d.)
Comment	<p>There are adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development with the provision of experienced services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is an underdeveloped SME sector in rural areas. The business demography indicators (number of business entities per 1 000 inhabitants) indicates that SME density in predominantly rural regions is less than the national average (32 per 1 000 inhabitants) while the SME density is relatively high in the intermediate regions (45 per 1 000 inhabitants), reaching the EU 27 average of 45 per 1 000 inhabitants. As per LAU 1 level, the average number of businesses per thousand inhabitants in rural municipalities (municipalities with headquarter in village) is 18 compared to average of 36 in urban municipalities (with headquarters in towns). - The access of rural SMEs to business consultancy services is weak. The Ministry of Economy via the Agency for promotion of SME supported the creation of a network of advisors and promoted voucher system of use of consultancy services. To support the self-employment, the Agency for employment runs a soft loan schemes for business establishment and self-employment. The main interest in using this scheme is agriculture, trading and services, and the lowest interest is in crafts. - The efforts to promote entrepreneurship and crafts in rural areas are constrained by the poor educational status of the labour force and lack of professional experience. - The entrepreneurship promotion schemes operated in rural areas to date, revealed that there is a lack of mature business ideas and entrepreneurial skills and knowledge. Business start-ups are constrained by low incomes/ low purchasing power of rural residents and the saturation of sectors that require low start-up capital (small retail shops, restaurants, communal services). - Out of 37 rural municipalities in total, there are 15 rural municipalities, which are surrounding urban centres (out of which only 7 are surrounding the city of Skopje). In general, these municipalities have a better human resource potential and better opportunities for business development based on efficient integration with urban centres. - The Southeast Planning Region achieves significant results in the economy of the Republic of Macedonia. Following Skopje region, this region has the most dynamic growth. In the economy structure all economic sectors are represented, of which the most important are: agriculture, construction, trade, mining, textile industry, tobacco industry and catering. Even though the industry predominates, services also show an exceptionally dynamic growth. However, the Southeast Planning Region is mainly an agricultural region having excellent climate conditions for the production of early fruit and vegetables, as well as fresh vegetables and fruit - Inadequate coordination of program and activities directed towards different economic sectors in rural areas
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The business demography indicators (number of business entities per 1 000 inhabitants) indicates that SME density in predominantly rural regions is less than the national average (32 per 1 000 inhabitants) while the SME density is relatively high in the intermediate regions (45 per 1 000 inhabitants), reaching the EU 27 average of 45 per 1 000 inhabitants. - Out of 37 rural municipalities in total, there are 15 rural municipalities, which are surrounding urban centres (out of which only 7 are surrounding the city of Skopje).
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (Grozdanic, 2013)
Comment	<p>The area is good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is also worrying is the low share of fixed capital investments of the region in the total level of fixed capital investments of only 4,33% in 2013. This generally indicates that a very small percentage of gains is invested in purchasing new technologies and overall modernisation of companies. Enterprises from the region are still predominantly labour intensive with a low level of technical and technological equipment (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - Low competitiveness of economic activities in rural areas (for example, agriculture, forestry, fishery, food sector, rural tourism, service industry);
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is also worrying is the low share of fixed capital investments of the region in the total level of fixed capital investments of only 4,33% in 2013.
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (Grozdanic, 2013)
Comment	<p>There are enough possibilities for employment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Employment opportunities in rural areas are limited and dominated by agriculture as an economic sector. All these factors limit rural employment and economic growth - The remoteness from large urban centres, small population and low-population density in these municipalities create additional constraints to socio-economic development. The rural areas outside urban municipalities experience higher population decline; have less educated labour force and experienced much higher unemployment rates. In the rural municipalities bordering or near the capital, the socio-economic development can be regarded as positive

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The high unemployment rate of young people (15-24) is an additional problem that leads to the out migration of the young labour force from rural areas to urban centres and abroad - In the predominantly rural regions, 3,8% of the total employment was in the agriculture and food processing sectors. This indicator is even higher bearing in mind that the majority of rural population is engaged in the agricultural sector (mainly subsistence/family farming) either as a main sources of income or as additional activity - A critical weakness in the rural economy is the job creation, high costs of starting up new businesses and of employing new workers. This reason is also found as crucial affecting the national labor market from functioning effectively to reduce unemployment from its historically high levels. High long-term unemployment found in rural areas is related to the poor qualification structure of the unemployed - Unemployment rate is worse in rural than in the urban regions. The average unemployment rate in the predominantly rural regions is above the national unemployment rate (30,5% vs. 29,1%) while the unemployment rate in the intermediate rural regions of 26% is lower than the national average - The rural areas in Macedonia outside urban municipalities experience higher population decline; less access to public services; have less educated labour force; experienced much higher unemployment rates and have lower incomes - The unemployment rate in the Southeast region was significantly higher in urban areas than in rural areas, which is due to the development of agriculture in the region. When it comes to the sex, the situation varies, but over the past two years the unemployment rate has been higher among women (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - Majority of rural women are employed in the textile sector (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014)
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the predominantly rural regions, 3,8% of the total employment was in the agriculture and food processing sectors. - The average unemployment rate in the predominantly rural regions is above the national unemployment rate (30,5% vs. 29,1%) while the unemployment rate in the intermediate rural regions of 26% is lower than the national average
Source	(Ministry of Finance, 2019); (EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017) ; (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014)
Comment	<p>The area offers possibilities for sustainable tourism (cultural heritage, nature, sports, local food, ...)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a good potential for development of tourism in rural municipalities but it is still underdeveloped. ... official statistics do not provide data focused specifically on rural tourism in all its forms. During the period 2008-2012, the leading tourist destinations were the lake areas, the most important one being the lake of Ohrid, followed by Skopje (22%), mountain areas (10%) and Spa's (4%), vacation and recreation and cultural tourism. Estimated 4% of the total accommodation capacities are located in the rural areas. - Currently rural tourism generates a very small share of the national tourism revenues. It is concentrated in a limited number of regions (mainly in the National Parks, East region and natural lakes). During the last few years a few villages located close to the lake resorts also offer rural tourism accommodation. ... Among the greatest obstacles for tourism development in rural areas is insufficient development of tourism attractions and facilities as well as difficult access to tourism amenities, national parks and tourist sites primarily due to the poor condition of the road infrastructure. - There is a significant problem of lack of trained human resources, and of strategic planning and marketing of rural tourism resources and products. - Opportunities offered by heritage and tourism, attracting visitors and contributing to the development of tourism as a growing sector in the national and rural economy. - The villagers have little work experience and tourism related activities; people do not get clear information about the real capacities of alternative tourism; the locals are unaware of the importance of traditional architecture; insufficient awareness of the population about real opportunities for development and supply of tourists
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estimated 4% of the total accommodation capacities are located in the rural areas.
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015); (Empowering rural stakeholders in the Western Balkans, n.d.; Petrovska et al., 2014)
Comment	<p>The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agriculture is a field which provides employment for a large number of workers. - Agriculture represents 9-20% of GDP of Western Balkan countries. - There is some support for organic production, agricultural genetic resources, and some additional support for hilly and mountainous regions, but it is very limited given the potentials and possibilities provided by EU policy. - Main characteristic of Macedonian agriculture is traditional extensive agriculture, which is main precondition for development of organic production. Although organic agricultural production in Republic of Macedonia is one of the fastest growing agribusiness sectors, there is a lack of organization, cooperation, it is necessary to create a policy or strategy
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agriculture represents 9-20% of GDP of Western Balkan countries.
Source	(Grozdanic, 2013); (Hadzi Naumova-Mihajlovska, 2017)
Comment	<p>There are good conditions for development of the agro-processing industry...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the majority of rural regions, manufacturing is represented mainly by small companies, serving local/regional markets. Almost all of the food processing industry (except for meat processing and slaughterhouses) is located in rural areas. In all regions the development of industry is constrained by the quality of road infrastructure and business related infrastructure and increasingly by the shortages of qualified labour
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moderate supporting environment for developing of agro-processing industry

Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	
Comment	<p>Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The findings demonstrate that the employment rate of rural women amounted to 34%, what is lower than the employment rate of men in rural areas (66%). According to the structure of the status of employees in rural areas, women in the “unpaid family workers” category amounted to 8%, compared to women in urban areas amounting to only 1%. Additionally, the data from the field research show that rural women have very low levels of decision-making in the family and leadership of family businesses, especially in the rural areas with predominantly Muslim population - Furthermore, the figures show that the Macedonian rural woman faces various challenges in terms of gender equality in many areas such as: daily activities and households, receiving of incomes (in most cases the rural women occurs as unpaid workers), access to education, participation in decision making at the households level and employment representation in the decision making at local and national levels. Women and men of varying ethnic groupings have varying levels of socio-economic status, political participation, and access to resources, all of which affect their ability to cope with and respond to sustainable development challenges
Definition	
Values	- The findings demonstrate that the employment rate of rural women amounted to 34%, what is lower than the employment rate of men in rural areas (66%).
Source	(Gorgievski & Kovacevikj, 2017)
7. Environment & Biodiversity	
Comment	<p>There are efficient waste management practices by individuals and the business sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In most of the rural populated areas, no collection and depositing of municipal solid waste is performed. - Municipal public enterprises have established a system of collection, transport and depositing of municipal and solid waste for the centres of municipalities and in some cases for larger rural settlements. As a result of this situation, as well as due to the low awareness and poor economic condition of rural population, this waste is treated by incineration or is deposited in illegal landfills which, according to unofficial information, number approximately 700 landfills in the region. They are mostly located in close proximity to villages, near river-beds or on agricultural areas, and as such they pose serious danger causing soil, groundwater and surface waters pollution, and finally, they endanger people’s health. - The situation related to solid waste management at the moment is below any standards in terms of care for the environment. - Environmental monitoring is also put into question taking into consideration that waste management strategies are either outdated or municipalities are not in the financial position to implement them. Municipal and solid waste management is under the jurisdiction of municipalities. They pursue this jurisdiction via municipal public enterprises. - Until now, they have not been coordinated and they have been functioning according to their own regulations which generally create a dysfunctional regional system having negative consequences for the whole planning region. - The waste collection, transport and depositing system does not cover the whole region, i.e. most of the villages are exempted from this system resulting in the existence and continuous creation of new illegal landfills. This is also enabled to a certain degree by the insufficiently developed, i.e. insufficiently precise primary and secondary legislation - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites. Estimated 200 ha are under unorganised waste disposal sites
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites. Estimated 200 ha are under unorganised waste disposal sites - Around 60% - 70% of the population in the Southeast Planning Region is benefiting from the public system for collecting waste performed by public enterprises, but only 10% of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste. General practice is collection of non-separated communal and non-hazardous industrial waste as well as non-hazardous and hazardous non-separated waste fractions
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014)
Comment	<p>Nature in the area is diverse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The condition of environment protection and management of the Southeast Planning Region is relatively good and it gives the region an image of an ecologically clean area. There are major polluters in the region; therefore the diversity of natural resources is still on a relatively good level.
Definition	
Values	- Satisfactory level of diversity in natural resources
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014)
Comment	<p>The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The region is rich in forest and underground waters, rivers, natural lake and a number of artificial accumulations. - Part of the underground waters is known as water with high capacity of geothermal energy. - There are many monuments of nature and natural reserves in the region. - The key identified weakness is that the region lacks a regional strategic document for environment management which points to the fact that the region does not have a clear and common vision, goals, priorities and measures for environment

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The analysis shows that the region has human resources in the private and civil sector, which have some experience and knowledge in sustainable environment management, however there is a lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection. - What is also a weakness for the region is the uncontrolled discharge of waste water and chemical substances in the water and soil as well as the large number of illegal dump sites, which can harm the biodiversity by threatening the water resources, infrastructural capacities, agricultural land and forests in the region.- - The region does not have an efficient regional approach for forest protection, especially with regards to fire and landslides protection. Therefore, there is a need to define measures which will improve the forest protection and system and will provide coverage of the entire region with a fire protection system (The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014) - There are no enterprises in the meat sector which have rendering facilities and waste disposal poses great pressure on the production activity especially in rural areas where the waste disposal systems are underdeveloped. - Abundant land, a favourable climate, Relatively non-polluted environment and agricultural resources - Large areas of agricultural land not polluted and not intensively cultivated
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfactory level of open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery
Source	(The Center for Development of the SE planning region, 2014); (Grozdanic, 2013)
Comment	<p>High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The cultural heritage is located in the rural areas and has the biggest development potential considering the diversity and quality of cultural and historical treasures and archaeological sites in the country and the increasing interest in cultural tourism on the market. There are 15 123 objects registered as immovable cultural heritage (2 567 monuments from the Neolithic to Ottoman historical period archaeological sites 5 160, 4 681 memorial monuments, 1 286 objects of urban, rural and commercial architecture, 29 segments of urban and rural complexes, churches and 1 156 monasteries, 61 medieval buildings, forts, bridges, towers, 112 mosques, 71 other objects originating from 15 to 19 century) and 500 000 museum relics. - Institutional responsibility for cultural heritage is under the Department for Protection of Cultural Heritage under the Ministry of Culture. Currently, there are several rural settlements protected as monuments of culture and natural rarities: Village of Galichnik (from 1975), Rural area Kitchinica (from 2004), Rural area Gari (from 2003), Historical area Smilevo (from 2003), Rural Area Zeleznec (from 2004), Urban area of Village Konjsko (from 1979) and Village Gorno Vranovci (from 1981). According to the National Strategy for cultural development 2013-2017, strategic aim is to decentralise the cultural events from urban to rural areas, thus promoting the cultural heritage, tradition and local values and its link to rural tourism. This also requires development of the road infrastructure as most of the cultural heritage is located in outmost rural areas and the nearby settlements are with less than 150 inhabitants and affected by outward migration.
Definition	
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are 15 123 objects registered as immovable cultural heritage (2 567 monuments from the Neolithic to Ottoman historical period archaeological sites 5 160, 4 681 memorial monuments, 1 286 objects of urban, rural and commercial architecture, 29 segments of urban and rural complexes, churches and 1 156 monasteries, 61 medieval buildings, forts, bridges, towers, 112 mosques, 71 other objects originating from 15 to 19 century) and 500 000 museum relics - Currently, there are several rural settlements protected as monuments of culture and natural rarities: Village of Galichnik (from 1975), Rural area Kitchinica (from 2004), Rural area Gari (from 2003), Historical area Smilevo (from 2003), Rural Area Zeleznec (from 2004), Urban area of Village Konjsko (from 1979) and Village Gorno Vranovci (from 1981).
Source	(EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION, 2015)

Table 51. Mazowieckie / POLAND SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services	-			2019	Rocznik Statystyczny Województwa Mazowieckiego 2018
2. Recreation / social activities	Offer of recreational and social activities for both young and elderly citizens in the region is diverse and depends on the activity of schools and cultural centres. Thus, the more active the employees of these institutions the more developed the offer.				Statistics Poland / Topics / Other studies / Cities, Voivodship / Statistical Atlas Of Mazowieckie Voivodship
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	Very diverse quality and access to housing possibilities				Statistics Poland / Topics / Other studies / Cities, Voivodship /
4. Demographic & human capital	Ageing population				Województwo mazowieckie w liczbach » Przystępne dane
5. Business, economy & innovation	Generally, in Poland, a unitary state, there are hardly any local/regional initiatives offered to encourage entrepreneurs. LAG and local Development Strategies are main local policies supporting the state policy. This can also be done via quality of governance and regional endowment.				PAIH mazowieckie
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	Pressure from agglomeration on cultural offer				Mazowieckie - Polonia Datos y estadísticas - knoema.com
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Farming practises				Mazowieckie - Polonia Datos y estadísticas - knoema.com

Table 52. Segóbriga / SPAIN SWOT Indicators

	Comments	RELATED INDICATORS			
		Definition	Value and units	year	source)
1. Availability of public and other services	Related to ICT and high-speed internet connection	Households with internet access	percentage of total households in the region		Productos y Servicios / Publicaciones / Publicaciones de descarga gratuita (ine.es)
2. Recreation / social activities	The leisure offer is limited and poorly diversified	Number of cinemas, Cultural companies, infrastructure, spending on cultural activities	0	2018	Cultura: Servicio de Estadística de Castilla-La Mancha (jccm.es)
3. Living condition, quality of life and standard of living	Related to quality of life	socioeconomic situation of population, Family Budget, are centers for the homeless			Condiciones de vida: Servicio de Estadística de Castilla-La Mancha (jccm.es)
4. Demographic & human capital	In the territory there is masculinization, and a sustained decline in population.	Population decrease percentage	6%	2014-2018	National Institute of Spain http://www.ies.jccm.es/estadisticas/por-tema/poblacion/padrones-municipales/
	There is a very high emigration from the territory	Percentage increase in emigration in the territory	37%	2014-2018	National Institute of Spain
5. Business, economy & innovation	Related to the innovation	N enterprises, Regional innovation scoreboard		2014-2018	Economía: Servicio de Estadística de Castilla-La Mancha (jccm.es)
	Related to the organic farming	Organic farming	Number of companies		Agricultura: Servicio de Estadística de Castilla-La Mancha (jccm.es)
	Actively promote rural to attract new business	LEADER projects in county Sierra y Mancha Alta Conquense	Nº projects		Microsoft Word - Publicacion 2020 (adesiman.org)
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		health and educational infrastructures	Nº infrastructures		Sociedad: Servicio de Estadística de Castilla-La Mancha (jccm.es)
7. Environment & Biodiversity	Data related to natural spaces, waste management, water supply, etc.				Medio Ambiente: Servicio de Estadística de Castilla-La Mancha (jccm.es)

Annex 10 Responses to the Monitors' Comments and Advisory Board Review

Comments made by the monitors	Section in the text / Explanation	Advisory Board's Comments	Reply to the AB's comments
<p>Overall: document was delayed by several months; for that reason, the needs analysis was linked with collection of policy measures. Did this narrow down the needs assessment or was it positive?</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> Introduction Page 10</p> <p><i>"The extension of T4.3 was justified by Steering Committee. Once the needs were detected, T4.4 could start and both T4.3 and T4.4 were working together in a positive and efficient way."</i></p>	<p>I am not sure whether the explanation provided here and at p.10 properly addresses the comment made by the monitors.</p> <p>In my opinion the monitors are not doubting the need of an extension, rather they would like you to clarify the "effects"/modifications in the workflow between T4.3 and T4.4.</p> <p>Thus, I do not see the value of describing the timeline of the two scenarios in such detail at p.10. Probably, you should provide details on how preliminary/partial results from T4.3 were fed into T4.4 and, most importantly, if there was a feedback loop from T4.4 to T4.3 while the two tasks were active simultaneously (which I think it is what the monitors are asking you to explain).</p> <p>In the first periodic report (p.70), there is written << However, since D4.2 influences other tasks and deliverables, it is decided to provide two sets of results, a preliminary result towards the end of February or early March to allow partners responsible for T4.4, D1.4, D3.2 to proceed as planned and a final result towards the end of May (M12)>>. I guess that is the reason for which the monitors are asking you to elaborate more on the linkages between needs analysis and collection of policy measures.</p> <p>Please also note that the sentence above - reported at pag.70 of the first periodic report - seems to contradict you statement in the << PoliRural_Response_to_Review_Report_Annex.pdf >> where you say << The collection of policies and measures was carried out once the needs identification phase was completed>> (p. 49). I am bit puzzled here, since the two tasks actually overlapped in time once the extension was granted.</p>	<p>The Needs Gathering results have been provided in two stages. Our task 4.3 was coordinated with task T4.4. (policy mapping). In conversations with those responsible for task 4.4, it was seen that they needed to collect the needs of each country independently. Therefore, this work was carried out, and once it was finished it was delivered. (first stage). Thus task 4.4 could progress. After that, our task T4.3 continued with the aggregation and synthesis process, resulting in a single general SWOT and a single set list of Needs (for 12 pilots), and a clustering map of the pillars that framed all the pilots.</p>
<p>Relevant comments made about COVID and the increased importance of teleworking.</p>	<p><i>"TRAGSA takes the comment as positive. No addressed in the text."</i></p>	<p>No comment</p>	
<p>The sections contributed from the pilot teams differ in length and understanding of questions or workshop sections. How will these differences in 'quality' and 'perspective' of the local teams studying the areas impact on the assessment? Overall, the needs assessment does not look fully systematic. For example: Why Greece and Italy did have much fewer survey participants?</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> 2.2 Survey of rural attractiveness in pilot regions Survey Methodology IV Survey Design Page 15</p> <p><i>"In spite of the wide rural diversity in pilot's areas in PoliRural, the methodology used to collect the information allowed to unify and homogenize the analysis."</i></p>	<p>At pag 19 you wrote << Taking into account the aforementioned diversity among the different territories participating in POLIRURAL, each pilot established which was their best spectrum of agents to direct the survey>> .</p> <p>This seems a quite vague statement which may reinforce the monitors' doubt that <<need assessment does not look fully systematic>></p> <p>Perhaps an in-depth reflection on how the diversity of each pilot affects (or not) the composition and size of the corresponding target group is needed here, going through all twelve pilots.</p> <p>Perhaps, in cases such as Italy and Greece, this was an objective limitation to the analysis. If so, this should be acknowledged, and its impact on the assessment evaluated and reported here. In addition, you could also discuss what future actions could be planned to overcome such limitation (for example complementing this analysis with future workshops targeting a larger group where you could reassess/adjust these results).</p> <p>Furthermore, your answer seems to suggest that the issues arisen here by the monitors are overcome by your methodological approach, but to me this is not clear.</p>	<p>The diversity between the 12 pilots does not only refer to the clearly identified differences in terms of number of inhabitants, demographic dynamics, economic activities flow, natural resources and landscapes and other resources of the territory. The diversity among the 12 pilots also refers to governance, which determines the level of social organization existing in each territory. This has been a crucial factor to "Stakeholders engagement". Each territory had a starting point, and in the case of Greece and Italy, in the early stages of the project (when the survey regarding needs was conducted), the size of the SH panel was not very large, because the SH engagement was in a preliminary phase. Progress over time in the involvement of stakeholders, is one of the objectives of POLIRURAL project, from which, as indicated, each pilot started from a different baseline.</p>

Comments made by the monitors	Section in the text / Explanation	Advisory Board's Comments	Reply to the AB's comments
<p>Annex 5 shows the numbers of survey participants, e.g., 2 represent farmers' organisation. This explains why the needs of farming are underrepresented in the needs assessment. In contrast, Flanders has strong focus on farming with numerous representatives from the agricultural sector. There is a bias, even more significant due to Corona restrictions that need reflection.</p>	<p><u>Section 1:</u> Introduction 1.1 Policy context Page 12</p> <p><i>"Although it may seem that there are aspects that are not taken into account, the pilots have been able to make their needs assessment, promoting what distinguishes them the most."</i></p> <p><u>Section 2:</u> 3.3.2 Social Capital Page 58</p> <p><i>"To encourage people to become a farmer is an important factor of attractiveness that must be boosted."</i></p>	<p>I agree with the revision you made in the main text, but I am not sure it is sufficient to mitigate the risk of a bias. I agree with the monitors that there is a high risk of bias in your results due to the composition of the target group.</p> <p>I reiterate here my previous comment: if there is an objective limitation to the analysis, this should be acknowledged, and its impact on the assessment evaluated and reported here. In addition, you could also discuss what future actions could be planned to overcome such limitation (for example complementing this analysis with future workshops targeting a larger and more balanced group where you could reassess/adjust these results).</p>	<p>The Needs Gathering activity was carried out at the beginning of the project, when the group of SH involved was in an incipient phase. The possible biases due to a possible low representation of some group are now being corrected, in the FORESIGHT exercise, since Foresight intends to establish a vision, based on the analysis of the territory (Data, Drivers, Trends). That vision is now more solid and complete, since nowadays the stakeholder panels are more plural and broader.</p>
<p>Some specific details on the questions asked could be carefully scrutinised, for instance survey category distribution - p18 some of the categories could overlap e.g., expert could also be a recent entrant to the rural area?</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> 3 Grass roots needs analysis 3.1 Survey results analysis and pre-clustering Type or organization Page 21</p> <p><i>"The respondent had to choose a single option with which they most felt identified and thus avoid possible overlaps. This together with the participatory and confronted process of the pilots let eliminating the possible bias."</i></p>	<p>*P. 27, sentence <<The survey results were also confronted with different existing indicators at each pilot level that allowed to reduce the possible bias and reinforced the participatory process, leading to the identification of the grass roots needs.>> ...Could you please elaborate on this? It is rather vague...and what are these indicators?</p> <p>**Same for the sentence << ... the process for the identification of the grass root needs based on participatory and developmental process mitigated this risk.>> How exactly? The sentence and concepts behind are not clear to me</p>	<p>*When pilots were asked to prepare a SWOT, including essential aspects of their territory, they were also asked to complete the table called "Comments to the SWOT", in which they were asked to register "information that they consider relevant for the analysis with any explanation, additional on SWOT items. For example, comments on how opinions in the survey match information and indicators in the literature. Also include the indicators used to confirm the SWOT elements".</p> <p>This table was completed by pilots to have a sounder SWOT, as well as to check the coherence with the survey responses. This information is now included as the Annex 9 to the Report.</p> <p>**"Needs Gathering" has been carried out with the participation of stakeholders. Stakeholders have not only filled out a survey but have also participated in meetings where they have expressed their opinion and clarify their contributions to the survey.</p>
<p>Vague and uncritical comments made on some of the questions asked, e.g. 'good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making' - decision making in what?</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> 3.2 Recognising the rural needs through SWOT analysis Table 7 Pillar 6 Social and Cultural aspects. Compilation SWOT. Page 35</p> <p><i>"Decision-making is terminology is used here to refer to the fact that young people have adequate possibilities to participate and contribute with their opinions on the strategies and measures that are applied in the territories."</i></p>	<p>Perhaps the same clarification should be given earlier (e.g., p. 34 of the deliverable)</p>	<p>Definition of "Decision making" is included in pg 20, when this concept is mentioned.</p>

Comments made by the monitors	Section in the text / Explanation	Advisory Board's Comments	Reply to the AB's comments
<p>Regional stakeholders: who was included and why? (p12). Overall, the set-up of the local stakeholder groups and the methodological foundation of the work with the pilots regarding needs assessment require a thorough scientifically based review. This review cannot be delivered by the monitors as part of the first interim review. A review of the stakeholder set-up is strongly recommended in order to ensure a solid basis for all further work in WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7.</p>	<p><u>Section 1:</u> 2.2 Survey of rural attractiveness in pilot regions Survey Methodology I Target audience to be surveyed Page 15</p> <p><i>"T4.3 followed the guidelines explained in D1.3 regarding the set-up of the local stakeholder groups and the methodological foundation of the work with the pilots regarding needs assessment. To build a more solid methodology, T4.3 has been supported by other references."</i></p> <p><u>Section 2:</u> 3.3 Regional clustering based on needs assessment Page 54</p> <p><i>"The steps followed by the pilots to determine their needs were supported by the proposed methodology that allowed, with an overview of all the pilots, to help them select the most relevant needs of their territory."</i></p>	<p>I agree with your revision, but I also suggest referring to the methodology described in the internal deliverable "Stakeholder Mapping & Regional Panel Setup ". Note that I left several comments and suggestions in that internal deliverable which you might find helpful to address this point.</p> <p>In order to properly address this comment by the monitors, you may have to integrate and better document both the methods and <u>the results</u> of the SH mapping done in T4.2. Indeed, I think that the monitors' concern is also about the lack of documentation on how SH mapping was done. In conclusion, it seems to me that the monitors' request is 1) to detail the methodological approach followed for SH mapping and engagement and 2) provide evidence that such method is scientifically sound.</p>	<p>From our point of view, neither to expose the methodological approach followed for SH mapping and engagement, nor to provide evidence that such method is scientifically sound, are tasks of D4.2.</p> <p>The only thing we might include are the channels or tools, that pilots have used to publicize and conduct the survey, but we really don't know if it is of interest.</p>
<p>The report would benefit from an English language check.</p>	<p><i>"We would have appreciated a more detailed comment to address this issue."</i></p>	<p>I do not think this is the right answer. Probably the monitors were unable to be more specific because the document <u>as whole</u> suffers from poor English. Unfortunately, I also recommend a careful check of English (fragmented sentences, mismatch plural vs singular, "at this regard" should be "in this/that regard", too long periods, etc.). There are also many typos in the document.</p>	<p>We will have the services of a company specialized in reviewing documents in English.</p>
<p>How are potential entrants to rural areas defined?</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> 2.2 Survey of rural attractiveness in pilot regions Survey Methodology I Target audience to be surveyed Page 15</p> <p><i>"It is included a clarification about what Potential entrant is."</i></p>	<p>I agree with your clarification. However, it seems in contrast with the SH categories discussed elsewhere (E.g., in T74.2 internal deliverable) where newcomers and potential entrants are grouped together under the same category (and which is probably not advisable anyway).</p>	<p>We followed the guidelines in the D1.3 Needs Gathering & Policy Mapping Template to undertake our task. In this document the concept of "recent or potential newcomers/entrants" was defined.</p> <p>In the updated stakeholder methodology in January this year, the concept of newcomers and potential entrants is included in the same category: rural newcomers: Individuals who are considering relocating to rural area to live or taking up rural employment, or those who have done it very recently (no later than 7 years ago).</p> <p>We understand your point of view that "newcomers" and "potential entrants" shouldn't be grouped under the same category. This issue has also raised in the reviewers' comments to the stakeholder mapping methodology; for this reason, we have contacted those responsible who, as a result of this issue, are analyzing the convenience of addressing this concept in the right tasks in the future of the Project.</p>

Comments made by the monitors	Section in the text / Explanation	Advisory Board's Comments	Reply to the AB's comments
<p>p.58 calls for having rural proofing on all policies (similar to gender and environment), but research shows that rural proofing is not necessarily effective.</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> 4 Challenges <u>Page 65</u></p> <p><i>"It is necessary to formulate a coordinated rural development policy that encompasses all the different needs of rural regions and the different public or private actors."</i></p>	<p>I am bit confused here. In my view, the monitors are referring to the sentence <<it can be highlighted that there is a specific need to include a rurality view in all the different policies and actions to be developed, as it has been promoted for other policies with regard to gender equality and environmental aspects>>.</p> <p>According to the monitors, you claim-through this sentence- that rural proofing emerged as a main need of the pilots. On the other hand, the monitors point out that rural proofing is not necessarily effective.</p> <p>Thus, the real question posed to you by the monitors seems to be: is fulling this need (i.e. doing rural proofing) going to be effective in your case (i.e. for the pilots)? Have you taken into consideration the risk of ineffectiveness?</p> <p>I might have misinterpreted, but it seems that you did not answer to these questions.</p>	<p>In D4.2., an example of an adequate application of rural proofing has been included. It is clear that there is always a risk in policy design and application, but to minimize it, evaluation processes are carried out. In case of "environment proofing" or "equality proofing", there are many cases of success but also of failure, and not for this reason, the idea of including these transversal elements in the policy design is abandoned. Therefore, we consider of interest to maintain the recommendation established in D4.2 to deepen in rural proofing.</p> <p>We consider the concept of "Rural proofing" of interest also because it is explicitly included in the Commission's "Long-term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas - Towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040" (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/es/ip_21_3162) which has just been published.</p>
<p>How does gender sit within 'cultural appeal', p. 63; many other curious connections in these cluster maps.</p>	<p><u>Section:</u> 4 Challenges <u>Page 61</u></p> <p><i>"Sometimes changing a word better explains a concept."</i></p>	<p>Your strategy was to replace the word "appeal" with "diversity": I would recommend doing it throughout the entire document (starting from the executive summary), not just pag.60</p> <p>Maybe a more elaborated answer would have been more appropriate: what concept are you referring to?</p> <p>Plus, you did not really answer to the question (i.e., gender vs cultural diversity)</p>	<p>We have replaced "Appeal" for "Diversity" along the D4.2. Thank you!</p> <p>We also changed the text in order to connect the concepts involved.</p> <p>1.1.1 Cultural diversity</p> <p>This category includes those needs integrated in the Pillar 2: Recreational and social activities and Pillar 6: Social and cultural aspects</p> <p>Within Pillar 6 two needs are expressed in (Figure 17). One related to the gender equality issues and the enhancement of rural population in decision making with a special concern to women and youth, as well of minorities. Masculinization is a general problem in rural areas, due to the abandonment of women looking for new opportunities in urban areas. This results in a society with a lack of capacity for social, economic and cultural progress. This also includes a loss of rural traditions, and minor identity and belonging feelings.</p> <p>So, it is important to boost policies for the permanence of women in rural territories, and to promote their role in a broad sense (political, professional, social, etc.).</p> <p>Some changes in the D4.2 deliverable regarding "Cultural diversity": Pages: Executive Summary (8), 3.3.3 section ((60), Figure 21 (70)</p>
		<p>Additional comments:</p> <p>It might be helpful for the reader to add a section before section 3.1.1, where a synthesis of the need assessment is presented individually for each pilot. I recommend this for three reasons 1) I found difficult to follow and appreciate the result of the cluster analysis not having in mind the specific characteristics and needs of each pilot; 2) in many instances, you highlighted that diversity of each pilots, therefore it makes sense to discuss here how such diversity impacts the need assessment done in each pilot; 3) this might be the best place to address the risk of bias in the result which you experienced in some of the pilots and to detail how you dealt/are going to deal with them (cf. my comments above).</p>	<p>We agree with your valuable comment about including an individualized assessment of the pilots' needs. This list of needs for each pilot is included in Annex 7. We have considered a synthetic and simple format to show the information to be as much understandable as possible.</p>